

Discussion paper and infographic(s) on trends in agri-food trade

MATS Deliverable 1.2

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Summary

The present discussion paper examines trends in the agri-food trade by focusing on six agri-food products traded globally namely: Wine, Dairy, Beef, Pork, Poultry, and Coffee. The study analyses global trade trends of these agri-food products and the impact of socioeconomic factors [such as GDP (Gross Domestic Product) and common language], geographical distance, various trade policies (e.g., tariffs, and non-tariff measures such as Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards, Technical Barriers to Trade and other non-tariff measures), and regimes [e.g., trade agreements, trade between the EU (European Union) and the rest of the World, EU-Africa, and EU-UK] on their trade flows.

The study uses network analysis in examining global trade trends for the 2009-2019 period. In general, networks are a way of depicting a system's structure that serves as a link between empirical data and a diverse set of sophisticated analysis techniques. The European Commission designs and promotes policy networks in almost all policy fields (Ahrens, 2018). Thus, understanding the overall policymaking process in multilevel governance systems such as the EU requires knowledge of networks and acknowledgment of support instruments throughout the CAP (Common Agricultural Policy).

The findings of the network analysis -with the assumptions mentioned in the network analysis section in each product- indicate the following, in regard to each examined product:

- **Wine market:** Our study reveals that the main feature throughout the reference years is the dominance of the EU, as a core player. France and Italy are the leading countries with strong trade flows within the continent, as well as outside of it. Furthermore, the Netherlands appears to have increased its trade flows through the reference years. Another crucial node with strong trade flows to the EU is the USA (United States of America). Moreover, the substantial trade flows between the UK (United Kingdom) and other countries, imply that the BREXIT (British Exit) will cause difficulties and fluctuations in wine trading. More precisely, the BREXIT will cause shifts in wine trade agreements that have been signed between the EU and Australia, South Africa, and the USA. Trade linkages/connections with Africa appear to be insignificant. Finally, the statistical analysis

presented via bar charts shows that the top wine exporters in 2019 are France, Italy, Spain, Australia, Chile, the USA, New Zealand, Germany, Portugal, Argentina, the UK, and South Africa. In the same year, the top importers are the USA, the UK, China, Germany, Canada, Hong Kong, the Netherlands, Japan, Switzerland, Belgium, the Russian Federation, and France.

- Dairy market: For all benchmark years, we observe that, in terms of trade flows, the robust European economies like Germany, France, the Netherlands, Italy, and Spain are the leading players, keeping strong relations between them and other countries. Furthermore, dairy trade flows have been substantially increased from the year 2013 to 2016 in some countries, like France, the Netherlands, and Germany. This might have been caused by changes in the 2014 CAP, which affected the dairy sector. Similarly, the USA, Australia, and China represent another significant group, which is characterized by its significant trade flows in the dairy industry. On the other hand, the UK holds a moderate position in the network with both strong and weak trade flows with various partners, indicating that the BREXIT may have a small effect on dairy international trade. Moreover, South Africa's presence on the network is weak. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top dairy exporters in 2019 are Germany, New Zealand, the Netherlands, France, the USA, Italy, Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, Poland, the UK, Belarus, and Australia. In the same year, the top importers are Germany, China, the Netherlands, Italy, the UK, France, Belgium, Russia, Spain, the USA, Japan, Mexico, and Saudi Arabia.
- Beef market: The findings demonstrate strong trade flows between countries, whereas a large number of countries appear to have large participation, according to all measures of the network analysis. A reason could be the EU and USA's exceptional market support measures, when specific circumstances mean that public support is required, for example, in cases of animal diseases or a loss of consumer confidence. Across all benchmark years, we observe that Brazil is a central player. The USA is another substantial pole, in terms of substantial trade value flows, keeping strong flows with other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. In the same vein is the presence of the EU, holding a core position in the network. On the other hand, some

MERCOSUR (Mercado Común del Sur) countries, like Paraguay and Uruguay, appear to have moderate trade flows. South Africa maintains a modest position in terms of trade flows. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top beef exporters in 2019 are Australia, Brazil, the USA, Argentina, India, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Ireland, Canada, Uruguay, Poland, Mexico, and France. In the same year, the top importers are China, the USA, Japan, South Korea, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Hong Kong, France, Vietnam, the UK, Chile, and Russia.

- **Pork market:** The network analysis highlights the changes in the global trade of the pork sector. More precisely, across all benchmark years, we observe that the strong European economies like Germany, France the Netherlands, Italy, and Spain are the leading players, in terms of substantial trade value flows, keeping strong trade flows between them and other countries. Similarly, the USA, Australia, and China represent another significant group, which is characterized by its strong trade flows in the pork industry. The boosting trade role of China is noteworthy, having increased its trade flows, especially between 2010 and 2013. On the other hand, the UK holds a moderate position in the network with both strong and weak trade flows with various partners, indicating that the BREXIT will cause a small effect on pork international trade. Just like the case with wine and dairy, Africa's presence is not noticeable in the pork trade. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top pork exporters in 2019 are the USA, Spain, Germany, Denmark, the Netherlands, Canada, Belgium, Brazil, France, Poland, and Mexico. In the same year, the top importers are China, Japan, Italy, Germany, Poland, South Korea, Mexico, the UK, the USA, France, Czechia, Hong Kong, and Romania.
- **Poultry market:** Our research reveals the importance of the USA and Brazil as central trade players, for all benchmark years. Over the years, there are strong network flows between these top countries and other continents. The USA appears to connect strongly with Europe, Asia, and Africa. On the other hand, Brazil appears to be forming an opposite pole, connecting with Russia's, Mexico's, and Korea's massive markets. Additionally, certain nations, such as Jordan, Sweden, Malaysia, and South Africa are on the margin of the trade flow. Furthermore, poultry products, which are practically not marketable in Europe, were sold on African

markets for a much lower price than local poultry products. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top poultry exporters in 2019 are Brazil, the USA, the Netherlands, Poland, Thailand, Chile, Honk Kong, Argentina, and Germany. In the same year, the top importers are China, Japan, Hong Kong, Saudi Arabia, Germany, Mexico, the UK, France, Vietnam, the United Arab Emirates, South Africa, South Korea, the Netherlands, and Iraq.

- Coffee market: Globally, coffee is the second most traded commodity and thus plays a vital role in the balance of trade between developed and developing countries, providing the latter with an important source of export earnings. Our analysis illustrates that South America is a central player in the coffee sector. More precisely, Colombia, Brazil, and Chile have leading roles in the international trade of coffee. Furthermore, Europe has also a significant role in the network. More precisely, Germany, Italy, the UK, Belgium, and many other nations, have strong trade flows with a large number of European countries, the USA, and Brazil. Japan and Indonesia appear to hold a moderate place. On the contrary, many countries have been placed in the margin of the network, like El Salvador, Nicaragua, and Slovakia. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top coffee exporters in 2019 are Brazil, Vietnam, Germany, Colombia, Switzerland, Italy, France, Honduras, Indonesia, Ethiopia, the Netherlands, Belgium, the USA, Guatemala, and Peru. In the same year, the top importers are the USA, Germany, France, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, Japan, Canada, Spain, the UK, Poland, and South Korea.

A literature review was performed on gravity models, to identify the main determinants of trade flows; six different products were considered within this review, namely, beef, coffee, dairy, pork, poultry, and wine. Based on the review, a variety of factors affecting trade were identified, in the context of a) financial [e.g. Dascal *et al.* (2002), Pinilla and Serrano (2008), Gouveia *et al.* (2018)], b) socioeconomic [e.g. Fathelrahman *et al.* (2014), Hndi *et al.* (2016), Sanjuan *et al.* (2017)], c) geographical [e.g. Owen and Winchester (2014), Santeramo *et al.* (2019), Zaninovic *et al.* (2021)], d) historical and cultural [e.g. Castillo *et al.* (2016), Dal Bianco *et al.* (2016), Lombardi *et al.* (2016)], e) policy and market [e.g. Kalaba and Kirsten (2012), Balogh and Jámbor (2018), Macedo *et al.* (2019)], f) food-safety [e.g. Wilson *et al.* (2003), Sun *et al.* (2014), Ishaqa *et al.* (2015)], and g) trade-related [e.g.

Pokrivcak *et al.* (2013), Sanjuán López *et al.* (2013), Owen and Winchester (2014)] aspects. In particular, the following determinants of trade flows can be reported: trading partners' GDP, population, commodity production, and trade openness; product export price; common currency, exchange rate; foreign direct investments to the exporting country; overall political and economic conditions (e.g. global economic recession); distance between countries (in terms of distance between capitals or major economic centers); common border; trading partner being landlocked; climate conditions (referring to products sensitive to climatic anomalies and variations); historical and cultural factors (common language, religion, legal system; colonial and historical ties); institutional quality; participation in Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) and Free Trade Agreements (FTAs). Other factors are tariffs imposed by the importer; Non-Tariff Measures (NTMs) imposed by the importer; product-specific aspects related to trade and food-safety-policies [e.g., H1N1-related ban for pork, food-safety related incidents (e.g. China's melamine-related incident in dairy products), specific regulations (e.g. on pesticides' maximum levels and veterinary drugs), Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE) (relevant to beef), Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD) (relevant to beef and pork), and Avian Influenza (AI) outbreaks (relevant to poultry)].

The study also uses gravity models for three products (i.e., wine, dairy, and beef) to analyze the effects of socioeconomic factors, geographical distance, and various trade policies on agri-food trade flows. The results of the gravity model for the 2009-2019 period indicate the following:

- Wine: the exporter's wine production and the importer's per capita GDP have a positive effect on wine trade flows (i.e., 1% increase in exporter wine production tends to increase wine trade by about 0.18%, while a 1% increase in importer per capita GDP would increase wine trade by about 0.26%); the distance between trading partners has a negative impact on trade (i.e., a 1% increase in the distance between two countries' capitals tends to reduce trade by about 0.33%); *ad valorem* equivalent tariffs have a negative but minimal impact on the wine trade (i.e., a 1% increase in the tariff rate will decrease trade by about 0.096%); among the NTMs (Non-Tariff Measures) (i.e., Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards, Technical Barriers to Trade and other NTMs), only the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards have a significant and negative effect on trade

(i.e., a 1% increase in Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards in the importing country will reduce trade flows by 0.44%); regional trade agreements have a relatively significant positive effect on trade (i.e., a 1% increase of regional trade agreements increases trade by 0.454%); the EU is a significant exporter in the global wine trade because trade flows are greater by 0.41% when the export country is an EU country, compared to the case where the exporting country is not an EU country; UK trade with the rest of the world (excluding the EU countries) is vital because trade between the UK and the rest of the world is greater by 1.22% compared to the average global wine trade; given the significant role of the UK on the global wine trade, the BREXIT would harm the EU's international trade position; temperature and precipitation in the exporting countries have small positive effects on trade flows.

- Dairy: the importer's GDP positively affects dairy trade flows (a 1% increase in importer GDP would increase dairy trade by about 0.38%); the distance between trading partners harms trade (a 1% increase in distance tends to reduce trade by about 0.63%); *ad valorem* equivalent tariffs have a negative but minimal impact on the dairy trade (a 1% increase in the tariff rate will decrease trade by about 0.103%); all NTMs (i.e., Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards, Technical Barriers to Trade, and other NTMs) have a significant negative impact on trade with the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards decreasing trade by about 0.22%, Technical Barriers to Trade reducing trade by about 0.23% and other NTMs decreasing trade by about 0.17%; regional trade agreements, as well as a common language, have a relatively substantial positive effect on trade with about 0.40% the first, and about 0.89% the latter; EU is a significant exporting region (with exports about 1.77% greater than the average global exports) but a less significant importing region (with trade imports about 0.42% below the average global imports); trade between the UK and the rest of the world (excluding the EU) is not that strong (being about 1.33% below the average global trade) indicating that the BREXIT will not affect the EU's global dairy trade position; the trading partnership between EU and African countries is about 0.74% less than the average international dairy trade.
- Beef: exporters' beef production and importers' GDP have a positive effect on beef trade flows with the first having an impact of about 0.11% and the

latter of about 0.42%; the distance between trading partners has a negative impact on beef trade of about 0.21%; tariffs do not have any significant effect on beef trade flows; among the NTMs, Technical Barriers to Trade restrain beef trade by about 0.25%, other NTMs reduce trade by about 0.14%, while the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards are not affecting beef trade; regional trade agreements, as well as a common language, have a relatively significant positive effect on trade with the first affecting trade by 0.34% while the latter by 0.68%; EU beef exports to the rest of the world are close to the average global beef exports, while EU beef imports are well below the average international beef imports by about 1.30%; beef trade flows within the EU are well above that of the average global beef trade by about 2.48%, indicating that the EU supports trade creation between EU members and trade diversion from non-members to members; the trade between the UK and the rest of the world (excluding the EU) is about 0.51% less than the average international beef trade, indicating that the BREXIT will not affect the EU's global beef trade position given the strong beef trading connections between the European countries excluding the UK; the trading partnership between EU and African countries is less than the average international beef trade by about 0.68%; MERCOSUR countries have a significant positive impact on the global beef trade by about 1.69%.

The analytical frameworks, the tools, and the data sources provided in the present study serve MATS to achieve its objective to identify key leverage points that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agricultural trade on environmental sustainability and human well-being. The current report provides socio-economic data and indicators that will be combined with the data and indicators of the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) in WP2 to form a complete data set needed in the analysis of WP3. Furthermore, the network analysis and gravity models developed in the present study form the basis for a systematic and in-depth understanding of the linkages between agricultural trade, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being within the 15 case studies examined in WP3. In a forthcoming updated version of D1.2, the gravity models of the present study will be expanded and re-estimated with additional variables (such as environmental and sustainability indicators as well as more specific economic variables like investments) to provide information about changes in the climate and the

SDGs on the international trade flows. This analysis was not yet feasible due to the lack of appropriate environmental and sustainability indicators and investment data. The update will be possible upon the successful completion of WPs 2 and 3.

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Avian Influenza
APEC	Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
BACI	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International
BREXIT	British Exit
BSE	Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CEPII	Centre d' Etudes Prospectives et d' Informations Internationales
CER	Closer Economic Relations
COMESA	Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa
CPTPP	Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership
EAC	East African Community
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EU	European Union
FAS	Foreign Agricultural Service
FSIS	Food Safety Inspection Service
FTA	Free Trade Agreement
FMD	Foot and Mouth Disease
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Council
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GNP	Gross National Product
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis Project
H1N1	Hemagglutinin Type 1 and Neuraminidase Type 1
HACCP	Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point
HIT	Heterogeneity Indexes of Trade
HMD	Hoof-and-Mouth Disease
HPAI	Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza

HS	Harmonized System
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
I-TIP	Integrated Trade Intelligence Portal
JEFTA	Japan-EU Free Trade Agreement
MERCOSUR	Mercado Común del Sur (Southern Common Market)
MFN	Most-Favored-Nation
NAFTA	North American Free Trade Agreement
ND	Newcastle Disease
NTM	Non-Tariff Measure
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
PAI	Probabilistic Affinity Index
PPML	Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood
QWPDR	Quality Wines Produced in Determined Regions
RTA	Regional Trade Agreement
SADC	Southern African Development Community
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SITC	Standard International Trade Classification
SPS	Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards
TARIC	TARif Intégré Communautaire (Integrated Tariff of the European Communities)
TBT	Technical Barriers to Trade
TCI	Trade Complementary Index
TRAINS	Trade Analysis Information System
TRQ	Tariff Rate Quotas
UK	United Kingdom
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
USA	United States of America
USD	United States Dollar
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture

WGI	Worldwide Governance Indicator
WP	Work Package
WTO	World Trade Organization
WWI	World War I

1 Introduction

This discussion paper aims to investigate the goals set by Task 1.2 of Work Package 1 (WP1 – Mapping linkages) of the EU funding MATS project. Based on the description of the action of the MATS project for WP1-T1.2, the present discussion paper aims to *“analyze and map EU agri-food trade flows in global trade. The analysis includes the identification of trends in trade and trade regimes, such as increasingly protectionist policies in some significant economies, possible trade disturbances linked to BREXIT, or the role of the CAP in supporting competitiveness, innovation in the agri-food sector, and food product quality.”*

The analysis provided in T1.2 of WP1 contributes to the development of the analytical framework, tools, and indicators in T2.1-2.2 of WP2. T1.2 uses network analysis, a powerful tool to map trade linkages between different countries for a series of agri-food products traded internationally (i.e., wine, dairy, beef, pork, poultry, and coffee). Furthermore, the present analysis reviews several academic studies performed in the same series of agri-food products, to identify various socioeconomic factors and changes in trade regimes and policies that affect global trade. In addition, the present report develops and applies gravity models for wine, dairy, and beef for the 2009-2019 period, to estimate and analyze various changes in economic activities and trade policies on international trade flows of these agri-food products. Thus, the analytical frameworks, the tools, and the data sources provided in the present study could be helpful for WP3, which performs a set of 15 case studies that are central in giving an in-depth contextual understanding of the sustainability impacts of agricultural trade. Note that the case studies provided in T1.2 of WP1 support WP3 to investigate the linkage of the case studies developed there, to the agricultural market, trade, and investment dynamics. In a forthcoming updated version of D1.2, the gravity models of the present report will be expanded and re-estimated with additional variables (such as environmental and sustainability indicators as well as more specific economic variables like investments) to measure the effect of climate change and the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) improvement on the international trade flows. Unfortunately, this analysis was not feasible due to the lack of appropriate environmental and sustainability indicators and investment data. The update will be possible upon the successful completion of WPs 2 and 3.

This discussion paper achieves its aim by examining trade flows of six main agri-food product categories, i.e., wine, dairy, beef, pork, poultry, and coffee, in a global context. In the first step, we use network analysis to analyze and map agri-food trade linkages. In general, networks are a common way of depicting a system's structure that serves as a link between empirical data and a diverse set of sophisticated analysis techniques. The European Commission designs and promotes policy networks in almost all policy fields (Ahrens, 2018). Thus, understanding the overall policymaking process in multilevel governance systems such as the EU (European Union) requires knowledge of networks.

Before moving into the intricacies of the research, it is important to address a fundamental question: why do we want to use Network Analysis to examine international trade data? Network analysis provides useful tools to visualize and synthetically represent international trade flows. Particularly, it allows for structurally studying trade linkages, taking into account the interdependence among all participant countries (De Benedictis *et al.*, 2014; Amador *et al.*, 2018). Thus, trade relations between each country pair are not analyzed in isolation but consider the full set of relations in the network (i.e., each country's relation with each other participating country).

Social networks are characterized by a high degree of heterogeneity and a power-law distribution of the network's nodes' topological features. Using centrality measurements, we will quantify nation heterogeneity in the World Trade Network. Because of this heterogeneity, a detailed structural analysis of the entire collection of network relations is required. This is exactly what is going to be emphasized in the next sections.

As a second step, we use gravity analysis to examine the impact of socioeconomic factors [such as GDP (Gross Domestic Product), common language], geographical distance, and various trade policies and regimes on agri-food trade flows.

The gravity model is one of the most well-known models in applied international trade research (Head and Mayer, 2014). The model, like the name indicates, applies Newton's gravitational idea to the issue of any kind of exchange between two groups. Tinbergen (1962) and Pöyhönen (1963) created the gravity model of international commerce separately. In its simplest version, the volume of trade between two nations is considered to grow in size (measured in national income), while decreasing based on the cost of transportation between them (measured by the distance between their economic centers. The GDP is commonly used to assess the economic size, whereas distance can refer to a geographic term, but it can also refer to other trade frictions or trade facilitators (Macedo *et al.*, 2020). Linnemann (1966) was the first to establish the most prevalent justification for the gravity model, i.e., that the gravity model is a simplified version of a "four-equation partial equilibrium model of export supply and import demand".

The theoretical foundations of the gravity model were further refined by Anderson (1979) and Bergstrand (1985; 1989). Anderson (1979) worked to create a theoretical foundation for the gravity equation by employing an expenditure system under the premise of homothetic preferences across regions, while Bergstrand (1985; 1989) developed a gravity model as a simplified version of a partial equilibrium demand-supply model.

The gravity model for a single agricultural commodity was revised by Koo *et al.* (1994), who showed in their study that "the gravity model for a single agricultural commodity can be parameterized more effectively by using time series and cross-section data rather than cross-section data alone".

The final section (i.e., Section 8) of this discussion paper presents an overview of the main findings and the literature review performed in it to explicitly show that it achieves the aims set by the description of the action of the MATS project for WP1-T1.2. In particular:

- Table 8.1 presents the most significant exporters and importers in global trade for each agri-food market under consideration.
- Table 8.2 presents an overview of the literature by categorizing the relevant studies based on their findings regarding the specific research areas described in the description of the action of the MATS project for WP1-T1.2. The categorization provided in Table 8.2 includes the effect on agri-food trade flows of trade regimes, trade competitiveness and innovation in the agri-food sector, and food product quality. The review also identified additional categories considered in the international literature, but they are not included in the description of the action of the MATS project for WP1-T1.2. Among these categories are GDP/income, population/area, production/consumption, geography, historical/cultural ties, climate/weather, and institutions/infrastructure/investment.
- Table 8.3 presents the main findings of the gravity models estimated for three product categories (i.e., wine, dairy, and beef). Gravity models were estimated to satisfy specific descriptions of the MATS project's action for WP1-T1.2. Such as the effect on international trade flows due to increasingly protectionist policies in some significant economies or possible trade disturbances linked to BREXIT. An additional variable, such as an EU variable, is included explicitly in the models to draw inferences about CAP competitiveness (i.e., how EU's trade is positioned relative to the global agri-food trade flows). Furthermore, based on the literature, variables like GDP, production, distance, common language are also included in the models, even though they are not considered in the description of T1.2 for obtaining unbiased empirical results. Finally, trade regime protectionist policies, captured by variables like trade agreements, tariffs, NTMs, are also considered, as required by the description of T1.2.

The present report provides essential information for future developments of MATS. This information includes:

- Identification of the leading international agri-food trade players.
- Identification of the main socio-economic factors affecting agri-food trade flows.
- Development of gravity models capable of answering questions imposed in WP1-T1.2.
- The gravity models used in WP1-T1.2 can answer questions in WP3 (which aims to investigate the linkage between agricultural market, trade, and investment dynamics) if adequately mortified and supplied with appropriate data (i.e., environmental, sustainability, and investment data).
- Finally, Tables 2.3.2, 3.3.1, and 4.3.1 of the present discussion paper provide useful data sources which can be used in WP2 and WP3.

2 WINE

2.1. Network analysis and results of the wine international market

This section examines the world's major wine exporters and importers, using data on trade flows coverage time from 2010 to 2019. We consider a reliable data set stemming from the BACI (Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International) dataset from CEPII (Centre d' Etudes Prospectives et d' Informations Internationales), the leading French center for research and expertise on the world economy. We selected wine bottles with a capacity of less than 2 liters from the initial database, using the 6 digit Harmonized System, for our research. Furthermore, our sample consists of those countries with a value of wine trade flows greater than 1% of the total global wine trade. This threshold is used to exclude small trade flows, to eliminate unnecessary noise originating from such trades. A detailed list of the counties with their ISO 3 code is found in Appendix A1.

The international wine trade has experienced considerable growth, but this is only one of the aspects of the complex evolution of the global wine sector. There have been significant shifts in the geography of production and consumption as well as the direction of export flows (Anderson and Nelgen, 2011a; Banks and Overton, 2010; Mariani *et al.*, 2011). The considerable growth of the international wine trade has led wine producers to maintain a more prominent position in the world wine market (Anderson 2004).

Figure 2.1.1 illustrates the top wine exporters in 2010 as the reference year. This graph makes it possible to acknowledge where each country fits into the overall trade. According to this, France, Italy, Australia, Spain, and Chile are the worldwide leading countries in wine exports in 2010, based on export value. Germany, the USA (United States of America), Portugal, and New Zealand have also a prominent position in the trade. On the other hand, the remaining countries, Argentina, South Africa, and the UK (United Kingdom) have a comparably lower trade export value.

Figure 2.1.1

Continuing to Figure 2.1.2, we display the top wine exporters in 2013 as the reference year. We observe a similar interpretation as in Figure 2.1.1. The top wine exports are now France, Italy, Spain, Chile, and Australia, with the USA, Germany, New Zealand, Portugal, Argentina, the UK, and South Africa having a secondary, but still significant role. The structure of the figure indicates, as in Figure 2.1.1, that the major European economies play leading roles in wine exports. Remarkably, Chile presents a boosting performance in relation to 2010.

Figure 2.1.2

Figure 2.1.3 has an almost identical form to Figure 2.1.2. The benchmark year for this analysis is 2016. France, Italy, Spain, Chile, Australia, and the USA are the dominant countries concerning wine exports for years 2013 and 2016. Argentina has a dynamic shift forward and China’s s emerging economy introduces its prominent role in the wine sector. In terms of export value, the UK and South Africa are at the bottom of the ranking.

Figure 2.1.3

Figure 2.1.4, illustrates the most recent data we have, concerning wine exports, for the benchmark year 2019. This visualization offers a similar pattern to the previous years’ export trends of the wine sector and allows to stronger recognize the core role

of the European countries in the wine trade. France, Italy, and Spain, once more, are the dominant players, followed by Australia, Chile, the USA, New Zealand, Denmark, Portugal, and the less favorable Argentina, UK, and South Africa.

Figure 2.1.4

In the following Figures 2.1.5 through 2.1.8 we present the major wine importers with the assumptions introduced at the beginning of our analysis. A quite different scenario is depicted in comparison to the wine export flows. At a first glance, we notice that the import wine trends include a large number of countries. Furthermore, the leading exporting countries have dropped to the bottom of the ranking, concerning imports.

Figure 2.1.5 illustrates the top wine importers for the year 2010. The world’s largest economy by nominal GDP and net wealth, the USA, holds a prominent position, with the UK, Germany, Canada, the Netherlands, and Hong Kong composing a mainstream second pole. In this line, we observe the vital footprint of China’s emerging economy and Japan as the other Asiatic node. From the EU, Sweden and Ireland have a limited import value as depicted in Figure 2.1.5.

Figure 2.1.5

In Figure 2.1.6 which displays the reference year 2013 of wine importers, we have an almost identical visualization, in relation to Figure 2.1.5. China’s boosting role in trade is a determinant factor in this visualization.

Figure 2.1.6

Figures 2.1.7 and 2.1.8 illustrate the major importing countries for the benchmark years of 2016 and 2019, respectively. The most notable aspect is that we have a similar scenario in terms of importing countries’ volume, with the exception that China has begun to emerge as a central player.

Figure 2.1.7

Figure 2.1.8

Although global trade patterns have considerably changed over time, it is worth noting that France, Italy, and Spain have long been major destinations for wine exports, while the USA and the UK are the primary importing countries. On the other hand, Africa appears to have limited trade flows. Besides, trade is low in Africa and the continent is increasingly marginalized in world trade (Zhang and Batinge, 2021).

In what follows we will quantify the heterogeneity of countries in the world trade network by using measures of centrality. In particular, we focus on centrality measures to describe the degree of heterogeneity across countries in bilateral trade flows. We illustrate in detail the centrality measures of the world trade network in 2010, 2013, 2016, and 2019. Network analysis dispenses several indicators for evaluating the importance of a node, mapping different aspects of its position (Borgatti, 2005). Our methodology includes all the criteria described above, with the distinction that our sample consists of those countries with a value of wine trade flows greater than 100 million dollars.

In social network research, centrality is one of the most studied topics. A significant number of measures have been developed, including degree centrality, closeness, betweenness, eigenvector centrality, information centrality, flow betweenness, the rush index, the influence measures of Katz (1953), Hubbell (1965), Taylor's (1969) measure, etc.

Eigenvector centrality, also called eigencentality, is a measure of the influence of a node in a network. It assigns relative scores to all nodes in the network based on the concept that connections to high-scoring nodes contribute more to the score of the node in question than equal connections to low-scoring nodes. A node is important if it is linked to other important nodes. The centrality of each node is proportional to the sum of the centralities of those nodes to which it is connected. In general, nodes with high eigenvector centralities are those which are linked to many other nodes which are, in turn, connected to many others. The notion is that even if a node just influences one other node, which then influences other nodes (who in turn influence even more nodes), the first node in the chain is extremely powerful. At the same time, eigenvector centrality can be viewed as a model of nodal risk in which a node's long-term equilibrium risk of receiving traffic is a function of its contacts' risk levels.

Centrality Authority is the generalization of eigenvector centrality. The hubs and authorities' centrality scores are two linked centrality measures that are recursive. The hubs score of a node is the sum of the authorities' scores of all its successors. Similarly, the authorities' score is the sum of the hubs' scores of all its predecessors. The sum of all hubs scores is 1 and the sum of all authorities' scores is also 1.

Centrality Hub is another generalization of eigenvector centrality. According to Fahren et. al (2019) study, the effect of changes in weight using the Probabilistic Affinity Index (PAI) on the results of measurements of Hubs and Authorities Centrality is the change in the centrality value and the change in the highest user order.

Another well-known centrality measure is betweenness centrality (Freeman, 1979). Betweenness quantifies the number of times a node acts as a bridge along the shortest path between two other nodes. The betweenness centrality type measures how often each graph node appears on the shortest path between two nodes in the graph. It is a way of detecting the amount of influence a node has over the flow of information in a graph. It is often used to find nodes that serve as a bridge from one part of a graph to another. If the quickest way between any two nodes on a network disproportionately involves certain nodes, then they are important in terms of global cohesion. Furthermore, betweenness centrality is a useful measure in the cases when a node is important as an intermediary i.e. in a communication network. A node is crucial in the transmission of information if flows of information are disrupted or must make a longer path if that node stops passing information or if it disappears from the network. However, in the case of aggregate or sectoral trade flows, this measure seems not well suited for an application to bilateral trade relationships, unless it would be possible to distinguish among trade flows in final products and intermediate products.

A node's closeness centrality is the sum of graph-theoretic distances from all other nodes, where the distance from a node to another is defined as the length (in links) of the shortest path from one to the other, as Freeman (1979) has first described. In a connected graph, the normalized closeness centrality (or closeness) of a node is the average length of the shortest path between the node and all other nodes in the graph. Thus, the more central a node is, the closer it is to all other nodes. Closeness centrality measures how many steps are required to access every other node from a given node. It describes the distance of a node to all other nodes. The more central a node is, the closer it is to all other nodes. The closeness centrality can also be interpreted as the inverse of the proportion between the shortest of the shortest paths and the sum of the actual shortest paths. In this case, the closeness of a node is measured in terms of the sum of the inverse edge weights of this node to all the other nodes in the network (Swain and Ranganathan, 2021).

Each node represents a country in the network, which is denoted with its corresponding 3-code acronym. Different lines connect different countries. These lines represent the volume of the trade flows between the countries depicted. Therefore, in what follows we display our analysis for the visualization of the data. In Appendix B1 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016.

We illustrate the network analysis for the years 2010, 2013, 2016, and 2019 respectively, based on eigenvector centrality. In Figure 2.1.9 we have the network analysis for wine in the reference year 2019 (in Appendix B1 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, and 2016). For every country in the network, we recorded all the trading partners (in correspondence to the study's assumptions) in terms of trade flows. The top influential players are France, the USA, Italy, Germany, and the UK. International trade in wine looks geographically segmented with the major role played by Europe on one side and Canada and Australia on the other. China, Chile, and Australia hold a moderate position in the graph, in terms of trading flows between

the countries. The boosting role of China is noteworthy in 2019, in comparison to the years 2010 and 2013. More precisely, we can see that China has strong trade flows with a lot of countries, while, for example, in 2010 it only trades with Australia and France.

Figure 2.1.9
Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD
Eigenvector Centrality

Next, we depict the wine network analysis for the years 2010, 2013, 2016, and 2019, based on authority centrality (Figure 2.1.10 for 2019; in Appendix B1 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, and 2016). Over the years, we observe that the USA and specific European countries are the principal players. Precisely, Italy trades wine with a large number of countries, like the UK, Denmark, and China. Furthermore, you can observe that the UK has substantial trade flows with a large number of nations, like Italy, Germany, and Hong Kong. On the other hand, China’s emerging economy and Chile appear to have a moderate contribution in terms of trade value. Finally, some countries are in the trade flow margin and have weak connections with other partners. For example, the Russian Federation trades only with Georgia and Lithuania.

Figure 2.1.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Authority

In terms of centrality hub, we illustrate the wine network trade in reference years 2010, 2013, 2016, 2019 (Figure 2.1.11 for 2019; in Appendix B1 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, and 2016). Across all benchmark years, we observe that the strong European economies like France, Italy, and Spain are the leading players, keeping strong trade flows between them and other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. For example, in 2019, we observe that Italy and France trade with a lot of countries that belong to Europe or other continents. On the other hand, Australia and Chile hold moderate trade flows in this centrality measure and appear to trade with a restricted number of countries, like Brazil or the UK. Finally, for the year 2019, Argentina and Brazil have a limited wine trade flow, particularly with the USA and Chile, respectively.

Figure 2.1.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

In what follows we present the wine network analysis for the years 2010, 2013, 2016, and 2019 based on centrality betweenness (Figure 2.1.12 for 2019; in Appendix B1 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, and 2016). Over the years, we observe a similar pattern regarding the intensity of trade flows, between countries. The main feature throughout the reference years is the dominance of the EU, as a core player. France, Italy, and the UK are the leading countries with strong trade flows within the continent and outside of it. Another crucial node with strong trade flows to the EU is the USA. In comparison to the other nations, China has a moderate trade size, holding a minor place in the depiction, but still maintaining close ties with some European countries. Finally, Argentina and Lithuania have limited trade flows throughout the years and more precisely their marginal flows are in 2019 with Japan and the Russian Federation, respectively.

Figure 2.1.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

In terms of centrality closeness (Figure 2.1.13 for 2019; in Appendix B1 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, and 2016), throughout the benchmark years, we have the dominance of Europe. Precisely Italy, France, and the UK appear as central players in the wine trade network, for all benchmark years. Over the years, there are strong network flows between the top countries and other continents. Another important node with strong trade flows to the EU is the USA. In comparison to the other continents, Asia has middle to limited trade size, with China and Japan occupying modest positions in the graph while preserving tight links with Europe and Chile.

Figure 2.1.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

2.2. Gravity literature review of the wine international market

Dascal *et al.* (2002) used a gravity model to examine the main factors having an impact on the EU’s wine trade flows. Data referred to the 1989-1997 period, taking into account the first 12 EU countries. Other countries also included in the analysis were Austria, Sweden, and Finland (only as partner countries of the EU, as they became EU-members after 1995), as well as Canada, Japan, Switzerland, and the USA as the biggest importing countries from the EU, and Australia, Bulgaria, Chile, Hungary, Romania, and the USA as the biggest exporting countries to the EU. Two different analyses were performed, one concerning the exports of the EU countries (dependent variable: volume of wine exported), and the other concerning their imports (dependent variable: volume of wine imported). The independent variables of both models included the importer’s and exporter’s per capita GDP, distance, unit price value of wine (exported in the first model, imported in the second), spot exchange rate, wine production index, and a dummy variable indicating the trade flows among EU member countries. The study’s results indicated that, on a statistically significant level, exporter’s and importer’s GDP, distance, exchange rate, production index, and EU membership had a positive effect on exports, while unit price of exports had a negative effect. For the analysis concerning EU imports, GDP, EU membership, and unit price of imports had the same effect as in the export’s

model, while distance, exchange rate, and production index were found to have a different sign, with the three of them having a negative effect on imports.

De Blasi *et al.* (2007) applied a gravity model to investigate Italy's exports of high-quality wine (specifically, QWPDR (Quality Wines Produced in Determined Regions)] to its main importing countries. Data covered the 1995 to 2005 period, taking into account the 55 largest importers of QWPDR from Italy (accounting for over 92% of Italy's exports for the specific product, in 2005). The dependent variable was expressed as the value of QWPDR exports from Italy; independent variables included Italian QWPDR production, per capita GDP of the importing country, a dummy variable indicating if the importer is an EU-member, a dummy variable indicating if the importer has started EU Accession Negotiations, as well as a set of dummy variables indicating the specific country and year effects. Based on the model's results Italian QWPDR production, the importer's per capita GDP, as well as the importer being an EU member or having initiated EU Accession Negotiations, facilitated Italian exports on a statistically significant level.

Pinilla and Serrano (2008) used a gravity model to examine Spanish table wine exports, and their determining factors, during the 1871-1935 period. Data covered Spain's 19 main trade partners, for the aforementioned period. The dependent variable was defined as the volume of Spanish table wine exports; independent variables comprised of the importer's and exporter's (i.e., Spain's) GDP and per capita GDP, distance, common language, a dummy variable indicating WWI (World War I) period (1914-1918), and a set of dummy variables taking into account changes of commercial policies of important wine-importing countries [France: Franco-Spanish treaties (1878-1891), USA: Prohibition effect (1920-1933), Argentina: stricter tariff system (1890-1935), Uruguay: stricter tariff system (1902-1935)]. The results of the study indicated that, on a statistically significant level, importer's GDP and per capita GDP, common language, and the Franco-Spanish treaty had a positive effect on Spanish table wine exports, while distance, WWI, and stricter commercial policies imposed by the importer (Argentina, USA, Uruguay) harmed exports.

Castillo *et al.* (2016) employed a gravity model to explore the changes having occurred in the global wine export dynamics, and define its determinants. Data covered the 1988-2012 period, taking into account bottled and bulk wine (2204.21 and 2204.29, respectively, of the tariff code TARIC); it should be mentioned that four different analyses were performed, taking into account the two wine categories (bottled and bulk) and two discrete periods: 1988-1999 (continuous change) and 2000-2012 (established export dynamic). The major importing (14 countries: Belgium, Canada, China, Denmark, Germany, Japan, the Netherlands, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, USA, Norway, and Finland) and exporting (9 countries: Argentina, Australia, Chile, France, Italy, New Zealand, Portugal, South Africa, and Spain) countries by volume of wine exported were taken into account, accounting for over 85% of world total trade flows of bottled and bulk wine. The dependent variable is defined as exports in volume (either for bottled or bulk wine), while independent

variables consist of importer's and exporter's GDP, export price, distance, a set of country-related dummy variables [specifying EU-continental (Belgium, the Netherlands, Switzerland), China and Russia, the USA and the UK], common border, common continent, common language, participation in the same economic and trade agreement, and common currency. The results indicated that, in general, the importer's and exporter's GDP and common language had a statistically significant positive effect on trade, while distance and export price had a negative effect. Results, when taking into account the four different analyses (two product codes, and two periods) were indecisive concerning the effect of common border, common continent, participation in the same trade agreement, and common currency.

Dal Bianco *et al.* (2016) examined the effect of trade barriers [focusing on transport costs, tariffs, TBTs (Technical Barriers to Trade), and SPSs (Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards)] on the world wine trade, through the implementation of a gravity model. The data used, referred to the 1997-2010 period, taking into account the 12 main importing and exporting countries; the product under examination was HS (Harmonized System) 6-digit code 220421, i.e. "wine of fresh grapes (other than sparkling wine) and grape must with fermentation prevented, etc. by adding alcohol, containers of not over 2l". The dependent variable of the model was defined as the quantity of wine exports. Independent variables included exporter's wine supply, importer's wine production, importer's GDP, distance, common language, wine-specific tariff protection, and a set of seven variables indicating the number of restrictive regulations/ measures set by the importer (concerning labeling, food standards, conformity assessment, food containers, human health, packaging, and SPS measures). The results of the model indicated that, on a statistically significant level, importer's GDP, exporter's supply, and common language had a positive effect on exports, while importer's production, tariffs, and various technical barriers (related to labeling, conformity assessment, human health, and packaging) harmed wine trade. SPS measures were not found to create a trade barrier to wine.

Lombardi *et al.* (2016), through a gravity model, examined the intra-EU trade of the world's three most important and historical competitors, namely Italy, France, and Spain. Data took into account the EU countries which during 2000-2014 (i.e., the period under examination) imported an average of 50 million liters of wine per year, accounting for over 90% of intra-EU trade in volume, for all years in question (16 countries, namely, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, UK). Two analyses were performed, one on bottled wine, considered as the sum of wines in containers equal to or less than two liters (HS6-digit code 220421) and sparkling wines (HS6-digit code 220410), and the other on bulk wine (HS6-digit code 220429). The dependent variable was defined as the export value of wine, while independent variables included importer's wine production (i.e., supply), importer's total wine imports (i.e., demand), weighted distance, common language, and two variables indicating France's and Italy's export trends (rising or falling) in comparison to Spain (set as the benchmark). The results showed that, on a statistically significant

level, bulk exports were positively affected by demand and negatively by distance; the same results stood for bottled wine, with the addition of language as a facilitating factor. Referring to the three countries' trends, a falling trend was indicated for France for bulk wine, while all three countries presented a rising trend in bottled wine, with Italy having the best trend, and being followed by Spain and France.

Balogh and Jám bor (2018) investigated the impact of cultural-geographical proximity, free trade, and linguistic similarity on wine trade between the world's main wine producers, by applying a gravity model. Data were taken into account 32 considerable wine exporters and their 216 trading partners, referring to the HS4-digit product code 2204 (wine of fresh grapes, including fortified wines; grape must), covering the 2000 to 2012 period. The dependent variable is defined as the value of wine exports. Independent variables consist of importer's and exporter's GDP, distance, common language, common colonizer, colonial link, a dummy variable indicating if both trading partners are landlocked, common religion, RTAs (Regional Trade Agreements) between the partners, a dummy variable indicating if both countries are WTO (World Trade Organization) members, and a set of dummy variables, indicating specific common language classification (i.e., Anglo-Saxon, Germanic, Latin American, Latin European). The study's results showed that on a statistically significant level, importer's and exporter's GDP, common language and religion, colonial links, RTAs, and WTO membership, have a positive effect on wine exports, while distance and the fact that the countries are landlocked had a negative effect on exports.

Gouveia *et al.* (2018) applied a gravity model to investigate the macroeconomic determinants of Port wine exports, considering the diversity and the various quality levels of this product. Data covered the 2006-2014 period, considering the top-20 importing countries, which accounted for 94% of total exports. Ten different models were developed, based on the expression of export flows (by volume or by value) and quality of the product (standard, high standard, vintage, aged, and total). The dependent variable of the models was determined as Port wine export flows (either by volume or by value). The independent variables comprised of importer's GDP and per capita GDP, custom protection of Port wine (ad valorem equivalent tariff) imposed by the importer, nominal exchange rate, importer's per capita wine consumption, the number of Portuguese emigrants in the importing country, distance, common language, and a dummy variable indicating if the importer is landlocked. The study's results showed that Port wine exports (either by quantity or by value) are positively affected on a statistically significant level, by per capita GDP, common language, and the presence of a Portuguese emigrant community, while being negatively affected by the fact that a country is landlocked. When referring to specific product categories, it was indicated that GDP facilitated aged Port exports and per capita wine consumption facilitated high-standard, vintage, and aged Port exports.

Macedo *et al.* (2019) applied a gravity model to identify the macroeconomic determinants of exports, taking quality into account (by vertical differentiation) and focusing on Portuguese Douro wines. Data covered the 2006 to 2015 period, referring

to 192 potential trade partners (with around 65% of the export flows being equal to zero); three different qualities of Douro wine were taken into account, namely standard, reserve, and grand reserve. Different models were developed, defining the dependent variable either as the volume, or the value of Portugal's Douro exports. The independent variables included the importer's per capita GDP, distance, common language, common currency, common border, a dummy variable indicating if the trading partners are members of the same RTA, and a set of dummy variables indicating the category of the wine (reserve, or grand reserve). The results showed that the importer's GDP, common language, and common currency favored wine exports on a statistically significant level. The quality of the wine was also found to have a significant effect, with wines of higher quality than the standard (i.e., reserve and grand reserve) performing worse in the international markets.

Santeramo *et al.* (2019) used a gravity model to examine the impact of country-specific NTMs (Non-Tariff Measures) on global wine imports. Four product categories were examined, both separately and in aggregation: HS6-digit codes 220410 (wine, sparkling), 220421 (wine, still, in containers holding 2l or less), 220429 (wine, still, in containers holding more than 2l), and 220430 (grape must). The data covered 24 countries (chosen among the top importers, exporters, and producers), for the 1991 to 2016 period. The dependent variable is defined as the import values of wine. The independent variables of the model consisted of SPS measures, TBT measures, pre-shipment inspections, and export-related measures. The analyses results indicated that country-specific NTMs facilitated wine imports, with different effects depending on the product category and the measurement type. Specifically, on a statistically significant level, TBT measures and pre-shipment inspections favored bottled wine, while SPS and export-related measures enhanced all product types. The only statistically significant negative effect was that of TBT measures on bulk wine.

Ayuda *et al.* (2020) employed a gravity model to identify the determinants of world wine exports during the first globalization period. Data referred to the 1848-1938 period, taking into account the major exporting countries (accounting for 75-85% of world exports in volume or 75-90% in value). Different models were developed for ordinary (in casks) and high-quality (bottled) wine; the dependent variable in both cases was defined as the wine trade between Algeria, France, Italy, and Spain and its 37 trading partners. The independent variables comprised of importer's GDP, exporters' wine production, as well as the 1,2, and 3 lagged values of exporters' wine production (to measure the effect of the harvest of previous years), importer's wine production (as well as 1,2 and 3 lagged values), real transporting costs, colonial link (i.e., the importer being a colony of the exporter), level of monopolistic competition (expressed as the wine imported by the exporters from their partners), a dummy variable indicating if both partners belonged to the gold standard (in reference to the impact of exchange rate variations), and a set of dummy variables indicating certain political and economic situations with direct effects of international wine exports [i.e., WWI, Great Depression, Soviet Union establishment, and North American Prohibition]. The analyses indicated that, on a statistically significant level, exporter's

wine production, and exporter's lagged production (mainly for low-quality wine), level of monopolistic competition (for high-quality wine), and the golden standard (for high-quality wines) favored wine exports, while the examined political and economic situations, the importer's lagged production, and importer's wine production (for low-quality wines) and transportation costs (for low-quality wines) had an unfavorable effect towards exports.

Macedo *et al.* (2020) utilized a gravity model to examine the determinants of Port wine exports, while especially focusing on the effect of climate change and NTMs. Data covered the 2006 to 2018 period, referring to Portugal's Port wine exports to 60 countries (representing 98% of the total value exported for that period); Port wine is included under the HS8-digit code 22042189 (before 2010, it was also included in the code 22042195), i.e., "in containers holding <5 2 liters and of actual alcoholic strength of >15% volume, with Protected Designation of Origin or Protected Geographical Indication"). The dependent variable referred to the value of Port wine exports; independent variables included the importer's per capita GDP, exchange rate, ad valorem equivalent tariffs imposed by the importer to Port wine, a dummy variable indicating if the importer is among the top-10 wine producers, the number of SPS, TBT and other NTMs (the three of them, considered separately), and climate conditions in the importing country (expressed as averages or anomalies for the hottest and coolest trimesters). The results of the study showed that, on a statistically significant level, the importer's per capita GDP facilitated Port exports, while mean temperature and climate anomalies in the importing country, as well as particular SPS and TBT measures imposed by the importer, had an unfavorable effect for exports.

Zaninovic *et al.* (2021) applied the gravity model to examine the differences between the determinants of sparkling wine and still wine. Data took into account the 1996-2019 period, referring to a worldwide level; three different models were developed, for each of the following product categories: sparkling wine (HS6-digit code 220410), still wine in containers holding 2 liters or less (HS6-digit code 220421) and still wine in containers holding 2 liters or more (HS6-digit code 220429). The dependent variable was set as the value of trade flows; different models were developed, to estimate exports and imports separately. The independent variables included the importer's and exporter's GDP, distance, colonial link, common language, common border, and a dummy variable indicating if the trading partners have signed an RTA. Results indicated that on a statistically significant level, importer's and exporter's GDP facilitated wine trade, while distance had an unfavorable effect on trade flows. On the other hand, RTAs, colonial links, common language, and border had different effects on the still wine trade, compared to the sparkling wine trade.

2.3. Gravity analysis of the wine international market

Bellow, we present the gravity model used in the case of wine, the data set used in the estimation of the model, and the empirical results obtained from the estimation of the wine gravity model.

2.3.1. The gravity model of the wine international market

The Gravity model is used in applied international trade in explaining various kinds of inter-regional and international trade flows. It was introduced by Tinbergen (1962) and in its basic form, it relates the trade flows between two countries by their economic sizes (positively related) and the distance between them (negatively related). The economic size is generally captured by the GDP, while distance can be measured in geographic terms by physical distance (Head and Mayer, 2013). The gravity model of trade has been widely used to assess empirically the effect on trade of distance and common borders (Disdier and Head, 2008; McCallum, 1995) and a variety of policy issues, including international agreements, tariff and NTMs, and various trade distortions (Anderson, 2000, 2011; Baier and Bergstrand, 2001, 2007; Cheng and Wall, 1999; Dal Bianco *et al.*, 2016; Grant and Boys, 2011; Raimondi and Opler, 2011; Rose, 2004; Xiong and Beghin, 2011).

A general expression of the gravity model is

$$X_{ijt} = cM_{it}^{\alpha}M_{jt}^{\beta}D_{ij}^{*\delta}, \quad (2.3.1)$$

where X_{ijt} are the country's exports i to destination j at time t , M_{it} represents the exporter's supply (i.e., the wine production of country i) at time t , M_{jt} is the per capita GDP of country j at time t , D_{ij}^* measures the geographical distance between the capitals of countries i, j .

Taking natural logarithms on both sides of Eq. (2.3.1), we obtain the following expression

$$\ln X_{ijt} = c^* + \alpha \ln M_{it} + \beta \ln M_{jt} + \delta \ln D_{ij}^* + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2.3.2)$$

where ε_{ij} is the error term and it is assumed to be identically and independently distributed, and $c^* = \ln c$.

Following previous studies (Jayasinghe *et al.*, 2010; Dal Bianco *et al.*, 2016) we augment 'geographical distance' by including country-specific tariffs, NTMs, and a dummy variable indicating if the origin and destination countries are engaged bilaterally in a regional trade agreement within the given year. Thus, D_{ij}^* is proxying 'economic distance' and is modeled as

$$D_{ijt}^{\delta} = (D_{ij})^{\delta_1} (1 + tr_{jt})^{\delta_2} (1 + sps_{jt})^{\delta_{31}} (1 + tbt_{jt})^{\delta_{32}} (1 + ontm_{jt})^{\delta_{33}} (1 + tag_{ij})^{\delta_4} \quad (2.3.3)$$

where D_{ij} is the geographical distance between the capitals of countries i, j ; tr_j represents the *ad valorem* equivalent tariff imposed by country j to the county's i exports; the variables sps_{jt} , tbt_{jt} and $ontm_{jt}$ belong to the class of NTMs and represent Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards, Technical Barriers to Trade and other NTMs, respectively, imposed by the importing country; tag_{ij} a dummy variable indicating if the trading partners are engaged bilaterally in a regional trade agreement.

Furthermore, we add a constant, equal to 1, to avoid the possibility of taking the logarithm of zero. Eq. (2.3.2) becomes as follows given the specification of Eq. (2.3.3)

$$\ln X_{ijt} = c^* + \alpha \ln M_{it} + \beta \ln M_{jt} + \delta_1 \ln D_{ij} + \delta_2 \ln(1 + tr_{jt}) + \delta_{31} \ln(1 + sps_{jt}) + \delta_{32} \ln(1 + tbt_{jt}) + \delta_{33} \ln(1 + ontm_{jt}) + \delta_4 \ln(1 + tag_{ijt}) + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2.3.4)$$

Following Anderson and Van Wincoop (2003) and Dal Bianco *et al.* (2016), we introduce additional variables in Eq. (2.3.4) and we obtain Eq. (2.3.5).

$$\ln X_{ijt} = c^* + \alpha \ln M_{it} + \beta \ln M_{jt} + \delta_1 \ln D_{ij} + \delta_2 \ln(1 + tr_{jt}) + \delta_{31} \ln(1 + sps_{jt}) + \delta_{32} \ln(1 + tbt_{jt}) + \delta_{33} \ln(1 + ontm_{jt}) + \delta_4 \ln(1 + tag_{ijt}) + \zeta_1 eu_i + \zeta_2 eu_j + \eta_1 ukeu_{ij} + \eta_2 ukrest_{ij} + \theta_1 temp_{it} + \theta_2 temp_{jt} + \theta_3 precip_{it} + \theta_4 precip_{jt} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2.3.5)$$

In Eq. (2.3.5), eu_i (eu_j) is a dummy variable assuming the value of 1 if the exporting (importing) country is a member of EU; $ukeu_{ij}$ taking the value of 1 if trading partners are the UK and an EU country member; $ukrest_{ij}$ assuming the value of 1 trading partners are the UK and a non-EU country member. The final four variables in Eq. (2.3.5) are included to capture weather conditions. In particular, $temp_i$ ($temp_j$) measures the average air temperature in the exporting (importing) country, while $precip_i$ ($precip_j$) measures the average precipitation in the exporting (importing) country. Finally, In Eq. (2.3.5), we can include fixed effects to account for multilateral resistance terms (Feenstra, 2004; Baier and Bergstrand, 2007; Subramanian and Wei, 2007; Baldwin and Taglioni, 2006; Dal Bianco *et al.* 2016).

2.3.2. Data used in the wine gravity model

This section provides the description, data sources, and descriptive statistics of the variables used in the gravity model.

Table 2.3.1. Variable definition, descriptive statistics, and data sources

Variables	Variable Definition	Descriptive Statistics	Data Sources
X_{ij} (Trade flows from country i to j)	Trade flow as reported by the importer in thousands current US\$	Mean: 310585 Min: 100711 Max: 1321883 St. dev.: 248503.3	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
M_{it} (Production-exporter)	Wine production in tonnes	Mean: 2856448 Min: 0 Max: 5414983 St. dev.: 1765579	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United States https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data
M_{jt} (Per capita GDP-importer)	GDP per capita (current thousands US\$)	Mean: 45.57 Min: 3.749 Max: 87.99 St. dev.: 16.47	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8

D_{ij} (Distance)	Distance between capitals (km)	Mean: 5911.11 Min: 262.38 Max: 19147.14 St. dev.: 5550.33	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
tr_{jt} (MFN applied rates-importer)	Ad valorem (on value) tariff rate	Mean: 83.76 Min: 0 Max: 3000 St. dev.: 448.91	World Integrated Trade Solution https://wits.worldbank.org/
sps_{jt} (Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 8.21 Min: 0 Max: 17 St. dev.: 7.66	The UNCTAD, TRAINS NTMs database https://trainsonline.unctad.org/detailedSearch
tbt_{jt} (Technical Barriers to Trade)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 3.32 Min: 0 Max: 24 St. dev.: 2.87	The UNCTAD, TRAINS NTMs database https://trainsonline.unctad.org/detailedSearch
$ontm_{jt}$ (Other non-tariff measures)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 0.95 Min: 0 Max: 13 St. dev.: 1.49	The UNCTAD, TRAINS NTMs database https://trainsonline.unctad.org/detailedSearch
tag_{ijt} (Regional trade agreements)	1 if the pair currently has an RTA	Mean: 0.60 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.49	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
eu_i (EU member-exporter)	1 if the exporting country currently is an EU member	Mean: 0.67 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.47	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
eu_j (EU member-importer)	1 if the importing country currently is an EU member	Mean: 0.42 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.49	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
$ukeu_{ij}$ (Trading partnership UK – EU)	1 if the trading partners are the UK and an EU member	Mean: .087 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.28	
$ukrest_{ij}$ (Trading partnership UK-non-EU country)	1 if the trading partners are the UK and a non-EU member	Mean: 0.106 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.304	

$temp_{it}$ (Temperature-exporter)		Mean: 12.91 Min: 6.84 Max: 22.88 St. dev.: 3.60	World Bank Group, Climate Change Knowledge Portal https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/download-data
$temp_{jt}$ (Temperature-importer)		Mean: 9.02 Min: -4.86 Max: 26.11 St. dev.: 6.15	World Bank Group, Climate Change Knowledge Portal https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/download-data
$precip_{it}$ (Precipitation-exporter)		Mean: 799.72 Min: 377.53 Max: 1992.8 St. dev.: 317.76	World Bank Group, Climate Change Knowledge Portal https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/download-data
$precip_{jt}$ (Precipitation-importer)		Mean: 983.64 Min: 377.53 Max: 2297.77 St. dev.: 438.87	World Bank Group, Climate Change Knowledge Portal https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/download-data

2.3.3. Empirical results of the wine gravity model

First, we apply the ordinary least squares (OLS) method in Eq. (2.3.5) to obtain estimates of the unknown parameters. The OLS are the best linear unbiased estimators if the errors (ε_{ij}) of Eq. (2.3.5) are independently and identically distributed with a constant variance of σ_ε^2 . However, these conditions are violated as indicated by the White test and Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity and the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation (Table 2.3.2). Thus, we use the Driscoll and Kraay (1998) correction to fix heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. Failure to correct for autocorrelation can result in understated standard errors (Moulton, 1990).

Table 2.3.2. White Test and Breusch-Pagan test for Heteroscedasticity & Wooldridge test for autocorrelation

White Test		Breusch-Pagan tests/Cook-Weisberg test		Wooldridge test	
F(2,501)=30.23	Prob>F=0.0000	chi2(1)=95.24	Prob>chi2=0.0000	F(1,50) = 206.833	Prob > F = 0.0000

Notes: H_0 for White's test is that the variances for the errors are equal
 H_0 for Breusch-Pagan tests/Cook-Weisberg test assumes constant variance
 H_0 for the Wooldridge test assumes no first-order autocorrelation

The second column of Table 2.3.3 presents results for pooled OLS (OLS_POOLED) estimation of Eq. (2.3.5), while the third column shows OLS estimates of Eq. (2.3.5) with yearly fixed effects included (OLS_FE).

Table 2.3.3. Estimation results of Eq. (5)

(1) Variables	(2) OLS_POOLED	(3) OLS_FE	(4) PPML	(5) PPML_ME
<i>Intercept</i>	5.6554*** (2.094)	5.3195** (2.149)	1.9690*** (0.165)	
M_{it} (<i>Production-exporter</i>)	0.1738*** (0.040)	0.1751*** (0.042)	0.0140*** (0.003)	0.1748*** (0.040)
M_{jt} (<i>Per capital GDP-importer</i>)	0.2539*** (0.087)	0.2641*** (0.088)	0.0205*** (0.006)	0.2554*** (0.086)
D_{ij} (<i>Distance</i>)	-0.3226*** (0.068)	-0.3263*** (0.069)	-0.0260*** (0.005)	-0.323*** (0.067)
tr_{jt} (<i>MFN applied rates-importer</i>)	-0.0848*** (0.030)	-0.0963*** (0.035)	-0.0069*** (0.002)	-0.0858*** (0.029)
sps_{jt} (<i>Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards</i>)	-0.4310*** (0.133)	-0.4433*** (0.132)	-0.0346*** (0.010)	-0.4296*** (0.130)
tbt_{jt} (<i>Technical Barriers to Trade</i>)	0.2291 (0.156)	0.2326 (0.159)	0.0184 (0.012)	0.2284 (0.153)
$ontm_{jt}$ (<i>Other non-tariff measures</i>)	-0.0345 (0.086)	-0.0075 (0.111)	-0.0027 (0.006)	-0.0345 (0.084)
tag_{ijt} (<i>Regional trade agreements</i>)	0.4172** (0.198)	0.4544** (0.205)	0.0341** (0.015)	0.4236** (0.196)
eu_i (<i>EU member-exporter</i>)	0.4000*** (0.146)	0.4107*** (0.147)	0.0324*** (0.011)	0.4022*** (0.142)
eu_j (<i>EU member-importer</i>)	-0.1510 (0.301)	-0.1501 (0.308)	-0.0124 (0.023)	-0.1544 (0.295)
$ukeu_{ij}$	0.3617 (0.295)	0.3333 (0.298)	0.0285	0.3538 (0.284)

(Trading partnership UK – EU)			(0.022)	
$ukrest_{ij}$ (Trading partnership UK-nonEU country)	1.2198*** (0.274)	1.2356*** (0.275)	0.0988*** (0.021)	1.2268*** (0.270)
$temp_{it}$ (Temperature-exporter)	0.0428*** (0.012)	0.0439*** (0.012)	0.0034*** (0.001)	0.0433*** (0.012)
$temp_{jt}$ (Temperature-importer)	0.0061 (0.009)	0.0061 (0.009)	0.0005 (0.0008)	0.0063 (0.009)
$precip_{it}$ (Precipitation-exporter)	0.0007*** (0.0002)	0.0007*** (0.0002)	0.00006*** (0.00001)	0.0007*** (0.0001)
$precip_{jt}$ (Precipitation-importer)	0.0002 (0.0003)	0.0003 (0.0003)	0.00002 (0.00002)	0.0002 (0.0003)
2010.year (Dummy variable)		0.0630 (0.042)		
2011.year (Dummy variable)		0.2436*** (0.053)		
2012.year (Dummy variable)		0.1421*** (0.050)		
2013.year (Dummy variable)		0.1204** (0.055)		
2014.year (Dummy variable)		-0.0016 (0.067)		
2015.year (Dummy variable)		0.0232 (0.064)		
2016.year (Dummy variable)		0.0112 (0.075)		
2017.year (Dummy variable)		0.1043 (0.094)		
2018.year (Dummy variable)		-0.0429 (0.099)		
2019.year (Dummy variable)		0.1324 (0.119)		

Statistics	N=504	N=504	N=504	
	F(16, 55) =5.69	F(26, 55) =7.58	R-squared=0.404	
	Prob > F = 0.0000	Prob > F = 0.0000	LL =-1105.904	
	R-squared=0.401	R-squared=0.416	AIC=2245.809	
	Root MSE=0.507	Root MSE=0.506	BIC=2317.593	
	LL =-364.076	LL =-357.867		
	AIC=762.152	AIC=769.734		
	BIC=833.9358	BIC=883.744		

Notes: **, *** denote 5 and 1 percent significance level, respectively; N denotes the number of observations; LL is the log-likelihood; AIC and BIC are the Akaike's and Schwarz's Bayesian information criteria, respectively.

A log-likelihood ratio test supports the inclusion of the annual dummy variables in Eq. (2.3.5) and thus, the OLS_FE model is preferred over the OLS_POOLED. In particular, the value of the log-likelihood test is equal to 12.4, suggesting the rejection of the null hypothesis that the time effects are not statistically significant at the 1% significance level. Column four of Table 2.3.3 presents the estimates of Eq. (2.3.5) using the Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML) estimation approach, while column five provides the marginal effects based on the PPML estimates. We estimated the PPML model for checking the robustness of our results. Note that the advantage of the PPML model is that it corrects for sample selection bias that might result from excluding zero observations. Since we have considered only trade flows with a value above 0.5% of the global wine value traded, selection bias is not present. As a result, we expect that the magnitude, statistical significance, and economic interpretation of marginal effects obtained from the PPML model would be very similar to those of the OLS_POOLED and OLS_FE approaches. A thorough inspection of Table 2.3.3 shows that the empirical results obtained from the three estimation approaches (i.e., OLS_POOLED, OLS_FE and PPML) are similar and thus support the robustness of our findings in our preferred model (i.e., OLS_FE). In the rest of the section, unless specified otherwise, we refer to the estimates from the OLS_FE model.

First, the R-squared is 0.416, which shows that the explanatory variables account for about 42% of the observed variation in the wine trade in the data, indicating that the model fits the data relatively well. Furthermore, the F-test is statistically significant at the 1% level, which provides second support of the satisfying performance of the model. The wine production of the exporter (M_{it}) and the per capita GDP of the importer (M_{jt}) are both positively associated with trade at the 1% level of significance. The results show that we would expect that a 1% increase in exporter wine production tends to increase wine trade by about 0.18%, while a 1% increase in importer per

capita GDP would increase wine trade by about 0.26%. On the other hand, the coefficient on distance (D_{ij}) is negative at the 5% significance level, indicating that a 1% increase in distance tends to reduce trade by about 0.33%. Thus the parameter estimates of wine supply, per capita GDP and distance have the expected signs and are statistically significant. Note that previous studies, such as Bianco *et al.* (2016) and Silva and Tenreyro (2006), find that the estimated elasticity for GDP is greater than one. This finding might be attributed to the fact that these studies use GDP instead of per capita GDP as the present study does.

The effect of the *ad valorem* equivalent tariffs (tr_{jt}) is negative and statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that a 1% increase in the tariff rate will decrease trade by about 0.096%. The small effect of tariffs on trade flows might be because tariffs remained relatively stable during the study period. In other words, tariffs in the main destination countries did not vary significantly to provoke any substantial effect on trade. It is worth stating that previous research [e.g., Gouveia *et al.* (2018) and Macedo *et al.* (2020)] did not find any significant effect of tariffs on wine trade flows.

Among the NTMs, only the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards (sps_{jt}) are statistically significant (at the 1% level), while Technical Barriers to Trade (tbt_{jt}) and other NTMs ($ontm_{jt}$) are not statistically significant at any conventional level of significance. The results show that a 1% increase in sps_j in the importing country will reduce trade flows by 0.44%. The study by Macedo *et al.* (2020) finds a negative effect of sps_j on trade, while the study by Santeramo *et al.* (2019) finds a positive effect. Regional trade agreements (tag_{ijt}) have a positive and statistically significant effect on trade, showing a 0.454% increase on trade for a 1% increase of tag_{ij} .

The statistical significance of the dummy variable eu_i indicates that trade flows are greater by 0.41% when the export country is an EU country compared to the case where the exporting country is not an EU country. However, in the case where the importing country is an EU country (i.e., consider the dummy variable, eu_j) the effect is not statistically significant, compared to the case where the importing country is not an EU country. These results support the conclusion that the EU is a significant exporter in the global wine trade and enhances the global wine trade.

The trading partnership *UK – EU* as indicated by the $ukeu_{ij}$ dummy is not statistically significant at any conventional level of significance, indicating that the trade between the *UK* and the *EU* is not significantly different from the average global wine trade. Furthermore, the trade between the *UK* and the rest of the world, excluding the *EU*, is much greater than the average global wine trade, as it is supported by the statistically significant value (i.e., 1.2198) corresponding to the coefficient of the dummy variable $ukrest_{ij}$. These results could indicate that the BREXIT (British Exit) might not have an adverse effect on the *UK*'s global wine trade position, since *UK*'s trade flows with the *EU* are not significantly different from the average global wine trade flows but *UK*'s trade flows with the rest of the world (excluding the *EU* countries)

are much higher than the average global trade flows. However, this might not be true for the EU, since the EU's trade exports with the rest of the world (including the UK) are higher than the average global wine trade. Given that the UK is an important global trading country, the BREXIT might have a negative effect on the EU's international position in the global wine trade. Finally, the weather variables, i.e., *temp* and *precip*, indicate that both temperature and precipitation in the exporting countries have positive and statistically significant effects on wine trade flows.

2.4. Conclusions of the wine international market

Network analysis has provided a comprehensive review of the evolving global trade of the wine sector. By applying network methods in the wine industry, we have increased the depth of our understanding of global trends in this field. More precisely, this study has yielded the following insights. First, our study revealed that the main feature throughout the reference years is the dominance of the EU, as a core player. France and Italy are the leading countries with strong trade flows within the continent and outside of it. Moreover, another crucial node with strong trade flows to the EU is the USA. In addition, it is evident the substantial trade flows between the UK and other countries, imply that the BREXIT may have caused difficulties and fluctuations in wine trading. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top wine exporters in 2019 are France, Italy, Spain, Australia, Chile, the USA, New Zealand, Germany, Portugal, Argentina, the UK, and South Africa. In the same year, the top importers are the USA, the UK, China, Germany, Canada, Hong Kong, the Netherlands, Japan, Switzerland, Belgium, the Russian Federation, and France.

Based on the literature review performed on gravity models, the main determinants of wine trade flows consist of importer's and exporter's (per capita) GDP as well as their wine production, currency aspects (exchange rate, or common currency), wine export prices, the distance between the trading countries, geographical position (in terms of common borders, and the existence of a landlocked partner), climate conditions (temperature, climate anomalies), historical and cultural factors (common language, common religion, colonial links, overall political and economic conditions), and trade-related aspects, in the form of common participation in FTAs (Free Trade Agreements), and imposed tariffs and/or NTMs by the importing country.

The empirical results of the gravity wine model estimated in the present discussion paper for the 2009-2019 period provide the following conclusions. First, the economic activity captured by the exporter's wine production and the importer's per capita GDP has a positive effect on wine trade flows. In contrast, the distance between trading partners has a negative impact. Second, tariffs have a negative but minimal impact on the wine trade. Among the NTMs, only the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards have a significant and negative effect on trade. Third, regional trade agreements have a relatively significant positive effect on trade. EU wine exports (including the UK) to the rest of the world are well above the average international wine trade flows, while this is not true for the imports. This indicates that the EU is a significant exporting region in the global wine trade. The same is true for the wine trade between

the UK and the rest of the world (excluding the EU countries). Thus, the BREXIT might have a negative effect on the EU's international trade position since the UK is an important global trading country.

3 DAIRY

3.1. Network analysis and results of the dairy international market

In this section, the world's major dairy exporters and importers are presented, using data on trade flows from 2010 to 2019. Our data is stemming from the BACI dataset from CEPII, the leading French center for research and expertise on the world economy. Furthermore, our sample consists of those countries with a value of dairy trade flows greater than 90 million dollars which represents about 5% of total trade. This threshold is used to exclude small trade flows to eliminate unnecessary noise originating from such trades. The detailed list of dairy codes used in this study is found in Appendix A2.

It is impossible to exaggerate the dairy industry's importance in the EU. Dairy products are the second most important source of animal protein; in the EU, on average, 300 kg of milk are consumed per capita annually (Westhoek, *et al.* 2011). Dairy products are competitive on international markets, and their commerce has grown significantly in value, in the last decades. The network dynamics underlying these commercial interactions are extensive and complex. This necessitates the use of a network analysis approach to assess and comprehend the structure and dynamics of international interactions in the EU and the international dairy industry.

Figure 3.1.1 illustrates the top dairy exporters in the 2010 reference year, showing where each country fits into the international trade. According to this, Germany, France, New Zealand, and the Netherlands are the worldwide leading countries in dairy exports in 2010, based on export value. The USA, Belgium, Italy, and Denmark have also a prominent position in the trade. On the other hand, the remaining countries, Australia, Ireland, Poland, Belarus, Austria, and the UK have a comparably lower trade export value.

Figure 3.1.1

Continuing to Figure 3.1.2, we display the top dairy exporters in the 2013 reference year. We observe a similar interpretation as in Figure 3.1.1. The top dairy exporters

are once more Germany, New Zealand, the Netherlands, and France. A secondary but still significant role seems to be obtained by the USA, Italy, Belgium, Denmark, Australia, and Ireland. The figure illustrates, as in Figure 3.1.1, that powerful European economies like Germany and France play leading roles in dairy exports.

Figure 3.1.2

Figure 3.1.3, displays dairy exports, for the benchmark year 2016. This graph offers a similar pattern in relation to the export trends of the dairy sector and allows to stronger recognize the core role of the European countries and New Zealand in the dairy trade. The USA, Italy, Belgium, Denmark, and Australia are, once more, dominant players in the dairy exporting production, followed by the less favorable Ireland, Belarus, Poland, and the UK.

Figure 3.1.3

Figure 3.1.4, illustrates the most recent data we have, concerning dairy exports, for the benchmark year 2019. According to this figure, we have an identical pattern with the reference year 2016. Germany, New Zealand, the Netherlands, and France are the top dairy exporters. Minor exceptions are the fall of Australia and the rise of Spain

in the general ranking. This figure allows us to stronger recognize the core role of the European countries, the USA, and New Zealand in the dairy trade.

Figure 3.1.4

In the following Figures 3.1.5-3.1.8 we present the major dairy importers with the assumptions introduced at the beginning of our analysis. A quite similar and at the same time different scenario is depicted, in comparison with the dairy export flows. A remarkable point is that Germany is also the leading importing country for all the years available. Furthermore, the graphs illustrate the dominant presence of European countries and the emerging economy of China.

Figure 3.1.5 illustrates the top dairy importers for the year 2010. Europe’s largest economy by nominal GDP and net wealth, Germany, holds a leading position, with Italy, the sensitive economy of Russia, and the UK following. A European group consisting of France, Belgium, and Spain compose a mainstream second pole. In this line, we observe the vital footprint of China and the USA to compose a significant importing pillar. Based on their import value, the largest economy in the Arab world (i.e., Saudi Arabia) has a first appearance in the middle of the ranking, followed by Japan, Algeria, Mexico, and Indonesia.

Figure 3.1.5

Figure 3.1.6 displays the major importing countries for the benchmark year of 2013. In comparison to the previous Figure 3.1.5, Germany is still the top country in terms of import value. China’s boosting role in trade is a determinant factor in this graph, holding second place in the ranking. Referring to the following positions, the chart shows a similar pattern to the previous year, with the countries ranked almost in the same order.

Figure 3.1.6

Figure 3.1.7 illustrates the major importing countries for the benchmark years of 2016. The most notable aspect is that we have a similar scenario in terms of importing countries’ volume, with Germany for once more forging ahead.

Figure 3.1.7

Figure 3.1.8 depicts the major importing countries for the 2019 reference year. A similar pattern with the two previous charts is defined. A group of European countries is at the top of the list, accompanied by China, which is in the second position. Ireland is in last place, thanks to an increase in dairy output that has made the country more self-sufficient.

Figure 3.1.8

In what follows we shall use metrics of centrality to estimate the heterogeneity of countries in the global trade network. As we have described previously, in social network research, centrality is one of the most widely used topics. A significant number of measures have been developed, including degree centrality, closeness, betweenness, eigenvector centrality, information centrality, flow betweenness, the rush index, and the influence measures.

As previously described, each node represents a country in the network, which is denoted with its corresponding 3-code acronym. Different lines connect different countries. These lines represent the volume of the trade flows between the countries depicted. Therefore, in what follows we display our analysis for the visualization of the data. In Appendix B2 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016.

We illustrate the network analysis for the years 2010, 2013, 2016, and 2019 based on eigenvector centrality (Figure 3.1.9 for 2019; in Appendix B2 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). The presence of a massive network that includes a large number of countries with strong trade flows is evident. For every country in the network, we recorded all the trading partners (in correspondence to the study's assumptions) in the above years. The structure of the network seems to be quite clear with the European countries having the leading role. The top central players are France, Germany, Italy, the UK, and Spain. These countries appear to have strong trade flows with several other European countries, as well as with countries from other continents. Chile, New Zealand, China, and Saudi Arabia compose another significant trade group multi-linked with several other nations. Finally, the visualizations display Canada's and Slovenia's low rankings in terms of trade flows.

Figure 3.1.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

We depict the dairy network analysis for the years 2010, 2013, 2016, and 2019 based on authority centrality (Figure 3.1.10 for 2019; in Appendix B2 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe the dominant role of Europe with Germany, Italy, France, and the UK having strong trade flows within the continent and outside of it. The USA is another substantial player with trade connections with Europe, Asia, and others. China makes a significant appearance in 2013, and this trend continues until 2019. Finally, we observe that many nations have a marginal position in the dairy trade during the benchmark years; Thailand has trade flows only with New Zealand, and Portugal only with Spain.

Figure 3.1.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

In terms of centrality hub, we present the dairy network trade in reference to years 2010, 2013, 2016, 2019 (Figure 3.1.11 for 2019; in Appendix B2 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). Across all benchmark years, we observe that the strong European economies like Germany, France, the Netherlands, Italy, and Spain are the leading players, in terms of strong trade value connections, keeping powerful trade flows between them and other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. Similarly, the USA, Australia, and China’s boosting economy represent another significant group, which is characterized by its strong trades in dairy with multiple other nations. On the other hand, Indonesia and Hong Kong appear to have weak trade flows in this centrality measure. Canada, for example, has a limited dairy trade flow with the USA and Italy in 2019. Finally, Sri Lanka and Bangladesh hold a position in the periphery of the network and trade only with France and New Zealand, respectively.

Figure 3.1.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Next, we depict the dairy network analysis for the years 2010, 2013, 2016, and 2019 based on centrality betweenness (Figure 3.1.12 for 2019; in Appendix B2 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe a slight change in the main ranking, starting with 2010, where European countries are the core players. Germany, France, Italy, the UK, and Spain are the leading countries with strong trade flows within the continent and outside of it. Another crucial node with substantial trade flows to the EU is the USA. In comparison to the other nations, Asian countries have a poor trade size, with China and the Philippines holding a minor place in the depiction, but still maintaining close ties with Europe. In the year 2013, a similar pattern emerged, with Germany controlling a substantial portion of the global dairy trade, and China having now moderate network intensity.

Figure 3.1.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

In terms of centrality closeness (Figure 3.1.13 for 2019; in Appendix B2 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016), the result is a framework that emphasizes the importance of Europe; Italy, Germany, Belgium, Denmark, France, Greece, Spain, the UK are indicated as central players in the dairy trade network, for all benchmark years. Over the years, there are strong network flows between the top countries and other continents. The appearance of Greece in the network, with a distinct entry, is noteworthy. Another crucial node with strong trade flows to the EU is the USA. In comparison to the other continents, Asia has limited trade size, with China, the Philippines, and Japan, occupying modest positions in the graph while preserving tight links with Europe.

Figure 3.1.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

3.2. Gravity literature review of the dairy international market

Haq and Ishaq (2008) and Haq *et al.* (2013) focused on examining the effect of selection bias (i.e., (zero or missing trade flows are either ignored or replaced with a small positive number) in bilateral trade flows analyses based on gravity equations. In this context, gravity models were applied to estimate bilateral trade flows for 46 agrifood products, one of them being dairy products. The analysis took into consideration 52 countries for the 1990 to 2000 period; dairy products including fresh, not concentrated milk and cream, butter, cheese, and curd and edible products were taken into account, being disaggregated at 4-digit SITC (Standard International Trade Classification). The dependent variable was expressed as the real value of imports from one country to another. Independent variables included the distance between partners, common borders, preferential trade agreements between partners, importer’s and exporter’s Gini coefficients, importer’s and exporter’s GDP and per capita GDP, a binary variable indicating if either of the two countries is landlocked, 2 binary variables referring to colonization links (if trading partners ever colonized each other; if trading partners were ever colonized by the same colonizer, after 1945), and common language. According to the model results, the following statistically significant effects can be indicated; positive effect on trade flow: common

border, preferential trade agreements, exporter's GDP, landlocked, colony, and common language; negative effect on trade flow: distance, exporter's per capita GDP.

Kalaba and Kirsten (2012) examined the possible causes for poor trade performance in a tariff-reducing environment, based on the hypothesis that NTMs may be more trade-constraining than tariffs. To do so, they applied a gravity model using the 2000-2010 intra-SADC (Southern African Development Community) dairy trade. Four dairy product categories were examined separately: concentrated milk, unconcentrated milk, butter & cream, and cheese; only 11 out of the 15 SADC countries were taken into account, mainly due to lack of data. Exports between countries were the model's dependent variable; determining variables consisted of importer's and exporter's GDP, tariffs imposed by the importer, a dummy variable noting the presence of NTMs, and a time-invariant variable capturing trade costs (i.e., including bilateral distance, common border, language, colonizer, whether one or both are landlocked, members of an RTA). Referring to the results, differences concerning statistical significance and sign occur between the four dairy product categories; Focusing on tariffs and NTMs, it could be indicated that tariff has a statistically significant negative effect on concentrated milk and butter & cream, while NTMs have, on a statistically significant level, a negative effect on concentrated milk and a positive effect on butter & cream.

Pokrivcak *et al.* (2013) examined the NTMs set by Russia on dairy products, and their effect on the EU's dairy exports. The results of a performed survey indicated that several standards considering imported dairy products were seen as redundant and pointless. In addition, conformity assessment procedures were identified as a significant issue for countries exporting to Russia, as they were identified as "nontransparent, time-consuming and expose exporters to significant risk that their products may be refused entry at the Russian border". In addition, it was estimated that NTMs increased cost by 5-10%. A gravity model was developed; dairy products bilateral trade was set as the dependent variable, based on data on the exports of dairy products for the 13 world major dairy trading countries (note: the EU was represented as a single unit). Independent variables included importer and exporter GDP, the distance between the two countries' capitals, common language, common border, membership of a preferential trade agreement, and import tariffs. In addition, the model included dummy variables for trading pairs, to control for country-pair-specific fixed effects (including the effect of NTMs) affecting bilateral trade. According to the results of the performed gravity model, exporters' and importers' GDP have a positive effect on dairy product exports and imports respectively; distance has a negative effect, constraining trade; common language, border, and participation in free trade areas have a positive effect, leading to higher dairy trade. NTMs were also found to be statistically significant, with different effects, depending on the country pair: NTMs were more constraining for USA exports, rather than for EU exports to Russia; New Zealand's exports to Russia were influenced the least by NTMs. In any case, the results of the study do not indicate that Russian NTMs are significantly more constraining, in comparison to other countries' NTMs.

Sanjuán López *et al.* (2013) applied a gravity model taking into account all dairy codes in aggregation; the model involved the 2004-2007 period, taking into account 128 regions (not specifically defined in the study). The value of imports between each country pair was defined as the dependent variable of the model. Independent variables consisted of the power of the import tariff rate (measured in ad-valorem equivalents), the distance between country capitals, common border, common language, colonial linkage, latitude difference between countries, country remoteness (calculated as GDP weighted average of the distance to the countries with which each country trades), and per capita income (expressed as the difference between the importer's and the exporter's per capita income). Results indicated that all variables were statistically significant, with common border, common language, colonial linkage, and country remoteness having a positive effect, and import tariff rate, distance, latitude difference, and per capita income difference, a negative effect.

Fathelrahman *et al.* (2014) explored potential dairy products trade between selected major dairy-products exporting countries (Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands, and the USA) and the six GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council) countries (i.e., Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Oman, Kuwait, Qatar, and Bahrain), having in mind that GCC countries are not able to cover the increasing demand for dairy products (among other livestock products), due to the challenging environment and the decreasing stock of natural resources. The model took into account the aggregation of dairy products (expressed in milk equivalent) for the 2000-2010 period. The dependent variable is expressed as the value of dairy product exports from the origin to the destination country, while independent variables comprise of annual time effect (a dummy variable is included for each year), GDP, or per capita GDP for the origin and destination countries, the population of the destination country (expressed either as total population or population <14 years old), common borders, and distance between the countries. The analysis's findings indicate a positive effect of GDP and population on dairy trade and a negative effect of distance between countries.

Owen and Winchester (2014) applied a gravity model examining the effect of tariffs and TRQs (Tariff Rate Quotas), on the global trade of concentrated milk products. The model was fitted based on data from 15 exporters and 22 importers, i.e. the leading concentrated milk products [as defined by the GTAP (Global Trade Analysis Project) database] trading nations between 2005 and 2009. The model's dependent variable represented exports of concentrated dairy products from the exporting to the importing country. Independent variables comprised of ad valorem own tariff, ad valorem equivalent of tariffs and TRQs on dairy products, the distance between countries, common border, colonial link, common language, and FTA partnership. The study's results indicated a statistically significant positive effect of common language, common border, and participation in the EU on the concentrated milk exports, and a negative effect of ad valorem own tariff, distance, and the Australia-New Zealand CER (Closer Economic Relations) agreement.

Sun *et al.* (2014), through the application of a gravity model, investigated the effect of China's food safety standards on dairy products trade. The dependent variable of the model is expressed as the value of dairy imports from other countries to China. The model included data from ten major exporting countries, accounting for >95% of the total value of China's dairy imports between 1992 and 2010. The dataset contained data on "Concentrated milk and cream" (i.e. HS 0402), based on the rationale that imported dairy products by China are dominated by the specific product category. Determining variables include changes in China's food safety standards (based on two different measurements: a) maximum residue limits for lead and b) the number of regulations imposed on hazardous substances and bacteria in dairy products), China's (i.e., the importer's) GDP, the total output of dairy products of the exporting country, tariffs faced by the exporting country, and a dummy variable expressing the effect of the milk crisis in 2008 on imports due to changes of consumers' preference for domestic and imported dairy products. According to the study's results, food safety standards did not have any effect on China's dairy imports, a result not so surprising when taking into account that China's food safety standards are comparatively lower than those of its major exporters. On the other hand, tariffs harm imports, while exporters' total output and the dummy variable expressing the effect of the milk crisis in 2008 had a positive effect on China's dairy (HS 0402) imports.

Ishaqa *et al.* (2015) examined food safety effect on China's dairy products trade, having in mind the 2008 melamine baby milk powder contamination incident. Data used corresponded to the 2007-2012 period; while dairy products were categorized into 2 groups: a) milk and cream, and milk products other than butter or cheese, and b) dairy products and birds egg. The dependent variable represents the bilateral trade flow. Referring to the independent variables, they include a dummy variable differentiating between the pre and post-melamine periods, a dummy variable indicating the imposition of a ban due to the incident, distance between countries, tariffs, a dummy variable indicating if the partner country is landlocked, per capita economic sizes, partner's dairy production, common language, and regional trade agreements. Based on the analysis results, the melamine incident affected Chinese exports. Common language and border, regional trade agreements, and per capita economic size have a positive effect on China's exports, while, a negative effect on China's exports is indicated in the case of a landlocked partner or an increase in the partner's dairy production.

Schaak (2015) applied a gravity model to explore the effect of the ASEAN (Association of Southeast Asian Nations)-China-FTA on dairy products' international trade, namely to trade creation and trade diversion. The model included data from 36 countries [25 largest dairy exporting countries (1995-2013), China and ASEAN member countries]. The dataset contains data on the three SITC dairy product groups as well as their aggregate. The dataset contained data for four product categories: "Milk and cream and milk products other than butter or cheese" (SITC 022), "Butter and other fats and oils derived from milk" (SITC 023), "Cheese and curd" (SITC 024)

and their aggregated values “Total dairy products” (SITC 022 + 023 + 024). In the applied model, the market share of the exporting country is used as the dependent variable, while explanatory variables include dummy variables for the FTA effects, importing country-specific effects, and exporting country-specific effects. The estimates of the model included significant values for all framework effects, revealing trade creation, and/or trade diversion effects for all four dairy product groups. To conclude, the estimated overall net trade effect is negative, meaning that the current implementation of the FTA should be critically evaluated concerning dairy products.

Hndi *et al.* (2016) applied a gravity model to investigate the effect of FTAs on dairy trade flows. The study targeted specific North African countries (Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, and Tunisia) as reference countries and the rest of the world as partner countries, taking into account the 1991 to 2013 period. Concerning the data applied, it should be noted that the term “dairy” is used in general, without defining if only particular dairy product groups (according to SITC or HS classification) were taken into account. Trade flow between country pairs is defined as the model’s dependent variable. The determinants of the model comprise of importers and exporters GDP, importers and exporters population, geographical distance between the countries economical centers (in most cases, the countries’ capitals), common language, colonial relationship, and membership in FTAs. According to the model’s results, on a statistically significant level, importer’s and exporter’s GDP have a positive effect on dairy trade flow; importer’s and exporter’s population have a negative effect; common language has a positive effect; distance has a positive effect (in contrary to what was expected). FTAs, in general, don’t have a significant effect; however, when referring specifically to the AGADIR FTA, a significant effect that increases trade flow between signatory countries by more than 100% is indicated.

Sanjuan *et al.* (2017), prompted by the –at the time- ongoing EU trade negotiations, quantified NTMs’ effect (with a specific focus on SPSs and TBTs) on key EU dairy exports, based on a gravity model. The work took into account key African, Asian, and South American markets, for the 2009-2014 time period; 38 importers and 124 exporters (EU members were examined individually) were included in the model. 20 dairy HS-6 digit codes were taken into account being aggregated to HS4-digit level (i.e., 0401 to 0406). The model’s dependent variable was bilateral imports, while the independent variables comprised of power of the import tariff rate, GDP, per capita GDP, a dummy variable indicating the existence of FTAs, common currency, common language, colonial ties, geographical distance indicators (weighted distance by internal populations between the main countries’ cities, internal distance of countries, latitude difference, landlocked countries, common border), and country remoteness (calculated as GDP weighted average of the distance to the countries with which each country trades). Considering NTMs, a dummy variable indicates the existence of measures, while specific variables are included to examine the trade effect of a) SPS/TBTs and b) other NTMs. Based on the analysis’s results NTMs have a negative sign, thus indicating that the presence of NTMs in the third countries has an overall negative effect on trade [however, with some differences between the three markets

(Africa, Asia, and South America) taken into account). Moreover, it was revealed that SPS/TBT measures dominate the NTM effect in the dairy trade. It should be noted that better (in terms of statistical significance) results were retrieved, when the variables indicating the different NTM categories were applied, in relation to using the dummy variable expressing the existence of NTMs in general.

Berndt and Hess (2019) explored, through a gravity model, the EU's dairy sector export opportunities occurring due to the JEFTA (Japan-EU Free Trade Agreement). Disaggregated dairy trade data for the 15 products (on an HS 6-digit level) of the four most important -in terms of Japanese imports from the EU- dairy products ["Milk and cream" (0402), "Whey [...]" (0404), "Butter [...]" (0405) and "Cheese and curd" (0406)] were taken under consideration. The dependent variable was expressed as the trade flow from the exporter to the importer; determining variables included importer's and exporter's GDP, imposed tariffs, the existence of regional trade agreement between partners, and two dummy variables concerning NTMs: the first one indicating the existence of SPSs or TBTs, the second indicating the existence of NTMs other than SPSs or TBTs. Based on the model results, the importer's GDP (positive effect) and tariffs (negative effect) are the most important determining variables, with GDP being statistically significant for fewer products, but having a stronger effect compared to tariffs.

Kontsevaya *et al.* (2020) investigated the current international agricultural trade conditions between Russia and the EU (29 countries in total, 28 EU members, and Russia) while examining the effect of the Russian import ban. In this context, a gravity model was applied for dairy products for the 2000-2017 period; as not indicated differently in the study, it is assumed that the analysis was based on the aggregation of all dairy products. The dependent variable of the model was defined as the dairy trade flow. Independent variables included the importer's and exporter's GDP, the distance between EU capital and Moscow or St. Petersburg, common border, common language, common history (existence of active relations for the last 100 years), existence of a seaport in both countries, and a variable indicating the Russian import ban. The model's results indicate that, on a statistically significant level, common historical ties, and the importer's and exporter's GDP have a positive effect on dairy trade, while the Russian ban on imports affects trade negatively.

3.3. Gravity analysis of the dairy international market

Bellow, we present the gravity model used in the case of dairy, the data set used in the estimation of the model, and the empirical results obtained from the estimation of the dairy gravity model.

3.3.1. The gravity model of the dairy international market

The gravity model of dairy is based on that of the wine, Eq. (2.3.5), and it is given by Eq. (3.3.1) below:

$$\ln X_{ijt} = c^* + \alpha \ln M_{it} + \beta \ln M_{jt} + \delta_1 \ln D_{ij} + \delta_2 \ln(1 + tr_{jt}) + \delta_{31} \ln(1 + sps_{jt}) + \delta_{32} \ln(1 + tbt_{jt}) + \delta_{33} \ln(1 + ontm_{jt}) + \delta_4 \ln(1 + tag_{ijt}) + \gamma Comlang_{ij} + \zeta_1 eu_i + \zeta_2 eu_j + \zeta_3 euaf_{ij} + \eta_1 ukrest_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (3.3.1)$$

where X_{ijt} are the country's exports i to destination j at time t ; M_{it} represents the exporter's supply (i.e., the dairy production of country i) at time t ; M_{jt} is the GDP of country j at time t ; D_{ij} is the geographical distance between the capitals of countries i, j ; tr_j represents the *ad valorem* equivalent tariff imposed by country j to country's i exports; the variables sps_{jt} , tbt_{jt} and $ontm_{jt}$ belong to the class of NTMs and represent Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards, Technical Barriers to Trade and other NTMs, respectively, imposed by the importing country; tag_{ijt} a dummy variable indicating if the trading partners are engaged bilaterally in a regional trade agreement; $Comlang_{ij}$ a dummy variable taking the value of 1 if countries share a common official or primary language; eu_i (eu_j) is a dummy variable assuming the value of 1 if the exporting (importing) county is a member of EU; $euaf_{ij}$ taking the value of 1 if trading partners are an EU and an African country; $ukrest_{ij}$ assuming the value of 1 if trading partners are the UK and a non-EU country member; ε_{ij} is the error term and it is assumed to be identically and independently distributed.

3.3.2. Data used in the dairy gravity model

This section provides the description, data sources, and descriptive statistics of the variables used in the gravity model.

Table 3.3.1. Variable definition, descriptive statistics, and data sources

Variables	Variable Definition	Descriptive Statistics	Data Sources
X_{ij} (Trade flows from country i to j)	Trade flow as reported by the importer in thousands current US\$)	Mean: 9881.305 Min: 0.001 Max: 3488119 St. dev.: 64699.36	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
M_{it} (Production-exporter)	Number of dairy cows	Mean: 7.63e+09 Min: 0 Max: 8.79e+11 St. dev.: 5.39e+10	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United States https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data
M_{jt} (GDP-importer)	GDP (current thousands US\$)	Mean: 7.00e+08 Min: 0 Max: 2.14e+10 St. dev.: 2.38e+09	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
D_{ij} (Distance)	Distance between the most populated city of	Mean: 5651.72 Min: 0 Max: 19747.4 St. dev.: 4400.558	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8

	each country (km)		
tr_{jt} (MFN applied rates-importer)	Ad valorem (on value) tariff rate	Mean: 158.70 Min: 0 Max: 1428.33 St. dev.: 220.54	World Integrated Trade Solution https://wits.worldbank.org/
sps_{jt} (Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 0.07 Min: 0 Max: 7 St. dev.: 0.36	WTO, Integrated Trade Intelligence Portal (I-TIP) https://i-tip.wto.org/goods/Forms/TableView.aspx
tbt_{jt} (Technical Barriers to Trade)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 0.162 Min: 0 Max: 14 St. dev.: 0.706	WTO, Integrated Trade Intelligence Portal (I-TIP) https://i-tip.wto.org/goods/Forms/TableView.aspx
$ontm_{jt}$ (Other non-tariff measures)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 0.54 Min: 0 Max: 46 St. dev.: 3.06	WTO, Integrated Trade Intelligence Portal (I-TIP) https://i-tip.wto.org/goods/Forms/TableView.aspx
tag_{ijt} (Regional trade agreements)	1 if the pair currently has a RTA	Mean: 0.0087 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.093	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
$Comlang_{ij}$	1 if countries share a common official or primary language	Mean: 0.195 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.396	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
eu_i (EU member-exporter)	1 if the exporting country currently is an EU member	Mean: 0.414 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.493	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
eu_j (EU member-importer)	1 if the importing country currently is an EU member	Mean: 0.178 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.383	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
$euaf_{ij}$ (Trading partnership EU – African countries)	1 if the trading partners are EU and African countries	Mean: 0.0798 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.271	
$ukrest_{ij}$ (Trading partnership UK-non-EU country)	1 if the trading partners are the UK and a non-EU member	Mean: 0.992 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.090	

3.3.3. Empirical results of the dairy gravity model

First, we apply ordinary least squares (OLS) in Eq. (3.3.1) to obtain estimates of the unknown parameters. The OLS are the best linear unbiased estimators if the errors (ε_{ij}) of Eq. (3.3.1) are independently and identically distributed with a constant variance of σ_{ε}^2 . However, these conditions are violated as indicated by the White test and Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity and the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation (Table 3.3.2). Thus, as in the case of wine, we use the Driscoll and Kraay (1998) correction to fix heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. Failure to correct for autocorrelation can result in understated standard errors (Moulton, 1990).

Table 3.3.2. White Test and Breusch-Pagan test for Heteroscedasticity & Wooldridge test for autocorrelation

White Test		Breusch-Pagan tests/Cook-Weisberg test		Wooldridge test	
F(2, 62322)= 52.05	Prob>F=0.0000	chi2(1)= 550.55	Prob>chi2=0.0000	F(1, 6135) = 658.134	Prob > F = 0.0000

Notes: H_0 for White's test is that the variances for the errors are equal

H_0 for Breusch-Pagan tests/Cook-Weisberg test assumes constant variance

H_0 for the Wooldridge test assumes no first-order autocorrelation

The second column of Table 3.3.3 presents results for pooled OLS (OLS_POOLED) estimation of Eq. (3.3.1), while the third column shows OLS estimates of Eq. (3.3.1) with yearly fixed effects included (OLS_FE).

Table 3.3.3. Estimation results of Eq. (5)

Variables	(1) OLS_POOLED	(2) OLS_FE	(3) PPML	(4) PPML_ME
<i>Intercept</i>	4.6489*** (0.592)	5.2664*** (0.595)	1.3528*** (0.091)	
M_{it} (Production of exporter)	0.0077 (0.010)	0.0093 (0.010)	0.0020 (0.002)	0.0109 (0.011)
M_{jt} (Per capital GDP-importer)	0.3666*** (0.015)	0.3765*** (0.015)	0.0712*** (0.002)	0.3788*** (0.015)
D_{ij} (Distance)	-0.6294*** (0.038)	-0.6318*** (0.038)	-0.1177*** (0.006)	-0.6264*** (0.035)
tr_{jt} (MFN applied rates-importer)	-0.0975*** (0.011)	-0.1025*** (0.012)	-0.0189*** (0.002)	-0.1006*** (0.011)
sps_{jt} (Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards)	-0.1249 (0.088)	-0.2181** (0.094)	-0.0280* (0.015)	-0.1491* (0.081)

tb_{jt} (Technical Barriers to Trade)	-0.1635*** (0.050)	-0.2277*** (0.055)	-0.0292*** (0.008)	-0.1553** (0.047)
$ontm_{jt}$ (Other non-tariff measures)	-0.0941* (0.048)	-0.1704*** (0.054)	-0.0185** (0.008)	-0.0984** (0.044)
tag_{ijt} (Regional trade agreements)	0.5825*** (0.177)	0.4031** (0.189)	0.1039*** (0.027)	0.5527*** (0.148)
$Comlang_{ij}$ (Countries share common official or primary language)	0.8895*** (0.086)	0.8885*** (0.086)	0.1736*** (0.015)	0.9239*** (0.083)
eu_i (EU member-exporter)	1.7661*** (0.073)	1.7725*** (0.073)	0.3374*** (0.014)	1.7949*** (0.074)
eu_j (EU member-importer)	-0.4631*** (0.099)	-0.4176*** (0.100)	-0.0956*** (0.017)	-0.5090*** (0.093)
$euaf_{ij}$ (Trading partnership EU – AF)	-0.7448*** (0.093)	-0.7409*** (0.093)	-0.1306*** (0.019)	-0.6950*** (0.103)
$ukrest_{ij}$ (Trading partnership UK-nonEU country)	-1.3277*** (0.417)	-1.3303*** (0.415)	-0.1454** (0.046)	-0.7739** (0.246)
2010.year (Dummy variable)		-0.0459 (0.031)		
2011.year (Dummy variable)		0.0676* (0.037)		
2012.year (Dummy variable)		-0.0020 (0.038)		
2013.year (Dummy variable)		0.0611 (0.038)		
2014.year (Dummy variable)		-0.0832** (0.039)		
2015.year (Dummy variable)		-0.2448*** (0.039)		
2016.year (Dummy variable)		-0.3711*** (0.042)		
2017.year (Dummy variable)		-0.3366*** (0.045)		
2018.year (Dummy variable)		-0.3035*** (0.045)		
2019.year (Dummy variable)		-0.0349 (0.049)		
Statistics	N= 62,325 F(13, 7910) = 135.81	N= 62,325 F(23, 7910)=90.58	N= 62,325 R- squared=0.583	

	Prob > F = 0.0000	Prob > F = 0.0000	LL =- 163010.59	
	R-squared= 0.574	R-squared= 0.576	AIC=326049.2	
	Root MSE=2.922	Root MSE=2.919	BIC=326175.7	
	LL =-155269.4	LL =-155188.7		
	AIC=310566.8	AIC=310425.5		
	BIC=310693.3	BIC=310642.5		

Notes: *, **, *** denote 10, 5, and 1 percent significance level, respectively; N denotes the number of observations; LL is the log-likelihood; AIC and BIC are the Akaike's and Schwarz's Bayesian information criteria, respectively.

A log-likelihood ratio test supports the inclusion of the annual dummy variables in Eq. (3.3.1) and thus, the OLS_FE model is preferred over the OLS_POOLED. In particular, the value of the log-likelihood test is equal to 161.4, suggesting the rejection of the null hypothesis that the time effects are not statistically significant at the 1% significance level. Column four of Table 3.3.3 presents the estimates of Eq. (3.3.1) using the Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML) estimation approach, while column five provides the marginal effects based on the PPML estimates. We estimated the PPML model for checking the robustness of our results. Note that the advantage of the PPML model is that it corrects for sample selection bias that might result from excluding zero observations. Since we have considered only trade flows with a positive value of the global dairy traded, selection bias is not present. As a result, we expect that the magnitude, statistical significance, and economic interpretation of marginal effects obtained from the PPML model would be very similar to those of the OLS_POOLED and OLS_FE approaches. A thorough inspection of Table 3.3.3 shows that the empirical results obtained from the three estimation approaches (i.e., OLS_POOLED, OLS_FE and PPML) are similar. However, the results between the OLS_FE and PPML models are more similar. In the rest of the section, unless specified otherwise, we refer to the estimates from the OLS_FE model.

First, the R-squared is 0.576, which shows that the explanatory variables account for about 58% of the observed variation in the wine trade in the data, indicating that the model fits the data relatively well. Furthermore, the F-test is statistically significant at the 1% level, which provides second support of the satisfying performance of the model. The dairy production of the exporter (M_{it}) and the per capita GDP of the importer (M_{jt}) are both positively associated with trade. However only M_{jt} is statistically significant at the 1% level of significance. M_{it} represents the number of cows in the exporting country as a proxy for dairy production since dairy production data are unavailable for all sample countries. Thus, the number of cows might not capture dairy production adequately. The results show that we would expect that a 1% increase in importer GDP would increase dairy trade by about 0.38%. On the other hand, the coefficient on distance (D_{ij}) is negative at the 1% significance level, indicating that a 1% increase in distance tends to reduce trade by about 0.63%. A

comparison with previous literature supports our findings regarding the effects of GDP of the importer and the distance between the trading partners on dairy trade flows (e.g., Pokrivak *et al.*, 2013; Fathelrahman *et al.*, 2014; Owen and Winchester, 2014; Berndt and Hess, 2019).

The effect of the *ad valorem* equivalent tariffs (tr_{jt}) is negative and statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that a 1% increase in the tariff rate will decrease trade by about 0.103%. The small effect of tariffs on trade flows might be because tariffs remained relatively stable during the study period. In other words, tariffs in the main destination countries did not vary significantly to provoke any substantial effect on trade. Furthermore, all the NTMs are statistically significant at the conventional level of significance. In particular, the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards (sps_{jt}) are statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that a 1% increase in sps_j in the importing country will reduce trade flows by about 0.22%. The Technical Barriers to Trade (tbt_{jt}) are statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating that a 1% increase in tbt_j in the importing country will reduce trade flows by about 0.23%. The other NTMs ($ontm_{jt}$) are statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that a 1% increase in $ontm_j$ in the importing country will reduce trade flows by about 0.17%. The present study indicates that NTMs are more trade-constraining than tariffs. Our findings agree with most of the empirical evidence of the previous literature on the effect of tariffs and NTMs on dairy trade flows. For example, the study by Kalaba and Kirsten (2012) finds that tariffs have a negative and statistically significant effect on concentrated milk and butter & cream, while NTMs have a negative and significant effect on concentrated milk but a positive effect on butter & cream; Pokrivcak *et al.* (2013) find that NTMs were trade constraining; Sanjuan Lopez *et al.* (2013) find that import tariff rates have a negative effect on dairy trade; Sun *et al.* (2014) indicate that China's food safety standards do not have any significant effect on dairy products trade; Sanjuan *et al.* (2017) suggests that NTMs and especially SPS and TBTs have an overall negative effect on trade; Berndt and Hess (2019) find that tariffs have a negative effect and are the most important determining variables on dairy trade.

Regional trade agreements (tag_{ijt}) have a positive and statistically significant effect on trade, showing a 0.40% increase on trade for a 1% increase of tag_{ij} . This finding agrees with the study by Ishaqa *et al.* (2015). However, the study by Schaak (2015) supports a negative effect of the free trade agreements on trade, while the study by Hndi *et al.* (2016) finds an insignificant effect on dairy trade.

Common language ($Comlang_{ij}$) has a positive and statistically significant effect on trade, showing a 0.89% increase in trade if trading partners share the same language. This finding is supported by the studies of Haq and Ishaq (2008); Haq *et al.* (2013); Ishaqa *et al.* (2015); Hndi *et al.* (2016).

The statistical significance of the dummy variable, eu_i , indicates that trade flows are greater by 1.77% when the export country is an EU country compared to the case

where the exporting country is not an EU country. However, in the case where the importing country is an EU country (i.e., consider the dummy variable, eu_j) the trade flows are lower by 0.42% compared to the case where the importing country is not an EU country. These results support the conclusion that the EU is a significant exporter in the global wine trade and enhances the global dairy trade.

The trading partnership *EU – AFRICA* as indicated by the $euaf_{ij}$ dummy is negative and statistically significant at any conventional level of significance, indicating that the trade between the EU and the African countries is 0.74% lower than the trade between EU and non-African countries. Furthermore, the trade between the UK and the rest of the world, excluding the EU, is much less than the average global dairy trade, as it is supported by the negative and statistically significant value (i.e., -1.3303) corresponding to the coefficient of the dummy variable $ukrest_{ij}$. This finding could indicate that the BREXIT might not have an adverse effect on the EU's global dairy trade position, since UK's trade flows with the rest of the world are much below the average global dairy trade and even weaker than the EU's dairy trade with the rest of the world.

Finally, the coefficients of the yearly dummy variables show that the dairy international trade flow for the period 2014-2018 is statistically significantly lower than that of the year 2009 while the trade flows for the years 2010, 2012, 2013, and 2019 are not statistically significantly different than that of the trade flow of the year 2009. Only the trade flow of the year 2011 is statistically greater than the trade flow of the year 2009 at the 10% level of statistical significance. These results indicate that in recent years the global dairy trade has deteriorated.

3.4. Conclusions of the dairy international market

This analysis provides evidence that network interactions in the dairy sector highlight the changing global trade in the dairy sector. More precisely, across all benchmark years, we observe that the strong European economies like Germany, France, the Netherlands, Italy, and Spain are the leading players, in terms of strong trade value connections, keeping substantial trade flows between them and other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. Similarly, the USA, Australia, and China represent another significant group, which is characterized by its strong trades in the dairy industry. On the other hand, the UK holds a moderate position in the network with both strong and weak trade flows with various partners, indicating that the BREXIT may cause a small effect on dairy international trade. Finally, Africa's presence on the network is scarce. Africa, and in particular Ethiopia and Tanzania who are the leading cattle keepers in Africa, have a very low ratio of dairy output per cow, due to the breeds used; hence, most of the milk is used for domestic consumption, while processing is negligible. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top dairy exporters in 2019 are Germany, New Zealand, the Netherlands, France, the USA, Italy, Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, Poland, the UK, Belarus, and Australia. In the same year, the top importers are

Germany, China, the Netherlands, Italy, the UK, France, Belgium, Russia, Spain, the USA, Japan, Mexico, and Saudi Arabia.

Based on the literature review performed on gravity models, the main determinants of dairy trade flows consist of importer's and exporter's (per capita) GDP and population, the distance between the trading countries, geographical position (in terms of common borders, latitude difference, and the existence of a landlocked partner), historical and cultural factors (common language, historical ties, colonial links), specific political and economic conditions (e.g. bans, food-safety related incidents), and trade-related aspects in the form of common participation in FTAs, and imposed tariffs and/or NTMs by the importing country.

The empirical results of the gravity dairy model estimated in the present discussion paper for the 2009-2019 period provide the following conclusions. First, the economic activity captured by the importer's GDP positively affects dairy trade flows, while the distance between trading partners has a negative impact. Second, tariffs have a negative but minimal impact on the dairy trade. Third, all NTMs (i.e., Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards, Technical Barriers to Trade, and other NTMs) have a significant negative impact on trade. Fourth, regional trade agreements, as well as a common language, have a relatively significant positive effect on trade. Fifth, EU dairy exports (imports) to the rest of the world are well above (below) the average international dairy trade flows. This indicates that the EU is a significant exporting region but a less significant importing region in the global dairy trade. Fifth, the trade between the UK and the rest of the world (excluding the EU) is less than the average international dairy trade, indicating that the BREXIT might not affect the EU's global dairy trade position. Finally, the trading partnership between the EU and African countries is less than the average international dairy trade.

4 BEEF

4.1. Network analysis and results of the beef international market

In this section the world's major beef exporters and importers are illustrated, using data on trade flows from 2010 to 2019. Our data is stemming from the BACI dataset from CEPII, the leading French center for research and expertise on the world economy. Furthermore, our sample consists of those countries with a value of beef trade flows greater than 90 million dollars which represents about 5% of total trade. This threshold is used to exclude small trade flows to eliminate unnecessary noise originating from such trades. The detailed list of beef codes used in this study is found in Appendix B3.

Figure 4.1.1 illustrates the leading beef exporters in the 2010 benchmark year. The ranking includes a considerable number of European countries. Australia leads the way as a beef exporter, with a percentage of around 12%, followed by Brazil, which has a similar ratio. The USA, the Netherlands, and Germany also play a pivotal role in exports, albeit in a smaller proportion than the previous countries. The following countries, i.e., France, New Zealand, Canada, Poland, Italy, and Argentina, display a smaller trade export value, with a ratio of around 2%.

Figure 4.1.1

Continuing to Figure 4.1.2, we display the top beef exporters in the 2013 reference year. A similar pattern can be seen as in the preceding graph, with a flip between Australia and Brazil, which is currently ranked first. The presence of India's massive market, which rises to fourth place, with a share of export value of almost 10% is particularly noteworthy. Belarus, the UK, and Spain are in the lowest rankings of the chart, in terms of export value.

Figure 4.1.2

Figure 4.1.3, displays beef exports, for the reference year 2016. According to this figure, we have a similar pattern with the reference year 2013. Australia, the USA, and Brazil continue to be at the top of the ranking as the leading beef exporters. In addition, with a market share of roughly 3%, New Zealand and Uruguay appear to have maintained their positions in the market. On the other hand, Germany has lost a major portion of its export volume this year and appears to be hovering around 3%. Spain, Belarus, and the UK continue to be at the lowest rankings.

Figure 4.1.3

Figure 4.1.4, illustrates the most recent data we have, concerning beef exports, for the benchmark year 2019. A similar pattern can be seen as in Figure 4.1.3, with a flip between the USA and Brazil, which is currently ranked second. The presence of Argentina, which appears to have a spectacular rise to fourth place with a portion of around 5%, is particularly noteworthy.

Figure 4.1.4

In the following Figures 4.1.5 through 4.1.8, we illustrate the major beef importers with the assumptions introduced at the beginning of our analysis. A quite different scenario is depicted in comparison to the beef export flows. Furthermore, the countries' rankings in the global beef trade have been inverted in comparison with the export trends.

Figure 4.1.5 displays the top beef importers for the reference year 2010. Italy and the Russian massive market appear to maintain a dominant position in the import ranking, having the largest percentage of approximately 9%. The USA and Japan also play significant roles, while the EU (i.e., France, the Netherlands, the UK, and Ireland), has roughly equal representation. Furthermore, a number of countries from Europe, Asia, as well as Canada are at the bottom of the rankings based on their import value.

Figure 4.1.5

In Figure 4.1.6, which displays the reference year 2013 of beef importers, we have an almost identical visualization, in comparison to Figure 4.1.5. With a substantial share of 15% of the import volume, the USA is in the first place. Another noteworthy

feature is Japan’s boosting role in trade, which is reflected in its third-place ranking. A mixed depiction of a large number of countries is followed by the participation of European, African, and Asian countries, holding a proportion of approximately 3 to 1.5%.

Figure 4.1.6

Figure 4.1.7 illustrates the major beef importing countries for the benchmark year of 2016. The most striking feature is the USA’s supremacy, which stands in contrast to Japan, which accounts for half of the USA’s import value. In what follows, China has begun to emerge as a central player, holding third place with a percentage of approximately 6%. Furthermore, Hong Kong has dropped in the rankings and is now in the middle of the graph with a proportion of around 4%. Finally, in the last positions, we have the same countries as in the previous reference year.

Figure 4.1.7

Figure 4.1.8 presents the leading importing countries for the benchmark year of 2019. The Asian economy appears to maintain a dominant position in the import ranking. China holds first place with a substantial difference from the USA, which now ranks second. The EU has a considerable presence with the appearance of Italy, Germany, and France. Based on their import value Iran, Portugal, and the United Arab Emirates are at the bottom of the rankings.

Figure 4.1.8

In what follows we shall use metrics of centrality to estimate the heterogeneity of countries in the global trade network. As we have described previously, in social network research, centrality is one of the most widely used topics. A significant number of measures have been developed, including degree centrality, closeness, betweenness, eigenvector centrality, information centrality, flow betweenness, the rush index, and the influence measures.

Each node represents a country in the network, which is denoted with its corresponding 3-code acronym. Different lines connect different countries. These lines represent the volume of the trade flows between the countries depicted. Therefore, in what follows we display our analysis for the visualization of the data. In Appendix B3 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016.

Figure 4.1.9 presents beef network analysis for the years 2019 based on eigenvector centrality (in Appendix B3 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). The beef network appears to have a well-defined structure, with Europe taking the lead. More precisely, Germany, the Netherlands, France, and Italy distinguish in the beef network analysis, having strong flows with a large number of nations in Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. South America, which is represented by Brazil, is a second prominent pole. Another important player is Asia. The top central players, China and Japan, appear to have strong trade flows with several EU countries as well as with countries from other continents. Another trading group with lower trade value is Israel. Finally, the visualizations display Turkey's, Algeria's, and Mexico's low rankings for 2019, 2016, and 2013 in terms of beef trade flows.

Figure 4.1.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figures 4.1.10 depicts the beef network analysis for the year 2019 based on authority centrality (in Appendix B3 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe that the European countries have increased their power as core players with extensive economic linkages to a variety of other countries and continents. On the other hand, the USA continues to be a prominent player with extensive trade ties with Europe, Mexico, and Japan. Another noteworthy feature is Brazil as a top trading country, with significant trade flows with a number of countries. Furthermore, some MERCOSUR (Mercado Común del Sur) countries, like Uruguay and Paraguay, appear to have moderate trade flows. The appearance of Turkey reveals a small trade flow in beef, whereas Belarus’s representation especially in 2019 reveals the same low trend.

Figure 4.1.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Authority Centrality

In terms of centrality hub, in Figure 4.1.11, we present the beef network trade in reference years 2019 (in Appendix B3 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). A large number of countries appear to have strong participation, according to the measure of centrality hub. Across all benchmark years, we observe the strong economy of Europe, with France, the Netherlands, and Spain having a central role. On the other hand, Brazil’s boosting market and Hong Kong represent another significant trade group, keeping substantial flows between them and other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. Finally, several countries, such as Myanmar, Turkey, and El Salvador, maintain a modest position in terms of trade flows.

Figure 4.1.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure 4.1.12 depicts the beef network analysis for the year 2019 based on centrality betweenness (in Appendix B3 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe that the EU with a variety of nations, like Germany, Spain, Poland, and the Netherlands is a major pole of the beef trade. The USA composes another substantial group, having strong trade flows with a large number of countries in Europe and across the globe. It's noteworthy that, in terms of centrality betweenness, several countries appear to have moderate trade linkages, like Hungary and Canada. Furthermore, a small number of nations, such as Greece and Malaysia, have limited trade flows and have been relegated to the network's periphery.

Figure 4.1.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

In terms of centrality closeness (Figure 4.1.13 for 2019; in Appendix B3 you will find the figures for years 2010, 2013, 2016), the result is a framework that emphasizes the importance of the EU with the participation of many countries. At the same time, Brazil seems to interact with a variety of countries in Europe and other continents based on beef trade flows. Furthermore, the USA has a substantial contribution to beef trade interaction as a central player, for all benchmark years. Over the years, there are strong network flows between the top countries and other continents. China and Japan appear to be forming a moderate pole. Finally, certain nations, such as Korea and Turkey are on the margin of the trade flows.

Figure 4.1.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019– Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

4.2. Gravity literature review of the beef international market

Wilson *et al.* (2003), having in mind food safety disputes such as that between the USA and EU over hormone-treated beef, employ a gravity model to examine the impact of differing national standards (in specific, tetracycline standards) on trade in beef and the trade effect of setting harmonized international standards. Data refer to 16 exporting and six importing countries, for SITC 0111 (fresh, chilled, or frozen beef), between 1995 and 2000. Trade between the EU members was excluded, as cross-border regulation is exempted in many cases between the member states. The dependent variable referred to the value of bilateral trade flow. Independent variables consisted of importer’s and exporter’s GNP (Gross National Product), importer’s and exporter’s population, distance, tetracycline residue standards in the importing country, a dummy indicating the EU ban on the USA and Canadian beef that are hormone-treated, a dummy indicating FMD (foot and mouth disease outbreaks), FTAs [a dummy for each of NAFTA (North American Free Trade Agreement) and APEC (Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation)], colonial ties and year dummies (to control systematic differences across time). On a statistically significant level, importer’s and

exporter's GNP, colonial ties have a positive effect on trade flows, while the importer's and exporter's population, more stringent standards set by the importer, distance, hormone ban, and APEC membership have a negative effect.

Gervais *et al.* (2011) applied a gravity model to examine the effect of NTMs on beef trade. The data referred to products of an HS6-digit level code (namely, 020110, 020120, 020130, 020210, 020220, and 020230), taking into account 37 countries (i.e., the 27 member states and Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, Japan, New Zealand, Russia, and the USA); the time dimension is limited to a single period (2009-2010). The dependent variable was determined as the value of exports; independent variables included population-weighted distance, common border, a dummy variable indicating if either of the countries is landlocked, common language, colonial ties, applied import tariffs, FTAs (EU, NAFTA, MERCOSUR, and Australia-New Zealand CER), and HIT (Heterogeneity Indexes of Trade) for individual pesticides and veterinary drugs. The HITs were calculated by comparing standards and regulations for each trading pair; index values of zero show that there is no difference in requirements between the importer and the exporter, while values equal to one show maximum regulation divergence. Results indicated that, on a statistically significant level, common language, tariffs, and FTAs have a positive effect on the value of beef exports, while distance, regulation divergence (expressed through the HITs) for pesticides and veterinary drugs, and the importer being landlocked have a negative effect.

Kotchoni and Larue (2011) applied a gravity model to investigate the impact of trade barriers on international beef trade. The data used referred to 41 countries for 1995-2005, i.e., the period characterized by the BSE (Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy) disease. The dependent variable was determined as beef trade flows, while independent variables included importer's and exporter's per capita GDP, importer's and exporter's production, importer's and exporter's population, distance, common borders, common language, tariffs, trade agreements, and BSE outbreaks in the importing and the exporting country. On a statistically significant level, common border and common language had a positive effect on beef trade flows, while distance and tariffs had a negative effect.

Cao and Johnson (2012) applied a gravity model to examine New Zealand's beef trade, focusing on the effects of quota restrictions and hygiene regulations. The data took under consideration beef and veal meat trade from New Zealand to nine major trading countries (namely, Australia, Canada, China, France, Germany, Japan, Korea, the UK, and the USA) for the 1994-2003 period. The dependent variable of the model was identified as the volume of exported meat. The independent variables included the importer's and exporter's (i.e., New Zealand's) GDP, the importer's and exporter's population, distance (as a proxy of transportation costs), a dummy variable indicating the presence of tariff-rate quota arrangements, exchange rate, unit meat export price at shipping point to destination, the volume of meat production in the importing country, and a dummy variable indicating the adoption of HACCP (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point). The results showed that, on a statistically significant level,

importer's GDP, New Zealand's (i.e., the exporter's) population, and quota arrangements had a positive effect on beef exports, while the exporter's GDP, distance, the volume of meat production in the importing country, and the unit meat export price harmed New Zealand's exports.

Fadeyi *et al.* (2014) examined the effect of the SADC FTA initiated in 2008 on South African agricultural trade, applying –in specific- a gravity model focusing on beef trade. Data focus on SADC 14 member states' and EU-15 countries' beef (code 0111: meat of bovine animals, fresh, chilled or frozen) trade flows, from 2000 to 2011. The dependent variable is defined as the total bilateral trade flows (exports and imports). The independent variables include importer's and exporter's GDP, importer's and exporter's population, the distance between economic centers, common language, common colony, common border, a dummy variable indicating a regional trade agreement between the countries, and a variable representing the level of "openness" of SADC members imports from the rest of the world. The study's results indicated that, on a statistically significant level, the importer's and exporter's GDP, the importer's population, common language and border, and a regional trade agreement between the countries have a positive effect on beef trade flows. On the contrary, exporter's population, distance, and being common colonies affect negatively beef trade flows.

Shang and Glynn (2014) investigated the effects of food safety incidents [BSE outbreaks and food safety recalls by the FSIS (Food Safety Inspection Service) on USA beef trade, by applying a gravity model. Data referred to USA beef trade across eleven importing and ten exporting countries for the 1989-2012 period. Two different equations were applied, to examine USA beef exports and imports separately. Hence, in the first model, the volume of USA beef exports was set as the dependent variable, while in the second model the volume of beef imports to the USA was the dependent variable. Independent variables consisted of importer's GDP, distance, common border, two dummy variables indicating the occurrence of BSE in the USA or the partner country, food safety recalls on USA beef imports and exports by the USDA (United States Department of Agriculture) FSIS, and the introduction of FTAs between the two countries. Referring to the USA beef export model, it is indicated that -on a statistically significant level- the importer's GDP and a common border have a positive effect on trade, while BSE outbreaks in the USA (i.e., the exporter) have a negative effect. When examining the model of USA beef imports, it is noted that distance, common border, and the introduction of an FTA between the USA and the importer have a statistically significant positive effect on USA beef imports.

Karemera *et al.* (2015) employed a gravity model to identify the factors that affect bovine meat trade flows, focusing especially on the effect of bilateral and regional free trade agreements. Data used took into account bovine meat trade flows for 57 countries, from 1986 to 2009. The dependent variable was set as the volume of exports. Independent variables included importer's and exporter's per capita GDP, importer's and exporter's livestock production, importer's and exporter's population, distance, common border, FTAs (NAFTA, EU, ASEAN, MERCOSUR), exchange rate

volatility, a dummy variable indicating cases of HMD (Hoof-and-Mouth Disease), and dummy variables representing major exporting meat countries (to identify quality differentiation by origin). Results indicated that importer's and exporter's per capita GDP and population, exporter's production, and common border had a statistically significant positive effect on exports, while HMD, distance, and exchange rate volatility had a negative effect. The results also indicated that NAFTA and EU assisted bovine meat trade through trade creation among members and trade diversion from non-members to members; MERCOSUR led to trade creation between members, while ASEAN led to trade diversion from non-members to members.

Labraga (2015) employed a gravity model to examine the effect of new and old sanitary standards on the bovine meat trade, having in mind the EU's decision to ban hormone-treated beef and the recognition of FMD (Foot and Mouth Disease) status on MERCOSUR countries' exports. Data referred to SITC 1111 (bovine meat with bone) and 1112 (bovine meat boneless) products for the 1983 to 2013 period, taking into account four exporters (MERCOSUR countries) and 42 importing countries (i.e., the world's leading meat importers, plus top-ten MERCOSUR importers that were not included in the overall global meat importers). The dependent variable of the model referred to export value; independent variables included common border, common language, distance, FTAs, FMD outbreaks and status in the exporting and importing countries, BSE status in the exporting country, and a dummy variable indicating the beef dispute between EU and USA [i.e., years when the EU imposed the ban (1989-2013) and years when the USA-100% ad-valorem tariff was in force for beef from EU (1989-1996 and 1999-2011)]. Results indicated that FTAs had a statistically significant positive effect on MERCOSUR countries' bovine meat exports, while FMD outbreaks and status, and the beef dispute between EU and USA harmed bovine meat exports.

Webb *et al.* (2017) and Webb *et al.* (2018) applied a gravity model to investigate the effect of FMD and BSE outbreaks on the beef trade. Data employed in the model refer to the aggregate of HS4-digit codes 0201 (fresh beef) and 0202 (frozen beef), taking into account 188 exporting countries (the remaining 7 countries -out of the total of 195- were excluded as they did not export any beef during the period under consideration) for the period between 1996 and 2013. The dependent variable is determined as total annual imports of products. Independent variables include a set of FMD and BSE-related dummy variables referring to both the import and the exporter, importer's and exporter's beef production, importer's and exporter's GDP, applicable tariff rate on imports, distance, common borders, colonial relationship, partners having a common legal system, and RTAs between partners. The empirical results show that on a statistically significant level the importer's GDP, the exporter's beef production, common borders, common language, colonial ties, common legal system, and RTAs have a positive effect, while tariffs and distance harm beef trade. Referring to the disease-related variables, in general, it could be noted that the occurrence of FMD or BSE outbreaks in the exporting country, as well as the case of the importer having no FMD outbreaks, have a negative effect on trade.

Ghazalian (2019) employed a gravity model to examine the factors affecting Canada's beef exports. Data cover HS4-digit categories 0201 (meat of bovine animals, fresh or chilled) and 0202 (meat of bovine animals, frozen) for the 2011 to 2015 period, taking into account major beef exporting countries (i.e., Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, EU-15 countries, New Zealand, Paraguay, the USA, and Uruguay) and their trading partners (i.e., 160 countries). The dependent variable is specified as Canada's value of beef exports; independent variables include importer's and exporter's per capita GDP, supply capacity and demand capacity, exporter's cost function (estimated based on productivity, cattle price, labor wage, and capital rent), tariffs, distance, common border, common language, and colonial ties. Results indicate that, on a statistically significant level, importer's and exporter's per capita GDP, supply and demand capacity, common border, colonial ties, and common language affect positively trade flows, while tariffs, distance, and exporter's cost function affect the trade negatively.

Zongo and Larue (2019) utilized a gravity model, to investigate the impact of BSE and FMD outbreaks on beef trade flows, by estimating the effect of a hypothetical removal of animal diseases outbreaks on trade flows. Data referred to HS4-digit disaggregated beef products (0102, 0201, 0202, and 0206, i.e., cattle, fresh and frozen meat, and offals), taking into account 40 countries for the 1996–2015 period. The dependent variable of the model is defined as the bilateral trade flow, while independent variables comprise of exporter's sectoral output, importer's sectoral expenditure, distance, common border, common language, tariffs, FTAs, SPS measures, and a set of BSE and FMD-related variables referring to both the import and the exporter. According to the model's results, and on a statistically significant level, exporter's output, importer's expenditure, and FMD outbreaks in the importing country affect positively trade flows, while applied tariffs, distance, FTAs, SPS measures, BSE and FMD outbreaks in the exporting country, and BSE outbreaks in the importing country negatively affect trade.

Zhang *et al.* (2020), in the context of China's increasing demand for beef (indicatively, China replaced the USA as the world's largest beef importer in 2018), developed a gravity model to examine the effects of animal diseases (FMD and BSE) and restrictive SPS measures on China's beef imports. The data covers the top-ten beef exporters from 1996 to 2018, and refers to eight HS6-digit codes (namely, HS020110, HS020120, HS020130, HS020210, HS020220, HS020230, HS021020, and HS160250). The dependent variable of the model was expressed as China's beef imports value, while independent variables comprised of the importer's and exporter's GDP, FMD, and BSE outbreaks in the exporting country, specific trade concerns raised by exporters due to restrictive SPS measures initiated by importers, distance, FTAs, and tariffs. The results indicated that, on a statistically significant level, the importer's (i.e., China's) and the exporter's GDP had a positive effect on China's beef imports, while BSE and FMD outbreaks in the exporting country, SPS measures imposed by China, FTAs and tariffs had a negative effect.

Banda and Kalaba (2021) used a gravity model to examine the impact of asymmetric (i.e. when a country or region implements different regulatory standards than other trade partners) regulatory measures on South African beef exports to the EU. The model was based on data concerning supply shares of South African beef exports to its partners from 1992 to 2019. Trade partners were grouped into six categories (EU, SADC, the Middle East, China, the rest of the African countries, and the rest of the World) and beef exports were correspondingly aggregated; a different analysis was performed for each country/region group. The total value of South African beef exports was set as the dependent variable, while independent variables comprised of South Africa's (i.e., the exporter's) per capita GDP, the importer's capita GDP, EU's number of regulatory measures on beef (being the key variable of this study), tariff rates imposed by the importer, and real exchange rate for the importer. Referring to South Africa's exports to the EU, the study's results indicate that, on a statistically significant level, EU per capita GDP had a positive effect on beef exports, while EU real exchange rate, EU regulatory measures, and South Africa's per capita GDP harmed beef trade. When referring to the independent variables of the analyses of South Africa's exports to the other five country/region groups, it should be noted that a variety of statistical significance and signs are present among the different models. Indicative, it could be mentioned that –in general- EU's regulatory measures have a statistically significant positive effect on South Africa's beef exports to countries outside the EU.

Darbandi *et al.* (2021), based on a gravity model, evaluated the impact of consumer awareness about beef safety on USA beef exports. Data referred to the USA as the exporter, and Canada, Japan, South Korea, and Mexico as the top importing countries, taking into account the period from 2001 to 2016. The dependent variable of the model was expressed as the level of USA beef exports, while independent variables comprised of the importer's GDP, distance (as a proxy of transaction costs), exchange rate, importer's and exporter's (i.e., the USA) production level of beef, a dummy viable indicating trade agreements between the USA and the importer, and consumer awareness about safety events (reflected through an index which was developed based on media reports). The results indicated that, on a statistically significant level, USA beef production and trade agreements had a positive effect, while the beef safety index, i.e. foodborne-disease news, harmed USA beef exports.

Tian *et al.* (2021) used a gravity model to explore the factors contributing to China's increasing bovine meat imports. Data used in the model referred to disaggregated data for bovine meat (fresh, chilled, or frozen beef; based on HS coding) imports from 1998 to 2016, taking into account nine countries (China, and eight partner countries from which China imported beef mostly, in specific accounting for over 98% of China's beef imports both in 1998 and in 2016). The dependent variable of the model is defined as China's bovine meat import volume. Independent variables include Chinas (i.e., the importer's) real GDP, exporter's annual total bovine meat exports volume (i.e. supply capacity), beef import price divided by China's domestic beef annual producer price (i.e. ratio between exporter's and China's beef prices),

distance, FTAs between China and the exporter, a dummy indicating BSE outbreaks in the exporting country, and a dummy variable differentiating between the pre-2008 and the post-2008 periods (accounting for significant differences in China's import patterns between the two periods). According to the study's results, the importer's GDP, exporter's supply capacity, and FTAs had a statistically significant positive effect on China's beef imports, while beef importing to domestic price ratio, distance, and BSE outbreaks in the exporting country had a statistically significant negative effect.

4.3. Gravity analysis of the beef international market

Bellow, we present the gravity model used in the case of beef, the data set used in the estimation of the model, and the empirical results obtained from the estimation of the beef gravity model.

4.3.1. The gravity model of the beef international market

The gravity model of beef is based on that of the wine, Eq. (2.3.5), and it is given by Eq. (4.3.1) below:

$$\ln X_{ijt} = c^* + \alpha \ln M_{it} + \beta \ln M_{jt} + \delta_1 \ln D_{ij} + \delta_2 \ln(1 + tr_{jt}) + \delta_{31} \ln(1 + sps_{jt}) + \delta_{32} \ln(1 + tbt_{jt}) + \delta_{33} \ln(1 + ontm_{jt}) + \delta_4 \ln(1 + tag_{ijt}) + \gamma Comlang_{ij} + \zeta_1 eu_i + \zeta_2 eu_j + \zeta_2 euwtr_{ij} + \zeta_3 euaf_{ij} + \eta_1 ukrest_{ij} + \eta_2 mrc_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (4.3.1)$$

where X_{ijt} are the country's exports i to destination j at time t ; M_{it} represents the exporter's supply (i.e., beef production of country i) at time t ; M_{jt} is the GDP of country j at time t ; D_{ij} is the geographical distance between the capitals of countries i, j ; tr_j represents the *ad valorem* equivalent tariff imposed by country j to country's i exports; the variables sps_{jt} , tbt_{jt} and $ontm_{jt}$ belong to the class of NTMs and represent Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards, Technical Barriers to Trade and NTMs, respectively, imposed by the importing country; tag_{ij} a dummy variable indicating if the trading partners are engaged bilaterally in a regional trade agreement; $Comlang_{ij}$ a dummy variable taking the value of 1 if countries share a common official or primary language; eu_i (eu_j) is a dummy variable assuming the value of 1 if the exporting (importing) country is a member of the EU; $euwtr_{ij}$ a dummy variable obtaining the value of 1 if the trading partners are EU countries; $euaf_{ij}$ taking the value of 1 if trading partners are an EU and an African country; $ukrest_{ij}$ assuming the value of 1 if trading partners are the UK and a non-EU country member; mrc_{ij} a dummy variable obtaining the value of 1 if a MERCOSUR country (i.e., Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Uruguay, and Venezuela) is trading with the rest of the world; ε_{ij} is the error term and it is assumed to be identically and independently distributed.

4.3.2. Data used in the beef gravity model

This section provides the description, data sources, and descriptive statistics of the variables used in the gravity model.

Table 4.3.1. Variable definition, descriptive statistics, and data sources

Variables	Variable Definition	Descriptive Statistics	Data Sources
X_{ij} (Trade flows from country i to j)	Trade flow as reported by the importer in thousands current US\$)	Mean: 14901.7 Min: 0.001 Max: 2682461 St. dev.: 88225.88	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
M_{it} (Production-exporter)	Number of cows	Mean: 4.15e+09 Min: 0 Max: 8.79e+11 St. dev.: 3.92e+10	Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QI
M_{jt} (GDP-importer)	GDP (current thousands US\$)	Mean: 7.09e+08 Min: 0 Max: 2.14e+10 St. dev.: 2.15e+09	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
D_{ij} (Distance)	Distance between the most populated city of each country (km)	Mean: 5569.80 Min: 0 Max: 19629.5 St. dev.: 4794.82	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
tr_{jt} (MFN applied rates-importer)	Ad valorem (on value) tariff rate	Mean: 195.78 Min: 0 Max: 1587.57 St. dev.: 242.13	World Integrated Trade Solutions https://wits.worldbank.org/Default.aspx?lang=en
sps_{jt} (Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 1.2 Min: 0 Max: 67 St. dev.: 4.95	WTO, Integrated Trade Intelligence Portal (I-TIP) https://i-tip.wto.org/goods/Forms/TableView.aspx
tbt_{jt} (Technical Barriers to Trade)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 0.379 Min: 0 Max: 45 St. dev.: 3.278	WTO, Integrated Trade Intelligence Portal (I-TIP) https://i-tip.wto.org/goods/Forms/TableView.aspx
$ontm_{jt}$ (Other non-tariff measures)	Number of measures in force	Mean: 1.228 Min: 0 Max: 31 St. dev.: 4.141	WTO, Integrated Trade Intelligence Portal (I-TIP) https://i-tip.wto.org/goods/Forms/TableView.aspx
tag_{ijt} (Regional trade agreements)	1 if the pair currently has a RTA	Mean: 0.462 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.499	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
$Comlang_{ij}$	1 if countries share a common	Mean: 0.198	The CEPII Gravity Database

	official or primary language	Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.399	http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
eu_i (EU member-exporter)	1 if the exporting country currently is an EU member	Mean: 0.409 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.492	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
eu_j (EU member-importer)	1 if the importing country currently is an EU member	Mean: 0.302 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.459	The CEPII Gravity Database http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/presentation.asp?id=8
$euwtr_{ij}$	1 if trade partners are EU members	Mean: 0.191 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.393	
$euaf_{ij}$ (Trading partnership EU – African countries)	1 if the trading partners are EU and African countries	Mean: 0.243 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.429	
$ukrest_{ij}$ (Trading partnership UK-non-EU country)	1 if the trading partners are the UK and a non-EU member	Mean: 0.028 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.165	
mrc_{ij}	1 if the exporter is a MERCOSUR member	Mean: 0.116 Min: 0 Max: 1 St. dev.: 0.320	

4.3.3. Empirical results of the beef gravity model

First, we apply ordinary least squares (OLS) in Eq. (4.3.1) to obtain estimates of the unknown parameters. The OLS are the best linear unbiased estimators if the errors (ε_{ij}) of Eq. (4.3.1) are independently and identically distributed with a constant variance of σ_ε^2 . However, these conditions are violated as indicated by the White test and Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity and the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation (Table 4.3.2). Thus, as in the case of wine, we use the Driscoll and Kraay (1998) correction to fix heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. Failure to correct for autocorrelation can result in understated standard errors (Moulton, 1990).

Table 4.3.2. White Test and Breusch-Pagan test for Heteroscedasticity & Wooldridge test for autocorrelation

White Test	Breusch-Pagan tests/Cook-Weisberg test	Wooldridge test

F(2, 27227)= 502.74	Prob>F=0.0000	chi2(1)= 2300.62	Prob>chi2=0.0000	F(1, 2155) = 275.134	Prob > F = 0.0000
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Notes: H_0 for White's test is that the variances for the errors are equal

H_0 for Breusch-Pagan tests/Cook-Weisberg test assumes constant variance

H_0 for the Wooldridge test assumes no first-order autocorrelation

The second column of Table 4.3.3 presents results for pooled OLS (OLS_POOLED) estimation of Eq. (4.3.1), while the third column shows OLS estimates of Eq. (4.3.1) with yearly fixed effects included (OLS_FE).

Table 4.3.3. Estimation results of Eq. (5)

Variables	(1) OLS_POOLED	(2) OLS_FE	(3) PPML	(4) PPML_ME
<i>Intercept</i>	-2.4510*** (0.695)	-2.5435*** (0.695)	0.2122* (0.128)	
M_{it} (Production of exporter)	0.1039*** (0.018)	0.1035*** (0.018)	0.0190*** (0.003)	0.1039*** (0.017)
M_{jt} (Per capital GDP-importer)	0.4164*** (0.024)	0.4154*** (0.024)	0.0783*** (0.004)	0.4286*** (0.025)
D_{ij} (Distance)	-0.2033*** (0.059)	-0.2042*** (0.060)	-0.0391*** (0.010)	-0.2140*** (0.058)
tr_{jt} (MFN applied rates-importer)	0.0051 (0.017)	0.0077 (0.017)	0.0007 (0.003)	0.0042 (0.019)
sps_{jt} (Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards)	0.1000 (0.067)	0.0975 (0.067)	0.0149 (0.011)	0.0817 (0.063)
tb_{jt} (Technical Barriers to Trade)	-0.2280 (0.165)	-0.2271 (0.1661)	-0.0455* (0.025)	-0.2493* (0.141)
$ontm_{jt}$ (Other non-tariff measures)	-0.1362* (0.071)	-0.1373* (0.071)	-0.0202* (0.012)	-0.1109* (0.065)
tag_{ijt} (Regional trade agreements)	0.3522** (0.161)	0.3422** (0.162)	0.0643** (0.030)	0.3517** (0.166)
$Comlang_{ij}$ (Countries share common official or primary language)	0.6769*** (0.124)	0.6771*** (0.124)	0.1149*** (0.022)	0.6287*** (0.124)
eu_i (EU member-exporter)	-0.5885*** (0.113)	-0.5932*** (0.113)	-0.1311*** (0.023)	-0.7174*** (0.130)
eu_j (EU member-importer)	-1.2915*** (0.173)	-1.2956*** (0.173)	-0.2369*** (0.032)	-1.296*** (0.180)
$euwtr_{ij}$	2.4778*** (0.215)	2.47795*** (0.215)	0.4548*** (0.039)	2.4877*** 0.219
$euaf_{ij}$	-0.6818***	-0.6819***	-0.1403***	-0.7674***

<i>(Trading partnership UK – AF)</i>	(0.101)	(0.101)	(0.021)	(0.117)
<i>ukrest_{ij}</i> <i>(Trading partnership UK- nonEU country)</i>	-0.5019** (0.222)	-0.5053** (0.222)	-0.0989* (0.051)	-0.5414* (0.281)
<i>merc_{ij}</i>	1.6870*** (0.133)	1.6882*** (0.133)	0.2862*** (0.022)	1.5653*** (0.120)
<i>2010.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.0698 (0.047)		
<i>2011.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.2184*** (0.053)		
<i>2012.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.1706*** (0.055)		
<i>2013.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.1214** (0.056)		
<i>2014.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.1731*** (0.058)		
<i>2015.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		-0.0638 (0.060)		
<i>2016.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.1413** (0.061)		
<i>2017.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.1486** (0.061)		
<i>2018.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.1695*** (0.062)		
<i>2019.year</i> <i>(Dummy variable)</i>		0.2154*** (0.068)		
Statistics	N= 27,230 F(15, 4424) = 64.64 Prob > F = 0.0000 R-squared= 0.5877 Root MSE=2.8533 LL =-67179.63 AIC= 134391.3 BIC= 134522.6	N= 27,230 F(25, 4424)=42.6 Prob > F = 0.0000 R-squared= 0.5884 Root MSE=2.8526 LL =-67167.69 AIC=134387.4 BIC=134600.9	N= 27,230 R- squared=0.592 LL =-68810.659 AIC=137653.3 BIC=137784.7	

Notes: *, **, *** denote 10, 5, and 1 percent significance level, respectively; N denotes the number of observations; LL is the log-likelihood; AIC and BIC are the Akaike's and Schwarz's Bayesian information criteria, respectively.

A log-likelihood ratio test supports the inclusion of the annual dummy variables in Eq. (3.3.1) and thus, the OLS_FE model is preferred over the OLS_POOLED. In particular, the value of the log-likelihood test is equal to 23.88, suggesting the rejection of the null hypothesis that the time effects are not statistically significant at the 1% significance level. Column four of Table 4.3.3 presents the estimates of Eq. (4.3.1) using the Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML) estimation approach, while column five provides the marginal effects based on the PPML estimates. We estimated the PPML model for checking the robustness of our results. Note that the advantage of the PPML model is that it corrects for sample selection bias that might result from excluding zero observations. Since we have considered only trade flows with a positive value of the global beef traded, selection bias is not present. As a result, we expect that the magnitude, statistical significance, and economic interpretation of marginal effects obtained from the PPML model would be very similar to those of the OLS_POOLED and OLS_FE approaches. A thorough inspection of Table 4.3.3 shows that the empirical results obtained from the three estimation approaches (i.e., OLS_POOLED, OLS_FE and PPML) are similar. In the rest of the section, unless specified otherwise, we refer to the estimates from the OLS_FE model.

First, the R-squared is 0.588, which shows that the explanatory variables account for about 59% of the observed variation in the wine trade in the data, indicating that the model fits the data relatively well. Furthermore, the F-test is statistically significant at the 1% level, which provides second support of the satisfying performance of the model. The beef production of the exporter (M_{it}) and the GDP of the importer (M_{jt}) are both positively associated with trade and statistically significant at any conventional level of significance. The results show that we would expect that a 1% increase in exporter beef production tends to increase beef trade by about 0.11%, while a 1% increase in importer GDP would increase beef trade by about 0.42%. The coefficient on distance (D_{ij}) is negative at the 1% significance level, indicating that a 1% increase in distance tends to reduce trade by about 0.21%. A comparison with previous literature supports our findings regarding the effects of exporter's beef production, GDP per capita of the importer, and the distance between the trading partners on beef trade flows (e.g., Wilson *et al.*, 2003; Gervail *et al.*, 2011; Kotchoni and Larue, 2011; Fadeyi *et al.*, 2014; Webb *et al.*, 2017; Ghazalian, 2019; Zongo and Larue, 2019).

The effect of the *ad valorem* equivalent tariffs (tr_{jt}) is statistically insignificant at any conventional level of significance indicating that tariffs do not have any significant effect on beef trade flows. The insignificant effect of tariffs on trade flows might be because tariffs remained relatively stable during the study period. In other words, tariffs in the main destination countries did not vary significantly to provoke any substantial effect on trade. Most of the previous literature find a negative effect of tariffs on beef trade flows (e.g., Kotchoni and Larue, 2011; Webb *et al.*, 2017; Ghazalian, 2019; Zongo and Larue, 2019), however, the study by Gervais *et al.* (2011) finds a positive impact.

Considering the results of the three estimated models (i.e., OLS_POOLED, OLS_FE, and PPML_ME), concerning the NTMs, only the other NTMs ($ontm_{jt}$) are statistically significant at the 10% level among the three models, indicating that a 1% increase in $ontm_j$ in the importing country will reduce trade flows by about 0.14%. Note that the Technical Barriers to Trade (tbt_{jt}) are statistically significant at the 10% level only in the PPML_ME model, indicating that a 1% increase in tbt_j in the importing country will reduce trade flows by about 0.25%. Finally, the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards (sps_{jt}) are not statistically significant at any conventional level of significance among the three estimated models. The present study indicates that most of the NTMs are trade restraining compared to the *ad valorem* equivalent tariffs (tr_{jt}), and Technical Barriers to Trade (tbt_{jt}) hurt more the beef trade than other NTMs ($ontm_{jt}$) as the results of the PPML_ME model indicate. Our findings concerning Technical Barriers to Trade (tbt_{jt}) are in line with previous literature (e.g., Wilson *et al.*, 2003; Gervail *et al.*, 2011; Darbandi *et al.*, 2021). As opposed to our findings regarding Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards (sps_{jt}) previous literature finds a negative impact on beef trade (Wilson *et al.*, 2003; Labraga, 2015; Webb *et al.*, 2017; Zongo and Larue, 2019).

Regional trade agreements (tag_{ijt}) have a positive and statistically significant effect on trade, showing a 0.34% increase on trade for a 1% increase of tag_{ij} . This finding agrees with previous literature (e.g., Gervail *et al.*, 2011; Kotchoni and Larue, 2011; Fadeyi *et al.*, 2014; Shang and Glynn, 2014; Labraga, 2015; Webb *et al.*, 2017; Darbandi *et al.*, 2021; Tian *et al.*, 2021). However, the studies by Wilson *et al.* (2003), Zongo and Larue, (2019), and Zhang *et al.* (2020) find a negative effect, while the study by Karemera *et al.* (2015) supports that free trade agreements lead to trade creation between members and trade diversion from non-members to members. Common language ($Comlang_{ij}$) has a positive and statistically significant effect on trade, showing a 0.68% increase in trade if trading partners share the same language. This finding is supported by the studies of Gervail *et al.* (2011), Kotchoni and Larue (2011), Fadeyi *et al.* (2014), Webb *et al.* (2017), and Ghazalian (2019), among others.

The statistical significance of the dummy variable, eu_i , indicates that trade flows are lower by 0.60% when the export country is an EU country compared to the average level of global beef export flow. In the case where the importing country is an EU country (i.e., consider the dummy variable, eu_j) the trade flows are lower by 1.30% compared to the case where the importing country is not an EU country. These results support the conclusion that the EU is close to the average beef global export flow level. However, it is much below the average beef global import flow level, indicating that it is not a significant importing region in the international beef trade. The statistical significance of the dummy variable, $euwtr_{ij}$, indicates that trade flows are 2.48% higher within the EU compared to the average level of global beef trade taking place outside the EU. Since European beef imports and exports are lower than the average global level and the trade flows within the EU are much higher than the

international average level, we may conclude that the EU supports trade creation between EU members and trade diversion from non-members to members.

The trading partnership *EU – AFRICA* as indicated by the *euaf_{ij}* dummy is negative and statistically significant at any conventional level of significance, indicating that the trade between the EU and the African countries is 0.68% lower than the trade between the EU and non-African countries. Furthermore, the trade between the UK and the rest of the world, excluding the EU, is much less than the average global beef trade, as it is supported by the negative and statistically significant value (i.e., -0.51) corresponding to the coefficient of the dummy variable *ukrest_{ij}*. This finding could indicate that the BREXIT might not have an adverse effect on the EU's global beef trade position, since the UK's trade flows with the rest of the world are much below the average global beef trade. However, the BREXIT might weaken the within the EU beef trade.

The statistical significance of the dummy variable, *merc_{ij}*, indicates that trade flows are 1.69% higher between the MERCOSUR countries and the rest of the world than the average level of global beef trade involving non-MERCOSUR countries. This finding shows the strong effect of the MERCOSUR countries on the global beef trade. Finally, the coefficients of the yearly dummy variables show that the international beef trade flows for the periods 2011-2014 and 2016-2019 are statistically significantly higher than that of 2009. These results indicate that in recent years the global beef trade has been improved.

4.4. Conclusions of the beef international market

The beef sector network analysis indicates strong trade flows between countries. More precisely, a large number of countries appear to have substantial participation, according to all measures of the network analysis. Across all benchmark years, we observe that Brazil and Chile are leading players. The USA represents another substantial pole, in terms of strong trade value connections, keeping substantial flows with other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. In the same vein is the presence of the EU, which includes different nations like Germany, Italy, and France processing a core position in the network. On the other hand, Africa and several other countries maintain a modest position in terms of trade flows. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top beef exporters in 2019 are Australia, Brazil, the USA, Argentina, India, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Ireland, Canada, Uruguay, Poland, Mexico, and France. In the same year, the top importers are China, the USA, Japan, South Korea, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Hong Kong, France, Vietnam, the UK, Chile, and Russia.

Based on the literature review performed on gravity models, the main determinants of beef trade flows consist of importer's and exporter's (per capita) GDP and population, exporter's and importer's beef production, beef exporting price, exchange rate, the distance between the trading countries, geographical position (in terms of

common borders and the existence of a landlocked partner), historical and cultural factors (common language, common legal system, colonial links), specific market conditions [e.g. EU's hormone ban, product-specific regulations (i.e., on pesticides and veterinary drugs), BSE and FMD outbreaks], and trade-related aspects in the form of common participation in FTAs and RTAs, and imposed regulations, standards, tariffs and/or NTMs by the importing country.

The empirical results of the gravity beef model estimated in the present discussion paper for the 2009-2019 period provide the following conclusions. First, the economic activity captured by the exporter's beef production and the importer's GDP has a positive effect on beef trade flows. In contrast, the distance between trading partners has a negative impact. Second, tariffs do not have any significant effect on beef trade flows. Third, among the NTMs, Technical Barriers to Trade restrain beef trade more than other NTMs, while the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards are not affecting beef trade. Fourth, regional trade agreements, as well as a common language, have a relatively significant positive effect on trade. Fifth, EU beef exports to the rest of the world are close to the average global export level, while EU beef imports are well below the average international beef import flows. However, beef trade flows within the EU are well above that of the average global beef trade, indicating that the EU supports trade creation between EU members and trade diversion from non-members to members. Sixth, the trade between the UK and the rest of the world (excluding the EU) is less than the average international beef trade, indicating that the BREXIT might not affect the EU's global beef trade position. Seventh, the trading partnership between EU and African countries is less than the average international beef trade. Finally, MERCOSUR countries have a significant positive effect on the global beef trade.

5 PORK

5.1. Network analysis and results of the pork international market

In this section, the world's major pork exporters and importers are presented, using data on trade flows from 2010 to 2019. Our data stems from the BACI dataset from CEPII, the leading French center for research and expertise on the world economy. Our sample consists of countries with a value of pork trade flows greater than 90 million dollars which represents about 5% of total trade. This threshold is used to exclude small trade flows to eliminate unnecessary noise originating from such trades. The detailed list of pork codes used in this study is found in Appendix A4.

Figure 5.1.1 illustrates the top pork exporters in the 2010 benchmark year. According to this figure, the largest economy of Europe, Germany, the USA, and Denmark are the worldwide leading countries in pork exports in 2010, based on export value, with a significant difference from the rest of the exporters globally. Spain, Canada, the Netherlands, and Belgium have also a prominent position in the trade. On the other hand, the remaining countries, Brazil, France, Poland, Austria, Hungary, Chile, and China, have a relatively lower trade export value.

Figure 5.1.1

Continuing to Figure 5.1.2, we display the top pork exporters in the 2013 reference year. We observe a similar interpretation as in Figure 5.1.1. The top pork exporters are once more Germany, the USA, and Denmark, followed by Canada, the Netherlands, and Belgium. France, Poland, and Brazil seem to have a secondary and stable role. Finally, Ireland and China hold a marginal position. The figure illustrates, as in Figure 5.1.1, a multi-participation of countries and continents in the ranking of pork exports.

Figure 5.1.2

Figure 5.1.3 displays pork exports for the reference year 2016. According to this figure, we have a similar pattern with the reference year 2013. Brazil and the USA are the top pork exporters. In addition, Spain holds third place instead of Denmark which this year has dropped one position. Another difference is the rise of Brazil. This graph allows us to stronger recognize the core role of the European countries, the USA, and the Asian countries in the pork trade.

Figure 5.1.3

Figure 5.1.4 illustrates the most recent data we have, concerning pork exports, for the benchmark year 2019. In this graph, we can see the dominance of the USA, followed by Spain and Germany with an important differential of the rest countries. Austria and Hungary hold a marginal position.

Figure 5.1.4

In the following Figures 5.1.5 through 5.1.8 we illustrate the major pork importers with the assumptions introduced at the beginning of our analysis. A quite different scenario is depicted in comparison to the pork export flows. Furthermore, the countries' rankings in the global pork trade have been inverted in comparison with the export trends.

Figure 5.1.5 displays the top pork importers for the year 2010. The economy of Japan appears to maintain a dominant position in the import ranking, having the largest percentage of approximately 15%. The EU, with Italy and Germany, holds a prominent role, while, on the other hand, the Russian Federation and Poland compose a mainstream second pole. The UK is next in the rankings followed by France and the USA. Furthermore, a number of countries from Europe, as well as Canada, are at the bottom of the rankings based on their import value.

Figure 5.1.5

Figure 5.1.6 illustrates the major importing countries for the benchmark years of 2013. The most notable aspect is that we have a similar scenario in terms of importing countries' volume, with the previous reference year, with the exception of

China starting to emerge as a central player, holding a percentage of approximately 3.5%.

Figure 5.1.6

In Figure 5.1.7, we present the leading importing countries for the benchmark year of 2016. China now ranks second in terms of imports, with a substantial share of 15% and establishing a dominant pole. Another important feature is Russia's low ranking, which has dropped from 7% (2013) to around 2% in terms of import value.

Figure 5.1.7

In Figure 5.1.8, we present the top importing countries for the benchmark year of 2019. Asia's powerful economies of China and Japan now rank in the two top positions in terms of imports, with a proportion of the market that is more than double that of the following countries, i.e., Italy and Germany. Another notable finding is that Russia has vanished from the map of import value.

Figure 5.1.8

Although global trade patterns have considerably changed over time, it is worth noting that Germany, Spain, and the USA have long been major destinations for pork exports, while Japan leads the importing countries, concerning pork trade.

In what follows we shall use metrics of centrality to estimate the heterogeneity of countries in the global trade network. As we have described previously, in social network research, centrality is one of the most widely used topics. A significant number of measures have been developed, including degree centrality, closeness, betweenness, eigenvector centrality, information centrality, flow betweenness, the rush index, and the influence measures.

As we described in a former section, each node represents a country in the network, which is denoted with its corresponding 3-code acronym. Different lines connect different countries. These lines represent the volume of the trade flows between the countries depicted. Therefore, in what follows we display our analysis for the visualization of the data. In Appendix B4 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016.

In Figure 5.1.9 we illustrate the pork network analysis for the year 2019 based on eigenvector centrality (in Appendix B4 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). For every country in the network, we recorded all the trading partners (in correspondence to the study's assumptions) in terms of trade flows in the above years. The network appears to have a clear structure, with Europe having a leading role. More precisely Germany, Denmark, Poland, Italy, and Spain distinguish in the trade node of pork, having strong flows with a large number of nations in Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. Another important player is Asia's rising economy. The top central players, China and Japan, appear to have substantial trade flows with several other EU countries as well as with countries from other continents. Another trading group with lower trade value is Brazil. Finally, the visualizations display Greece's and Sweden's low rankings in terms of pork trade flows.

Figure 5.1.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure 5.1.10 depicts the pork network analysis for the year 2019 based on authority centrality (in Appendix B4 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe that the European countries have increased their power as core players with extensive economic linkages to a variety of other countries and continents. On the other hand, the USA continues to be a prominent player with extensive trade ties with Europe, Mexico, and China. Another noteworthy feature is Asia's emerging economy (represented mainly by Japan and China) as a top trading country, with significant trade flows with several countries. The appearance of the Russian Federation reveals a small trade flow in pork, whereas Korea's representation especially in 2019 reveals the same low trend.

Figure 5.1.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Authority

In terms of centrality hub, in Figure 5.1.11 we present the pork network trade in the reference year 2019 (in Appendix B4 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). A large number of countries appear to have high participation, according to the measure of centrality hub. Across all benchmark years, we observe that Germany, China, Canada, and the USA are the leading players, in terms of substantial trade value connections, keeping strong flows between them and other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. On the other hand, several European countries, such as Czechia, Hungary, Bulgaria, and the Russian Federation, maintain a modest position in terms of trade flows.

Figure 5.1.11
Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD
Centrality Hub

Figure 5.1.12 depicts the pork network analysis for the year 2019 based on centrality betweenness (in Appendix B4 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe that the EU with a variety of nations, like Germany, Spain, Poland, and the Netherlands represents a major pole of pork trade. In the same vein are China and the USA, having substantial trade flows with a large number of countries in Europe and across the globe. It is noteworthy that, in terms of centrality betweenness, several countries appear to have moderate trade linkages, for example, Hungary only connects with Germany and Romania, whereas the Russian Federation has limited trade flows only with Brazil.

Figure 5.1.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

In terms of centrality closeness, looking at Figure 5.1.13 (in Appendix B4 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016), the result is a framework that emphasizes the importance of the EU with the participation of nations such as Germany, Spain, Belgium, and the Netherlands. Furthermore, the economy of the USA has a substantial contribution to trade interaction as a central trade player, for all benchmark years. Over the years, there are strong network flows between the top countries and other continents. Asia’s boosting economy, represented by China and Japan, appears to be forming a mainstream second pole, connecting with the massive markets of Europe and Chile. Finally, certain nations, such as Czechia, Bulgaria, and the Russian Federation, are on the margin of the trade flow.

Figure 5.1.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

5.2. Gravity literature review of the pork international market

Prentice *et al.* (1998) carried out a gravity model, to investigate the potential for increased pork exports from Canada to the USA. Employed data referred to Canadian pork exports from the five leading exporting provinces (Ontario, Quebec, Alberta, Saskatchewan, and Manitoba) to the USA, for the 1992–1996 period. Different analyses were performed for each one of the abovementioned Canadian provinces. The dependent variable of the model is expressed as the quantity of pork exports (in terms of truckloads); independent variables consisted of truck freight rate (i.e., transportation cost), importer’s disposable income, a production specialization index (i.e., the ratio of hog inventory to the human population of the importer), and a dummy variable taking into account the level of annual pork imports. According to the model’s empirical results and on a statistically significant level, importer’s disposal income has a positive effect on pork exports, while transportation costs and the production specialization index had a negative effect (i.e., an increase of the importer’s production leads to a decline of exports).

Boisson (2011) examined the effect of medium to long-term exchange rate volatility on USA pork exports to China, by applying a gravity model. Quarterly data for the

1995 to 2009 period (covering both floating and fixed-rate regimes) were utilized. The two largest pork export categories [based on the FAS (Foreign Agricultural Service) product category system] were taken into account in aggregation (i.e., they were added to construct the dependent variable), namely a) variety pork cuts, and b) fresh, chilled, and frozen cuts. The dependent variable is determined as total value exports from the USA to China. Independent variables include exchange rate volatility between the USA dollar and the Chinese yuan, USA (i.e., the exporter's) agricultural GDP, China's (i.e., the importer's) GDP and population, a dummy variable indicating China's membership to the WTO, and a dummy variable indicating the trade ban placed by China to USA pork, due to reported cases of H1N1 virus found in USA swine. According to the analysis results, on a statistically significant level, exporters' agricultural GDP, importer's GDP, and China's participation in the WTO had a positive effect on USA export flows to China, while exchange rate volatility and the H1N1-related ban had a negative effect.

Yang (2012) and Yang *et al.* (2012), being interested in the effect that consumer perceptions on disease-infected animals can have on trade, applied a gravity model to examine, in specific how FMD affects international pork trade. Data was employed for 186 countries, from 1996 to 2000, concerning the HS4-digit code 0203 (i.e., the meat of swine, fresh, chilled, and frozen). The determinant variable of the model refers to pork export value; independent variables comprise of importer's and exporter's GDP, distance, common language, post-colonial connections since 1945, and importing country's religion (i.e., Muslim), RTAs between the importing and exporting country, and a dummy variable indicating FMD for the exporting or the importing country. Additional analyses were performed, including, apart from the variable mentioned above, dummy variables indicating when the exporting or the importing country with FMD adopts a vaccination policy or a slaughter policy. The analyses results indicate that, on a statistically significant level, importer's and exporter's GDP, common language, common colonial ties, RTAs, and presence of FMD in the importing country have a positive effect on pork trade. On the contrary, distance, the religion of the importing country (i.e., Muslim), and the presence of FMD in the exporting country harm pork trade. Referring to the adoption of vaccination or slaughter policy, it should be noted that exporters with a vaccination policy have larger negative impacts compared to those with a slaughter policy. Importers with a vaccination policy import the same level of pork, while importers with a slaughter policy will import more pork.

Shahriar *et al.* (2019) applied a gravity model to identify the main determinants of China's pork export trade flows. Data referred to China's pork (HS 0203 - the meat of swine, fresh, chilled, and frozen) exports to its 31 regular trading partners (in terms of average pork exports), for 20 years (1997-2016). The applied model's determinant variable is China's pork exports to the partner countries. Independent variables taken into account include the product of China's and the trading partner's GDP, the product of China's and the trading partner's per capita GDP, the absolute difference between China's and trading partner's per capita GDP, the distance

between capitals, exchange rate value, importer's total area (in km²), a dummy variable indicating China's participation in the WTO, a dummy variable indicating the beginning of the "Belt and Road" initiative, common language, common border, and a dummy variable indicating if the importer is a landlocked country. The study's results show that on a statistically significant level, GDP (expressed as the product of the two partner's GDP), participation of China in the WTO, the initiation of the "Belt and Road" initiative, common language and border, and the importing country being landlocked have a positive effect on China's pork exports, while per capita GDP (expressed as the product of the two partner's per capita GDP), exchange rate value and importer's total area harm pork exports.

Shang and Tonsor (2019), by applying a gravity model, focused on the effect of specific SPS measures concerning animal and human health, as well as maximum residue limits, on the pork meat trade (as part of the red meat trade). The data used in the model referred to the HS4-digit code 0203 (meat of swine, fresh, chilled or frozen) for the 1997 to 2013 period; 15 countries/ regions accounting for >80% of red meat trade worldwide [not referring to "pork" in specific, as the study examines "red meat" trade in general (non- aggregatedly, both beef and pork)] were taken into account in the study. The dependent variable of the model is defined as pork trade value; independent variables include importer's per capita GDP, importer's and exporter's total production, a dummy variable indicating FTAs between the countries, and SPS measures imposed by the importer [with different analyses considering either aggregated, policy goal-oriented, related to BSE or related to FMD SPS measures]; a country-pair dummy includes all time-invariant determinants, such as common language and distance. The analyses results indicate that, on a statistically significant level, importer's per capita GDP and exporter's production have a positive effect on trade, while importer's production and aggregated SPS measures have a negative effect. In addition, it is worth noting that SPS measures related to BSE (i.e., measures restrictive for beef) have a positive effect on the pork trade, indicating a cross-species spillover effect.

Peci and Sanjuán (2020) carried out a gravity model referring to the pork trade, having in mind the trade effects created due to the implementation of NTMs by China. Data referred to 4 years (2012-2015), including 40 importers (accounting for 86% of global pork imports) and 152 exporters; 18 pork-related products were taken into account, based on the HS6-digit level categorization. The dependent variable was determined as the value of pork imports, while the independent variables consist of the product of the importer's and exporter's GDP, distance, common borders, colonial linkage, RTAs, tariffs, and NTMs. For the NTMs, the maximum available level of disaggregation (i.e. the four-digit level) was considered for the SPS and TBT measures, while the remaining NTMs were classified under the variable "Other". The empirical results indicated that on a statistically significant level, GDP, common border, and RTAs affect positively pork trade, while distance and several NTM subcategories (SPS and TBTs taken separately into account in the model; all other NTMs being aggregated) have a negative impact.

5.3. Conclusions of the pork international market

This network analysis provides evidence that the pork global trade is changing. More precisely, across all benchmark years, we observe that the strong European economies like Germany, France, the Netherlands, Italy, and Spain are the leading players, in terms of substantial trade value connections, keeping strong trade flows between them and other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. Similarly, the USA, Australia, and China's boosting economy create another significant group, which is characterized by its high trades in the pork industry. On the other hand, the UK holds a moderate position in the network with both strong and weak trade flows with various partners, indicating that the BREXIT may cause a small effect on pork international trade. Africa's presence on the network is scarce. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top pork exporters in 2019 are the USA, Spain, Germany, Denmark, the Netherlands, Canada, Belgium, Brazil, France, Poland, and Mexico. In the same year, the top importers are China, Japan, Italy, Germany, Poland, South Korea, Mexico, the UK, the USA, France, Czechia, Hong Kong, and Romania.

Based on the literature review performed on gravity models, the main determinants of pork trade flows consist of importer's and exporter's (per capita) GDP, exporter's and importer's beef production, exchange rate, the distance between the trading countries, geographical position (in terms of common borders and the existence of a landlocked partner), historical and cultural factors (importer's religion, common language, colonial links), specific market conditions [e.g. H1N1-related ban, FMD outbreaks], and trade-related aspects in the form of common participation in FTAs and RTAs, and imposed NTMs by the importing country.

6 POULTRY

6.1. Network analysis and results of the poultry international market

In this section, the world's major poultry exporters and importers are presented, using data on trade flows from 2010 to 2019. Our data stems from the BACI dataset from CEPII, the leading French center for research and expertise on the world economy. Our sample consists of countries with a value of poultry trade flows greater than 50 million dollars which represents about 5% of total trade. This threshold is used to exclude small trade flows to eliminate unnecessary noise originating from such trades. The detailed list of poultry codes used in this study is found in Appendix A5.

Figure 6.1.1 illustrates the top poultry exporters in the 2010 reference year. This figure enables you to see where each country fits into international trade. According to this, Brazil, the largest economy of Latin America, and the USA are the worldwide leading countries in poultry exports in 2010, based on export value, with a significant difference from the rest of the worldwide exporters. The Netherlands and Hong Kong have also a prominent position in the trade. On the other hand, the remaining countries, Germany, France, Poland, the UK, Denmark, Chile, and China, have a comparably lower trade export value.

Figure 6.1.1

Continuing to Figure 6.1.2, we display the top poultry exporters in the 2013 reference year. We observe a similar interpretation as in Figure 6.1.1. The top poultry exporters are once more Brazil and the USA, followed by the Netherlands. Poland, France, and Germany seem to have a secondary but still significant role, making substantial progress in the rankings. Finally, the UK, China, Chile, and Hungary hold a marginal

position. The figure illustrates, as in Figure 6.1.1, a multi-participation of countries and continents in the ranking of poultry exports.

Figure 6.1.2

Figure 6.1.3, displays poultry exports, for the benchmark year 2016. According to this figure, we have a similar pattern to the reference year 2013. Brazil, the USA, the Netherlands, and Poland are the top poultry exporters. Minor differentiations are the fall of China and the rise of Thailand in fifth place. This graph allows us to stronger recognize the core role of the European countries, the USA, and the Asian pole in the poultry trade.

Figure 6.1.3

Figure 6.1.4, illustrates the most recent data we have, concerning poultry exports, for the benchmark year 2019. This graph offers a similar pattern according to the export trends of the poultry sector for the year 2016. Brazil, the USA, the Netherlands, Poland, and Thailand are in a steady leading position, while Argentina and Turkey have a dynamic shift forward and introduce their prominent role in the poultry sector.

Figure 6.1.4

In the following Figures 6.1.5 through 6.1.8, we present the major poultry importers with the assumptions introduced at the beginning of our analysis. A quite different scenario is depicted in comparison to the poultry export flows. Furthermore, the countries' rankings in the global poultry trade have been inverted.

Figure 6.1.5 illustrates the top poultry importers for the year 2010. Asian countries appear to maintain a dominant position in the import ranking. Hong Kong, Japan, and China hold a prominent role, with the Russian Federation and Vietnam composing a mainstream second pole. The EU is next in the rankings with the presence of the UK, Germany, the Netherlands, and France forming another importing pillar. Based on their import value, Mexico, Saudi Arabia, and South Africa are at the bottom of the rankings. Furthermore, poultry products, that are practically not marketable in Europe, were sold on African markets for a much lower price than local poultry products.

Figure 6.1.5

Figure 6.1.6, which displays the reference year 2013 of poultry importers, has an almost identical visualization, in comparison to Figure 6.1.5. Asia has a dominant role in this graph, with Hong Kong, Japan, and China leading the rankings. A mixed

depiction of a large number of countries follows, with the participation of European, African, and Asian countries.

Figure 6.1.6

Figures 6.1.7 and 6.1.8 illustrate the major poultry importing countries for the benchmark years of 2016 and 2019, respectively. The most notable aspect is the total dominance of Asia's booming economy in the first three positions (China, Japan, and Hong Kong) in the rankings, in terms of importing countries' volume. Countries like Germany, Mexico, France, Vietnam, and Saudi Arabia follow. This graph allows us to stronger recognize the moderate role of the European countries in the ranking.

Figure 6.1.7

Figure 6.1.8

In what follows we shall use metrics of centrality to estimate the heterogeneity of countries in the global trade network. As we have described previously, in social network research, centrality is one of the most widely used topics. A significant number of measures have been developed, including degree centrality, closeness, betweenness, eigenvector centrality, information centrality, flow betweenness, the rush index, and the influence measures.

Each node represents a country in the network, which is denoted with its corresponding 3-code acronym. Different lines connect different countries. These lines represent the volume of the trade flows between the countries depicted. Therefore, in what follows we display our analysis for the visualization of the data. In Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016.

In Figure 6.1.9 we illustrate the poultry network analysis for the year 2019 based on eigenvector centrality (in Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). For every country in the network, we recorded all the trading partners (in correspondence to the study's assumptions) in terms of trade flows in the above years. The structure of the network seems to be quite evident with the USA and Brazil having the leading role, with substantial flows to a large number of nations such as Chile, Japan, and Thailand. Another important player is Asia's rising economy. The top central players, China, Hong Kong, and Vietnam appear to have strong trade flows with several EU countries as well as countries from other continents. Another trading group with lower trade value is Saudi Arabia and South Africa. Finally, the visualizations display Turkey's and Denmark's low rankings in terms of poultry trade flows.

Figure 6.1.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 50m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure 6.1.10 depicts the poultry network analysis for the year 2019 based on authority centrality (in Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe that the USA, Hong Kong, and China are the core players with extensive economic linkages to a variety of European countries and other continents. Furthermore, Chile is a prominent player with extensive trade ties to a number of countries. Another noteworthy feature is Brazil's emergence as a top trading country in 2013, with significant trade flows with several countries. The appearance of South Africa in 2019 reveals a small trade flow in poultry, whereas Saudi Arabia's representation in all reference years reveals the same low trend.

Figure 6.1.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Authority

In terms of centrality hub, Figure 6.1.11 presents the poultry network trade in the reference year 2019 (in Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). A large number of countries appear to have high participation, according to the measure of centrality hub. Across all benchmark years, we observe that the USA, Brazil, and Hong Kong are the leading players, in terms of substantial trade value connections, keeping strong flows between them and other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. On the other hand, several European countries, such as Poland, Denmark, and the Netherlands, maintain a middle position in terms of trade flows. Finally, Kazakhstan appears to have only modest trade ties with the USA, whereas Singapore and Jordan have limited trade flows with Brazil.

Figure 6.1.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Closeness

6.2. Gravity literature review of the poultry international market

Yuan and Awokuse (2003) applied a gravity model to evaluate the impact of medium and long-run exchange rate volatility on USA poultry exports. The model was based on disaggregated trade data of USA poultry exports to 49 countries (selected based on their importance to USA poultry exports, data availability, and the exchange rate regime) between 1976 and 2000. The dependent variable was defined as USA trade flow to the importing country, while independent variables included USA and importer’s per capita GDP, the unit export price of USA poultry (defined by dividing the export value by volume; this way, the distance between countries is also indirectly taken into account, having in mind that export value includes transportation costs), and exchange rate volatility. The model’s results indicate that, on a statistically significant level, exchange rate volatility (based on spot exchange rates) and unit export price harm the USA poultry export, while the importer’s income has a positive effect.

Fassarella *et al.* (2011) applied a gravity model to examine the impact of SPS and TBT measures -introduced by the main international importers- on Brazil’s poultry exports. The model was developed based on disaggregated data (on an HS6-digit

level) for the 1996 to 2009 period. The dependent variable was expressed as Brazil's poultry exports; independent variables included Brazil's and importers' GDP, applied tariffs by the importer, and the existence of SPS or TBT measures imposed by the importer. It should be noted that two different analyses were performed, referring to the SPS and TBT determining variables. The first analysis included a dummy variable indicating the overall existence of NTMs; the second analysis included, instead, five dummy variables, each indicating the existence of different types of introduced SPS and TBTs, classified as product, process, labeling, conformity, and prohibition/restrictions. Each classification included both SPS and TBT measures. Based on the models' results, the importer's and exporter's GDP had a statistically significant positive effect in both cases. Results referring to SPS and TBTs effects are rather indefinite. In the first analysis, the NTM-related variable was not found to be statistically significant; in the second analysis, particular variables had either a positive (labeling, prohibition) or a negative (conformity) effect on Brazil's exports.

Wieck *et al.* (2012a; 2012b) investigated the effect of policies related to Avian Influenza (AI) regulations on poultry meat international trade, based on a gravity model approach. Data involved the 2000-2007 period, and distinguished between uncooked (HS 0207) and cooked meat (HS 160231, 160232, 160239). Concerning the countries included in the model, important poultry meat exporters (Brazil, China, France, Germany, the Netherlands, and the USA) and importers were taken into account (Russia, Japan, remaining countries). The dependent variable is defined as the volume of poultry exports. Independent variables include production quantities of the exporter and consumption quantities of the importer (both instead of the corresponding GDPs), distance, common language [not included in the final model, see Wieck *et al.* (2012a) for detailed process], implementation of import bans, regionalization (expressing the principle of regionalization, i.e., countries allowing producers from non-affected regions within a country to maintain exports), and applied tariffs by the importer. The results concerning the cooked meat, indicate that –on a statistically significant level- exporter's production, importer's consumption, and implementation of bans have a positive effect on trade, while distance has a negative effect. In the case of uncooked meat, distance and implemented bans have a negative effect, while regionalization has a positive effect, all on a statistically significant level.

Davis (2014) applied a gravity model to estimate the short and long-term effects of exchange rate volatility, as well as the effect of regional relationships, on turkey trade flows. The study focused on a specific product category (i.e., turkey) instead of the aggregate poultry trade, based on the assumption that the effect of exchange rate volatility does not affect all products in the same way, due to the differences in biological and marketing factors across products. Data on turkey trade between 1999 and 2008 were used for all turkey exporting and importing countries. The dependent variable was defined as the quantity of imported turkey. Independent variables consisted of importer's and exporter's GDP, importer's and exporter's population, distance, real exchange rate volatility, common border, common language, and a set

of dummy variables indicating if both countries (importer and exporter) are members of the same trade agreement (NAFTA, APEC or the EU-27). Based on the study's statistically significant results, and referring to both the short-term and long-term analyses, exporter's and importer's GDP, exporter's and importer's population, common border, participation in the same trade agreement (NAFTA and EU-27), and exchange rate volatility all have a positive effect on turkey trade. On the other hand, distance (statistically significant only in the long-term analysis) and common language were found to harm trade.

Davis and Taha (2015) examined the effect of exchange rate volatility on Africa's poultry imports, through the application of a gravity model. Data from 2000 to 2012 were used, concerning poultry meat imported by African countries; poultry meats were examined on an HS6-digit level, including chicken meat (HS 02071), turkey meat (HS 02072), and other than chicken or turkey meat (HS 02073-02076). The dependent variable was defined as the quantity of exported poultry; independent variables included the importer's GDP, importer's population, the distance between countries, total poultry exported by the exporter, and the real exchange rate volatility. Two distinct analyses were performed, one examining short-term, and the other long-term exchange rate volatility. Analyses results indicate that both in the short and the long-term, importer's GDP and total poultry exports have a positive effect, while distance and exchange rate volatility hurt the quantity of exported poultry, all on a statistically significant level.

Thompson and Pendell (2016) examined the effects of pathogenic disease events on the poultry trade, prompted by the AI outbreak that occurred in the USA between 2014 and 2015. In this context, 12 poultry categories on an HS6-digit level were individually (i.e., not aggregately) examined for 11 years (2004-2015). The analysis included 24 exporting countries, referring to trading partners that accounted for at least 5% of trade from the exporting country for the base year (2013). Exporting quantity was set as the dependent variable of the gravity model. Independent variables consisted of importer's and exporter's population, importer's and exporter's GDP, distance, the annual share of world export market, a dummy variable indicating if Newcastle Disease (ND) was reported, a dummy variable indicating if HPAI (Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza) was reported, the number of simultaneous disease events in a given year, annual global per capita consumption of poultry meat, common borders, common currency, and a set of dummy variables indicating the geographical location (six continents & the Middle East) of the exporting country. Having in mind that 12 different models were produced (one for each product category), a variety of results can be indicated referring to the statistical significance and the sign of the determining variables. Distance, common currency, importer population, and exporter GDP are the variables being statistically significant in most of the models. On the other hand, in most of the cases, disease-related variables were not found to have a statistically significant effect. Following this, Thompson *et al.* (2020) performed a relevant study, with the main scope, period, involved countries, product categories, and trade determinants being common to the above.

An additional determinant variable was included in the model: a dummy variable indicating the December 2007 to June 2009 Great Recession, accounting for the changes in trade associated with this economic austerity period. The specific analysis indicated varying trade responses to AI outbreaks, depending on the specific poultry product.

Lei and Zhou (2017) and Zhou *et al.* (2019) focused on the impact of AI outbreaks and the following NTMs on international poultry trade, by examining China's exports to its 122 poultry importers (EU countries considered individually) through a gravity model. The analysis differentiated between uncooked (fresh, chilled, and frozen) and cooked (preserved and canned) poultry products (chicken, ducks, and geese), using trade data from 2005 to 2013. On an HS8-digit level, 11 uncooked and eight cooked poultry products were taken into account. The reason for differentiating between cooked and uncooked products was the fact that heat can inactivate AI, leading to different responses between the two product categories, thus enabling an advanced analysis of AI's impacts to trade. Four gravity model analyses were performed. For each one of the product categories (uncooked and cooked poultry), two different dependent variables were taken into account: China's export volume, and China's export value. The independent variables of each model consisted of China's and importers' GDP, distance, common border, and dummy variables indicating a) if the importer is a WTO member, b) if the importer and China are part of the same FTA, c) the occurrence of AI outbreaks in China, d) the occurrence of AI outbreaks in the importing country, and e) the initiation of new NTMs (including SPS and TBT measures) by the importing countries. Based on the analyses results, AI outbreaks in the importing country have a significant negative impact on poultry's imports, in comparison to relevant AI outbreaks occurring in the exporting countries. NTMs initiated due to the AI harm uncooked poultry trade, whereas, a temporary positive effect on cooked poultry trade. Additionally, when referring specifically to uncooked poultry products, the importer's GDP, the importer's membership to WTO, and a common border have a statistically significant positive effect.

Thompson (2018) applied a gravity model to estimate USA poultry exports, on the basis of the country's 2014-2015 AI outbreak, which led to the implementation of relevant trade restrictions by several countries (either on a national or a regional level). Thirty-two (32) importing countries were included in the analysis, namely those representing at least 0.5% of USA trade for the 2010-2014 period. Analyses were performed both on an aggregated (general poultry trade) and a disaggregated (product-specific trade) level, taking into account data between 2010 and 2016. The poultry products taken into account represented at least 1% of USA exports (namely, 14 product codes on the HS9-digit level). Hence, the included products represented 90% of all poultry exports for the 2010-2014 period. The dependent variable was quantity traded, while independent variables consisted of a dummy variable indicating the introduction of trade restriction by the importing country (either on a national level; or on a national, state, or county level), as well as a set of dummy variables defining the importer, the commodity traded and the specific period. The

study's results indicate that the introduction of trade restrictions harms trade, while the impact is diverse across the disaggregated poultry products.

6.3. Conclusions of the poultry international market

The results improved our understanding of international trade and how poultry trade behaves in network analysis. More precisely, the insights of our research emphasize the importance of the USA and Brazil as central trade players, for all benchmark years. Over the years, there are strong network flows between the top countries and other continents. The USA appears to connect strongly with Europe, Asia, and Africa. On the other hand, Brazil appears to be forming an opposite pole, connecting with Russia's, Mexico's, and Korea's massive markets. Furthermore, certain nations, such as Jordan, Sweden, and Malaysia, are on the margin of the trade flow. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top poultry exporters in 2019 are Brazil, the USA, the Netherlands, Poland, Thailand, Chile, Honk Kong, Argentina, and Germany. In the same year, the top importers are China, Japan, Hong Kong, Saudi Arabia, Germany, Mexico, the UK, France, Vietnam, the United Arab Emirates, South Africa, South Korea, the Netherlands, and Iraq.

Based on the literature review performed on gravity models, the main determinants of poultry trade flows consist of importer's and exporter's (per capita) GDP and population, exporter's poultry production, currency aspects (common currency, exchange rate), poultry export price, the distance between the trading countries, geographical position (in terms of common borders), historical and cultural factors (common language), specific market conditions [e.g. bans, economic recession, AI outbreaks], and trade-related aspects in the form of common participation in FTAs and RTAs, and imposed restrictions and NTMs by the importing country.

7 COFFEE

7.1. Network analysis and results of the coffee international market

In this section, the world's major coffee exporters and importers are presented, using data on trade flows from 2010 to 2019. Globally, coffee is the second most traded commodity and thus plays a vital role in the balance of trade between developed and developing countries, providing the latter with an important source of export earnings. Our data stems from the BACI dataset from CEPII, the leading French center for research and expertise on the world economy. Our sample consists of countries with a value of coffee trade flows greater than 100 million dollars which represents about 5% of total trade. This threshold is used to exclude small trade flows to eliminate unnecessary noise originating from such trades. The detailed list of coffee codes used in this study is found in Appendix A6.

Figure 7.1.1 illustrates the leading coffee exporters in the 2010 benchmark year. Brazil is the leading coffee exporter, accounting for roughly 22% of total export volume, followed by Germany, which accounts for nearly a third of Brazil's entire volume. Colombia, Vietnam, and Chile also play a pivotal role in the export trade, albeit in a smaller proportion than the top country. The following countries, Italy, Peru, Belgium, Indonesia, and Guatemala have a comparably lower trade export value, with a ratio of around 4 to 3%. Finally, Canada, Nicaragua, and Uganda have been placed on the margin of the ranking.

Figure 7.1.1

Continuing to Figure 7.1.2, we display the top coffee exporters in the 2013 reference year. A similar pattern can be seen in the preceding graph. Brazil, Germany, Chile, Colombia, and Vietnam remain the top five players, with Vietnam moving up to the second place, with a proportion of around 9%, in terms of export value. The existence of Indonesia's vast market is particularly noteworthy, which appears to have increased its share by about one percentage point. The rest of the countries have a relatively low percentage.

Figure 7.1.2

Figure 7.1.3, displays coffee exporters, for the reference year 2016. According to this figure, we have a similar pattern to the reference year 2013. Brazil, Germany, Chile, Colombia, and Vietnam continue to be at the top of the ranking as the leading coffee exporters. Honduras appears to have maintained its position in the market, whereas Indonesia has lost roughly one percentage point of the market share. The remaining countries have maintained a relatively low proportion of the export flows.

Figure 7.1.3

Figure 7.1.4, illustrates the most recent data we have, concerning coffee exports, for the benchmark year 2019. A similar pattern can be seen as in Figure 7.1.3, with Brazil remaining the top export country, and Vietnam, Germany, Colombia, and Chile following with percentages of around 8%. It is particularly noteworthy, that France has doubled its share in the coffee market.

Figure 7.1.4

In the following Figures 7.1.5 through 7.1.8, we illustrate the major coffee importers with the assumptions introduced at the beginning of our analysis. A quite different scenario is depicted in comparison with the coffee export flows. Furthermore, the countries' rankings in the global coffee trade have been inverted in comparison to the export trends.

Figure 7.1.5 displays the top coffee importers for the reference year 2010. USA's massive market and Germany appear to hold a dominant position in the import ranking, having the largest percentages of approximately 19% and 14% respectively. Asia's emerging economy with the presence of Japan also plays a significant role in the ranking, while the EU, with the presence of France, Belgium, Italy, the Netherlands, and the UK, has roughly equal representation of around 4.5% in terms of import flows. Austria, Chile, and the Russian Federation are at the bottom of the ranking based on their import value.

Figure 7.1.5

Figure 7.1.6, which displays the reference year 2013 of coffee importers, seems to have an almost identical visualization, in comparison to Figure 7.1.5. With a

substantial share of 17% of the import volume, the USA is in the first place. Another noteworthy feature is France’s boosting role in trade, which is reflected in their third-place ranking. A mixed depiction of a large number of countries follows, with the participation of European countries, as well as Australia and Asian countries, holding proportions of approximately 3 to 1.5%.

Figure 7.1.6

In Figure 7.1.7, we present the leading importing countries for the benchmark year of 2016. The USA appears to maintain a dominant position in the import ranking. Germany holds second place, despite a significant disparity of roughly 7% from the first-placed country. The remaining countries are in a steady downward spiral, with Greece in the last ranked position.

Figure 7.1.7

Figure 7.1.8 illustrates the major coffee importing countries for the benchmark year of 2019. USA’s first place is indisputable, followed by Germany which accounts for almost half of the USA import value. In what follows, France maintains the third rank, with a stable proportion of around 6.5%. Furthermore, the sequence of the remaining countries appears to be the same.

Figure 7.1.8

Following, we shall use metrics of centrality to estimate the heterogeneity of countries in the global trade network. As we have described previously, in social network research, centrality is one of the most widely used topics. A significant number of measures have been developed, including degree centrality, closeness, betweenness, eigenvector centrality, information centrality, flow betweenness, the rush index, and the influence measures.

Each node represents a country in the network, which is denoted with its corresponding 3-code acronym. Different lines connect different countries. These lines represent the volume of the trade flows between the countries depicted. Therefore, in what follows we display our analysis for the visualization of the data. In Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016.

In Figure 7.1.9 we display the coffee network analysis for the year 2019 based on eigenvector centrality (in Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). The intensity of trade flows between nations, as well as the large number of countries involved in the coffee trade, can be seen in the network visualization. Furthermore, the network appears to have a mixed structure, with the participation of different poles. Foremost, South America’s appearance is evident with Chile, Colombia, and Brazil having a major role in the trade. In what follows, we observe also Europe having a leading role. More precisely Germany, Italy, the UK, Belgium, and many other nations distinguish in the trade node of coffee, having strong flows with a large number of countries in Europe, as well as with the USA and Brazil. Japan and Indonesia appear to hold a moderate position in the graph. On the contrary, there is a large number of countries that have been placed in the margin of the network, like El Salvador and Slovakia trading connections only with the USA.

Figure 7.1.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019– Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure 7.1.10 illustrates the coffee network analysis for the reference year 2019 based on authority centrality (in Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). Over the years, we observe three significant poles emerging. First, the one from Latin America including Brazil, Chile, Colombia; next, the EU with the participation of a large number of countries, like Italy, Germany, Spain, and France has substantial trade linkages to a variety of other countries and continents. On the other hand, the USA continues to be a prominent player with strong trade ties with Europe, Japan, and Canada. The appearance of Indonesia reveals a small trade flow in coffee, whereas El Salvador's representation especially in 2019 reveals a limited trade connection.

Figure 7.1.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019– Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

In terms of centrality hub, in Figure 7.1.11 we present the coffee network trade in the reference year 2019 (in Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016). A large number of countries appear to have strong participation, according to the measure of centrality hub. Across all benchmark years, we observe that Brazil and Chile are the leading players. The USA represents another substantial pole, in terms of substantial trade value connections, keeping strong flows with other countries. This pattern seems to be stable throughout all reference years. In the same vein is the presence of the EU -including different nations like Germany, Italy, and France- which possesses a core position in the network. On the other hand, several countries, such as Saudi Arabia and Argentina in 2019, or Nicaragua in 2016 maintain a modest position in terms of trade flows.

Figure 7.1.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

In terms of centrality closeness, looking at Figure 7.1.13 (in Appendix B6 you will find the figures for the years 2010, 2013, 2016) we have a similar pattern as in previous visualizations. The coffee trading of many countries like Brazil, Italy, Germany, Chile, France, and Spain, and the intensity of their flows, provide a significant number of central players, with substantial contribution to trade interaction, for all benchmark years. Over the years, there are strong network flows between the top countries and other continents. Japan appears to be forming an additional pole, connecting with different countries. Finally, certain nations, such as Costa Rica in 2016, or Turkey, are on the margin of the coffee trade flows.

Figure 7.1.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2019– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

7.2. Gravity literature review of the coffee international market

Almeida *et al.* (2012), through a gravity model, investigated the impact of TBT and SPS agreements on worldwide green coffee exports. Data took into account the international trade of the five main countries (namely, Brazil, Colombia, Vietnam, Guatemala, and Indonesia) that produce green coffee, for the 1996 to 2010 period. The dependent variable of the model was defined as the value of coffee exports, while independent variables included importer’s and exporter’s GDP, distance, common border, imposed tariffs, and a dummy variable indicating if the importing country had imposed any SPS or TBT-related notifications to the imported coffee. Results showed that coffee exports are positively affected on a statistically significant level by the importer’s GDP, and negatively affected by distance and TBT measures; SPS measures had a negative effect, but it was not statistically significant.

Nugroho (2014) investigated the effect of country-specific regulations on trade in comparison to worldwide complied regulation on food safety standards, by developing a gravity model that focused on Indonesia’s coffee trades. Data took into consideration Indonesia’s coffee trades to 10 major importing countries (accounting for 73% of total coffee export from Indonesia), from 2002-2011, referring to HS4-

digit code 0901. The dependent variable of the model is set as the value of Indonesia's coffee exports. The independent variables included importer's GDP, Indonesia's (i.e., the country under examination) total coffee production lagged one year, distance, maximum residue levels of the Carbaryl pesticide in the importing and exporting country, and two dummy variables indicating policy changes in Indonesia's coffee export (the year 2005 for Japan, and the year 2007 for the EU). The model's results showed that, on a statistically significant level, the importer's GDP and Indonesia's total coffee production lagged one year had a positive effect on coffee exports, while distance and maximum residue levels of the Carbaryl pesticide harmed coffee trade.

Oumer and Rao (2015) analyzed the factors affecting Ethiopia's Sidama coffee exports in the international market, through the application of a gravity model. The data covered the 2002-2005 period (only four years, due to lack of data), taking into account 14 importing countries based on the extent of importing Sidama coffee from Ethiopia, and the availability of trade data. The model's dependent variable was determined to be the value of Ethiopia's Sidama coffee exports, while the independent variables included the exporter's (Ethiopia's) GDP, the product of the importer's and the exporter's GDP, importer's and exporter's population, per capita GDP differential between Ethiopia (the exporter) and the importer, distance, and common border. The results showed that the exporter's GDP and the per capita GDP differential between the exporter and the importer had a statistically significant positive effect on coffee exports, while distance had a negative effect.

Cardoso *et al.* (2016a) and Cardoso *et al.* (2016b) investigated the determinants of Italian coffee imports, by employing a gravity model. Data referred to coffee (not roasted not decaffeinated coffee, not roasted decaffeinated coffee and roasted coffee) import flows of Italy and its 11 main export partners (namely, Brazil, Cameroon, Colombia, Ethiopia, Guatemala, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Tanzania, Uganda, and Vietnam) for the 1995 to 2013 period. The dependent variable of the model is determined as Italian coffee imports, while independent variables comprise of importer's (i.e., Italy's) and exporter's GDP, exporter's coffee production, per capita coffee consumption in Italy, distance, a dummy variable indicating if the exporter is geographically adjacent to the European continent, and a dummy variable indicating the existence of a harbor in the exporting country. The results of the model revealed that, on a statistically significant level, the exporter's GDP, the exporter's coffee production, Italian coffee consumption, and the exporting country being adjacent to Europe enhanced Italian coffee imports, while the distance between Italy and the exporter had an adverse effect on coffee imports.

Vijayasuryan (2017), using a gravity model, investigated the determinants of India's coffee exports in the international market. The data took into account exports to 46 countries, for the 2001-2014 period. The dependent variable of the model was defined as India's coffee exports; independent variables comprised of the importer's GDP, the importer's area, distance, importer's population, common language, FTA or RTA membership, importer's trade openness (estimated by dividing average trade of

country with total GDP) and TCI (Trade Complementary Index) (explaining how well export and import structure of both trading partners complement each other). According to the study's results, the importer's GDP, population, and trade openness, as well as TCI had a statistically positive effect on India's coffee exports.

Bekele and Mersha (2019) explored the factors determining Ethiopia's coffee exports, through a gravity model. Data referred to 71 countries being consistent (i.e., importing Ethiopia's coffee at least once per year throughout the periods of the study) coffee importers from Ethiopia, for the 2005 to 2015 period. The dependent variable was defined as the annual USD (United States Dollar) value of Ethiopian coffee exports. Independent variables included lag of Ethiopia's coffee exports, importer's and exporter's (i.e., Ethiopia's) GDP, importer's and exporter's population, weighted distance, real exchange rate, Ethiopia's institutional quality [index estimated based on six parameters: a) rule of law, b) political stability, and absence of violence or terrorism, c) voice and accountability, d) government effectiveness, e) regulatory quality and f) control of corruption], and importer's and exporter's openness to trade (estimated as the total trade of a country with the world economy divided by its real GDP). The model's results showed that, on a statistically significant level, lagged Ethiopia's coffee exports performance, importer's and exporter's (i.e., Ethiopia's) GDP, the exporter's population, importers' openness to trade, and the exporter's institutional quality enhanced Ethiopia's coffee exports, while distance had a negative influence to exports.

Eshetu and Goshu (2019) applied a gravity model to investigate the factors determining Ethiopia's coffee exports. The data referred to the 1998 to 2016 period, taking into account 31 trading partners of Ethiopia, accounting for 97% of the country's total coffee exports. The dependent variable was determined as the volume of Ethiopian coffee export; independent variables included lag of Ethiopia's coffee exports, importer's and exporter's GDP, importer's and exporter's population, weighted distance, real exchange rate, foreign direct investments of Ethiopia, importer's and exporter's trade openness, and institutional quality index of Ethiopia [estimated based on six indicators –according to the WGI (Worldwide Governance Indicator): corruption control, rule of law, government effectiveness, voice and accountability, regulatory quality and political stability]. Based on the results, exporter's GDP and population, importer's and exporter's trade openness, foreign direct investment, and institutional quality had a statistically significant positive effect on coffee exports, while the lagged export volume, importer's population, real exchange rate, and distance were found to have a negative effect.

Handoyo *et al.* (2019) examined the effect of NTMs on Indonesian coffee export to main importing countries, based on the development of a gravity model. The data covered the 2003 to 2017 period, taking into account Indonesia's coffee (HS4-digit code 0901) exports to its main importer countries, being the USA, Philippines, Japan, Germany, Malaysia, and Italy. The dependent variable of the model was defined as the value of Indonesian coffee exports; independent variables included importer's GDP, exchange rate, distance, SPS measures, and TBT measures. The study's results

indicated that the importer's GDP, exchange rates, and TBT measures had a statistically significant positive effect on Indonesian coffee exports.

Nguyen (2020) used a gravity model to examine the determinants of Vietnam's coffee exports, one of the two most important agricultural products of the country (along with rice). The data referred to the 2000-2018 period, taking into account 35 coffee trading partners of Vietnam, based on the total export value in this period; the product under consideration was "roasted and not roasted coffee", i.e., code 0901 from the HS4-digit level categorization. The dependent variable of the model was identified as Vietnam's coffee export value, while independent variables consisted of importer's and exporter's GDP, importer's population, exchange rate, distance, common border, Vietnam's (i.e., exporter's) openness, and participation in FTAs [namely EU, ASEAN, CPTPP (Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership)]. The results indicated that the importer's and exporter's GDP, common border, and participation in ASEAN had a statistically positive effect on coffee exports, while the importer's population and participation in CPTPP had a negative impact.

Nsabimana and Tirkaso (2020), based on a gravity model, examined the effect of RTAs on coffee exports, specifically focusing on the impact of the EAC (East African Community) and the COMESA (Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa) on eight African countries. Data referred to the 1998-2013 period, taking into account eight Eastern and Southern African countries (i.e., Burundi, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda, and Zambia) as the exporters, and 139 worldwide coffee trading partners. The dependent variable was defined as the value of coffee exports, while independent variables included the importer's and exporter's GDP, importer's and exporter's population, distance, common border, common language, colonial relationship, common colony (meaning, having a common colonizer post-1945), common language, and RTA (i.e., EAC and COMESA) membership. Based on the results, and on a statistically significant level, the importer's and exporter's GDP, exporter's population, common borders, colonial ties, and RTAs had a favorable effect on coffee exports, while the importer's population and distance had an unfavorable effect towards exports.

Abafita and Tadesse (2021) examined the main determinants -with a special focus on RTAs- of global coffee trade flows, by employing a gravity model. The data took into consideration coffee [HS4-digit level code 0901 (roasted and not roasted coffee)] trade flows of 18 major coffee exporters (from three regions of the world: six from Africa, five from Asia, and seven from the Americas) and 201 trading partners (i.e., all the countries for which trade statistics are available) that represent over 90% of world coffee exports in recent years (2008 to 2015), for the period 2001-2015. The dependent variable is expressed as the export quantity/value of coffee; independent variables include importer's and exporter's GDP, importer's and exporter's population, the distance between capital cities, common language, common border, a dummy variable indicating if the exporter was a colony of the importer, real exchange rate, tariffs, a dummy variable indicating if the two countries belong to the

same RTA [EFTA (European Free Trade Association), NAFTA, COMESA, or bilateral agreement), amount of arable land in the exporting country, and infrastructural indices (expressed as % of paved roads). The study's findings indicated that importer's and exporter's GDP, exporter's population, common border, colonial link, common language, depreciation in exporting country's exchange rate, and the amount of arable land in exporting country had a statistically significant positive effect on coffee trade, while the importer's population, distance, tariffs applied by the importing country, the exporter's infrastructure (unlike what was expected) and global financial crisis were found to reduce coffee trade. The RTA variable was found to have no significant effect on the coffee trade.

Feyisa (2021) applied a gravity model to identify Ethiopia's coffee exports to its main trading partners. The data covered the 2011-2016 period, taking into account Ethiopia's coffee exports to 18 countries (based on trading partners' importance as an export destination for Ethiopia, and availability of data). The dependent variable of the model was determined as the value of Ethiopia's coffee exports, while the independent variables comprised of the importer's and exporter's GDP (i.e., Ethiopia's), weighted distance, importer's and exporter's population, real exchange rate, and foreign direct investment flow to Ethiopia. Based on the model's results, the importer's GDP and the exporter's (i.e., Ethiopia's) population have a statistically significant positive effect on coffee exports, while distance and -in contrary to what was expected- foreign direct investment flow to Ethiopia, had a negative effect.

7.3. Conclusions of the coffee international market

Our research on coffee network analysis provides the following insights: a) the presence of strong trade flows between nations, b) the large number of countries involved in the coffee trade, and c) the network's mixed structure with the participation of different poles. Foremost, South's America appearance is evident with Chile, Colombia, and Brazil having a leading role in the trade. On the other hand, Europe has a significant role in the network. More precisely Germany, Italy, the UK, Belgium, and many other nations pick out in the trade node of coffee, having substantial flows with a large number of countries in Europe, as well as with the USA and Brazil. Japan and Indonesia appear to hold a moderate position in the network. On the contrary, there are a large number of countries that have been placed in the margin of the network, like El Salvador and Slovakia. Finally, the statistical analysis presented via bar charts shows that the top coffee exporters in 2019 are Brazil, Vietnam, Germany, Colombia, Switzerland, Italy, France, Honduras, Indonesia, Ethiopia, the Netherlands, Belgium, the USA, Guatemala, and Peru. In the same year, the top importers are the USA, Germany, France, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, Japan, Canada, Spain, the UK, Poland, and South Korea.

Based on the literature review performed on gravity models, the main determinants of coffee trade flows consist of importer's and exporter's (per capita) GDP and population, exporter's coffee production, importer's coffee consumption, amount of

arable land in exporting country, trade openness, foreign direct investments, exchange rate, the distance between the trading countries, geographical position (in terms of common borders), historical and cultural factors (common language, colonial ties), specific market conditions [e.g. maximum pesticide residue levels, global financial crisis], institutional quality, and trade-related aspects in the form of common participation in FTAs and RTAs, and imposed tariffs and NTMs by the importing country.

8 Overview of the literature review and empirical findings

Table 8.1 illustrates the dominant trading partners and the trade between these partners

Table. 8.1 Main findings of Network Analysis

	Wine	Dairy	Beef	Pork	Poultry	Coffee
Dominant Trade Partners	France Italy Spain Australia Chile	Germany New Zealand France Netherlands USA	Australia Brazil USA Argentina India	Germany USA Denmark Canada Netherlands	Brazil USA Netherlands Poland Thailand	Brazil Vietnam Germany Colombia Switzerland
Main Regions/ Countries Trading with Asia	Latin America	France UK	Brazil Italy	Germany Canada UK	Brazil USA	USA EU
Main Regions/ Countries Trading with Latin America (MERCOSUR)	Asia	Germany Netherlands	Asia Netherlands USA	China Canada	China USA	UK EU

Table 8.2 presents a grouped representation of the statistically significant variables and their impacts on trade flows obtained from the gravity model literature review for wine, dairy, beef, pork, poultry, and coffee products. Note that a positive [+] sign indicates a positive impact while a negative [-] sign an adverse effect of the variables presented on the first column on trade flows of the six products.

Table 8.2. Gravity model literature review: Statistically significant effects of important variables on trade flows

	Wine	Dairy	Beef	Pork	Poultry	Coffee
TRADE COMPETITIVENESS						
importer's trade openness (dividing country's trade with total GDP)						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Vijayasuryan, 2017; Bekele and Mersha, 2019; Eshetu and Goshu, 2019
exporter's trade openness (dividing country's trade with total GDP)						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Eshetu and Goshu, 2019

TCI (Trade Complementary Index) (explaining how well the export and import structure of both trading partners complement each other)						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Vijayasuryan, 2017
level of monopolistic competition	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ayuda et al., 2020					
product quality	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Macedo et al., 2019					
unit price of exports	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Dascal et al., 2002		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Cao and Johnson, 2012		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Yuan and Awokuse, 2003	
unit price of imports	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Dascal et al., 2002					
export price	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Castillo et al., 2016					
ratio between exporter's and importer's prices			<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Tian et al., 2021			
exporter's cost function (estimated based on productivity, cattle price, labor wage, and capital rent)			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ghazalian, 2019			
transportation cost	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ayuda et al., 2020			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Prentice et al., 1998		
exchange rate	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002 <u>Effect on imports:</u>		Effect on exports: [-] Banda and Kalaba, 2021;	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Shahriar et al., 2019		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Handoyo et al., 2019 [-] Eshetu and Goshu, 2019

	[-] Dascal et al., 2002					
depreciation in exporting country's exchange rate						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Abafita and Tadesse, 2021
exchange rate volatility			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Karemera et al., 2015	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Boisson, 2011	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Davis and Taha, 2015 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Davis, 2014 [-] Yuan and Awokuse, 2003	
golden standard	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ayuda et al., 2020					
common currency	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Macedo et al., 2019					
TRADE REGIMES						
EU membership	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002; De Blasi et al., 2007 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Owen and Winchester, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Karemera et al., 2015			
importer having initiated EU Accession Negotiations	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] De Blasi et al., 2007					
Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs)	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Balogh and Jámbor, 2018	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ishaqa et al., 2015 [-] Owen and Winchester, 2014	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Fadeyi et al., 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Peci and Sanjuán, 2020		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020

Free Trade Agreements (FTAs)		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Pokrivcak et al., 2013 [-] Schaak, 2015 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Hndi et al., 2016	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Gervais et al., 2011; Karemera et al., 2015; Labraga, 2015; Darbandi et al., 2021 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Shang and Glynn, 2014; Zhang et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2021 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Wilson et al., 2003; Zongo and Larue, 2019		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Davis, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Nguyen, 2020 [-] Nguyen, 2020
Preferential trade agreements		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013				
Bilateral treaty	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Pinilla and Serrano, 2008					
WTO membership	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Balogh and Jámbor, 2018			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Boisson, 2011; Shahriar et al., 2019	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Lei and Zhou, 2017; Zhou et al., 2019	
World War I	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Pinilla and Serrano, 2008; Ayuda et al., 2020					

Great Depression	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ayuda et al., 2020					
Soviet Union establishment	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ayuda et al., 2020					
North American Prohibition	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ayuda et al., 2020					
China's 2008 milk crisis		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ishaqa et al., 2015 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Sun et al., 2014				
Russian ban on imports		Effect on trade flow: [-] Kontsevaya et al., 2020				
initiation of the "Belt and Road" initiative (for China as exporter)				<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Shahriar et al., 2019		
global financial crisis					<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Abafita and Tadesse, 2021	
tariffs	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Dal Bianco et al., 2016	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Kalaba and Kirsten, 2012; Owen and Winchester, 2014; Berndt and Hess, 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Sanjuán López et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Gervais et al., 2011; Cao and Johnson, 2012 [-] Ghazalian, 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u>			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Abafita and Tadesse, 2021

			[-] Kotchoni and Larue, 2011; Zongo and Larue, 2019			
NTMs		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Kalaba and Kirsten, 2012 [-] Kalaba and Kirsten, 2012; Pokrivcak et al., 2013 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Sanjuan et al., 2017			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Fassarella et al., 2011 [-] Fassarella et al., 2011; Lei and Zhou, 2017; Zhou et al., 2019	
TBTs	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Dal Bianco et al., 2016; Macedo et al., 2020 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Santeramo et al., 2019 [-] Santeramo et al., 2019			<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Peci and Sanjuán, 2020		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Handoyo et al., 2019 [-] Almeida et al., 2012
SPSs	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Macedo et al., 2020 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Santeramo et al., 2019		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Zhang et al., 2020 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Zongo and Larue, 2019	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Peci and Sanjuán, 2020 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Shang and Tonsor, 2019		
pre-shipment inspections	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Santeramo et al., 2019					
export-related measures	<u>Effect on imports:</u>					

	[+] Santeramo et al., 2019					
Implementation of bans by the importer					<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Wieck et al., 2012a; Wieck et al., 2012b	
regionalization (i.e., countries allowing producers from non-affected regions within a country to maintain exports)					<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Wieck et al., 2012a; Wieck et al., 2012b	
strict commercial policies imposed by the importer	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Pinilla and Serrano, 2008					
regulatory measures			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Banda and Kalaba, 2021			
trade restriction by the importing country					<u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Thompson, 2018	
INNOVATION IN THE AGRI-FOOD SECTOR AND FOOD PRODUCT QUALITY						
EU ban on the USA and Canadian beef that is hormone-treated			<u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Wilson et al. 2003			
beef dispute between EU and USA			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Labraga, 2015			
regulation divergence (expressed through the Heterogeneity Indexes of Trade) for pesticides and veterinary drugs			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Gervais et al., 2011			
maximum residue levels of the Carbaryl pesticide in the importing country					<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Nugroho, 2014	

more stringent tetracycline residue standards in the importing country			<u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Wilson et al., 2003			
BSE (Bovine spongiform encephalopathy) outbreaks in the exporter			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Shang and Glynn, 2014 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2021 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Zongo and Larue, 2019			
BSE outbreaks in the importer			<u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Zongo and Larue, 2019			
FMD (Foot and mouth disease) outbreaks in the exporter			<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Zongo and Larue, 2019	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012		
FMD outbreaks in the importer			<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Zongo and Larue, 2019	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012		

FMD outbreaks and status in the exporting and importing countries			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Karemera et al., 2015; Labraga, 2015			
H1N1 outbreak in exporter				<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Boisson, 2011		
AI (Avian influenza) outbreaks in the importer					<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Lei and Zhou, 2017; Zhou et al., 2019	
consumer awareness about safety events (i.e. foodborne-disease news)			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Darbandi et al., 2021			
GDP / INCOME						
exporter's GDP	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002; Castillo et al., 2016; Balogh and Jámbor, 2018; Zaninovic et al., 2021 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002; Zaninovic et al., 2021	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Pokrivcak et al., 2013; Fathelrahman et al., 2014 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Hndi et al., 2016; Kontsevaya et al., 2020	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Cao and Johnson, 2012 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Zhang et al., 2020 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Wilson et al., 2003; Fadeyi et al., 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012; Shahriar et al., 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Peci and Sanjuán, 2020	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Fassarella et al., 2011 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Davis, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Oumer and Rao, 2015; Bekele and Mersha, 2019; Eshetu and Goshu, 2019; Nguyen, 2020; Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020; Abafita and Tadesse, 2021 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Cardoso et al., 2016a; Cardoso et al., 2016b
exporter's agricultural GDP				<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Boisson, 2011		
importer's GDP	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002; Pinilla and	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Pokrivcak et al., 2013; Fathelrahman	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Cao and Johnson,	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Boisson, 2011;	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Fassarella et al.,	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Almeida et al., 2012; Nugroho,

	Serrano, 2008; Castillo et al., 2016; Dal Bianco et al., 2016; Balogh and Jámbror, 2018; Gouveia et al., 2018; Macedo et al., 2019; Zaninovic et al., 2021 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002; Zaninovic et al., 2021	et al., 2014; Berndt and Hess, 2019 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Hndi et al., 2016; Kontsevaya et al., 2020	2012; Shang and Glynn, 2014 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2021 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Wilson et al. (2003); Fadeyi et al., 2014	Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012; Shahriar et al., 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Peci and Sanjuán, 2020	2011; Davis and Taha, 2015; Lei and Zhou, 2017; Zhou et al., 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Yuan and Awokuse, 2003; Davis, 2014	2014; Vijayasuryan, 2017; Bekele and Mersha, 2019; Handoyo et al., 2019; Nguyen, 2020; Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020; Abafita and Tadesse, 2021; Feyisa, 2021
exporter's per capita GDP		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ishaqa et al., 2015 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Karemera et al., 2015; Ghazalian, 2019 [-] Banda and Kalaba, 2021	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Shahriar et al., 2019		
importer's per capita GDP	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] De Blasi et al., 2007; Pinilla and Serrano, 2008; Gouveia et al., 2018; Macedo et al., 2020	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ishaqa et al., 2015	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Karemera et al., 2015; Ghazalian, 2019; Banda and Kalaba, 2021	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Shahriar et al., 2019 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Shang and Tonsor, 2019		
per capita income difference between importer & exporter		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Sanjuán López et al., 2013				<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Oumer and Rao, 2015
importer's expenditure			<u>Effect on trade flow:</u>			

			[+] Zongo and Larue, 2019			
importer's disposal income				<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Prentice et al., 1998		
POPULATION/ AREA						
exporter's population		<u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Hndi et al., 2016	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Cao and Johnson, 2012; Karemera et al., 2015 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Wilson et al., 2003; Fadeyi et al., 2014		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Davis, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Bekele and Mersha, 2019; Eshetu and Goshu, 2019; Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020; Abafita and Tadesse, 2021; Feyisa, 2021
importer's population		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Fathelrahman et al., 2014 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Hndi et al., 2016	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Karemera et al., 2015 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Wilson et al., 2003; Fadeyi et al., 2014		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Davis, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Vijayasuryan, 2017 [-] Eshetu and Goshu, 2019; Nguyen, 2020; Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020; Abafita and Tadesse, 2021
importer's total area				<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Shahriar et al., 2019		
amount of arable land in exporting country						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Abafita and Tadesse, 2021
PRODUCTION/ CONSUMPTION						
production index	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002					

	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Dascal et al., 2002					
exporter's production	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] De Blasi et al., 2007; Dal Bianco et al., 2016; Ayuda et al., 2020	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Sun et al., 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Karemera et al., 2015; Darbandi et al., 2021 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Zongo and Larue, 2019	<u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Shang and Tonsor, 2019		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Cardoso et al., 2016a; Cardoso et al., 2016b
exporter's lagged production	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ayuda et al., 2020					<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Nugroho, 2014; Bekele and Mersha, 2019 [-] Eshetu and Goshu, 2019
importer's production	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Dal Bianco et al., 2016; Ayuda et al., 2020	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ishaqa et al., 2015	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Cao and Johnson, 2012	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Prentice et al., 1998 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Shang and Tonsor, 2019		
importer's lagged production	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ayuda et al., 2020					
importer's demand	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Lombardi et al., 2016		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ghazalian, 2019			

exporter's supply capacity			<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ghazalian, 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Tian et al., 2021		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Davis and Taha, 2015	
importer's per capita consumption	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Gouveia et al., 2018					
importer's consumption						<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Cardoso et al., 2016a; Cardoso et al., 2016b
GEOGRAPHY						
distance	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Dascal et al., 2002 [-] Pinilla and Serrano, 2008; Castillo et al., 2016; Lombardi et al., 2016; Balogh and Jámbor, 2018; Zaninovic et al., 2021 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Dascal et al., 2002; Zaninovic et al., 2021	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Pokrivcak et al., 2013; Fathelrahman et al., 2014; Owen and Winchester, 2014 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013; Sanjuán López et al., 2013 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Hndi et al., 2016	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Gervais et al., 2011; Cao and Johnson, 2012; Karemera et al., 2015; Ghazalian, 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Shang and Glynn, 2014; Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018; Tian et al., 2021 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [-] Wilson et al., 2003; Kotchoni and Larue, 2011; Fadeyi et al., 2014; Zongo and Larue, 2019	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Peci and Sanjuán, 2020	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Wieck et al., 2012a; Wieck et al., 2012b; Davis and Taha, 2015 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Davis, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Almeida et al., 2012; Nugroho, 2014; Oumer and Rao, 2015; Bekele and Mersha, 2019; Eshetu and Goshu, 2019; Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020; Abafita and Tadesse, 2021; Feyisa, 2021 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Cardoso et al., 2016a; Cardoso et al., 2016b

country remoteness		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Sanjuán López et al., 2013				
latitude difference		<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Sanjuán López et al., 2013				
landlocked	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Balogh and Jámbor, 2018; Gouveia et al., 2018	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Ishaqa et al., 2015 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Gervais et al., 2011	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Shahriar et al., 2019		
common border		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Pokrivcak et al., 2013; Owen and Winchester, 2014; Ishaqa et al., 2015 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013; Sanjuán López et al., 2013	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Shang and Glynn, 2014; Karemera et al., 2015; Ghazalian, 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Shang and Glynn, 2014; Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Kotchoni and Larue, 2011; Fadeyi et al., 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Shahriar et al., 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Peci and Sanjuán, 2020	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Lei and Zhou, 2017; Zhou et al., 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Davis, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Nguyen, 2020; Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020; Abafita and Tadesse, 2021
HISTORICAL / CULTURAL TIES						
common language	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Pinilla and Serrano, 2008; Castillo et al., 2016;	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Pokrivcak et al., 2013; Owen and Winchester,	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Gervais et al., 2011; Ghazalian, 2019	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012; Shahriar	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [-] Davis, 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Abafita and Tadesse, 2021

	Dal Bianco et al., 2016; Lombardi et al., 2016; Balogh and Jámbor, 2018; Gouveia et al., 2018; Macedo et al., 2019	2014; Ishaqa et al. (2015) <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013; Sanjuán López et al., 2013 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Hndi et al., 2016	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Kotchoni and Larue, 2011; Fadeyi et al., 2014	et al., 2019		
common religion	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Balogh and Jámbor, 2018					
religion of the importing country (i.e., Muslim)				<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012		
colonial ties	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Balogh and Jámbor, 2018	<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Haq and Ishaq, 2008; Haq et al., 2013; Sanjuán López et al., 2013	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Ghazalian, 2019 <u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Webb et al., 2017; Webb et al., 2018 <u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Wilson et al., 2003; Fadeyi et al., 2014	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Yang, 2012; Yang et al. 2012		<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Nsabimana and Tirkaso, 2020; Abafita and Tadesse, 2021
common historical ties		<u>Effect on trade flow:</u> [+] Kontsevaya et al., 2020				
common legal system			<u>Effect on imports:</u> [+] Webb et al.,			

			2017; Webb et al., 2018			
emigrant community of the exporter, in the importer	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Gouveia et al., 2018					
CLIMATE / WEATHER						
importer's mean temperature	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Macedo et al., 2020					
importer's climate anomalies	<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Macedo et al., 2020					
INSTITUTIONAL / INFRASTRUCTURE / INVESTMENT						
exporter's institutional quality [index estimated based on six indicators –according to the WGI (Worldwide Governance Indicator): corruption control, rule of law, government effectiveness, voice and accountability, regulatory quality and political stability]						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Bekele and Mersha, 2019; Eshetu and Goshu, 2019
exporter's infrastructure (expressed as % of paved roads)						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [-] Abafita and Tadesse, 2021
foreign direct investment						<u>Effect on exports:</u> [+] Eshetu and Goshu, 2019 [-] Feyisa, 2021

Table 8.3 illustrates a grouped representation of the variables and their impacts on trade flows obtained from the estimation of gravity models for wine, dairy, and beef products. Note that a positive (+) sign indicates a positive impact while a negative (-) sign an adverse effect of the variables presented on the first column on trade flows of the three products.

Table 8.3. Gravity model empirical results: Statistically significant effects of important variables on trade flows for three products

	Wine	Dairy	Beef
TRADE REGIMES			
Importer's MFN applied rates	Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -	
Importer's Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards	Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -	
Importer's Technical Barriers to Trade		Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -
Importer's Other non-tariff measures	Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -
Regional trade agreements	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +
GDP / INCOME			
Importer's per capita GDP	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +
PRODUCTION/ CONSUMPTION			
Exporter's production	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +
GEOGRAPHY			
Distance	Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -
COMPETITIVENESS			
EU exports relative to the average World exports	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: -
EU imports relative to the average World exports		Effect on trade flows: -	
Within EU trade relative to the average World trade			Effect on trade flows: +
MERCOSUR exports relative to the average World exports			Effect on trade flows: +
Trade between the UK and non-EU countries relative to the average World trade	Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -
Trade between the EU and African countries relative to the average World trade		Effect on trade flows: -	Effect on trade flows: -
HISTORICAL / CULTURAL TIES			
Common Language		Effect on trade flows: +	Effect on trade flows: +
CLIMATE / WEATHER			
Exporter's Temperature	Effect on trade flows: +		
Importer's Temperature			
Exporter's Precipitation	Effect on trade flows: +		
Importer's Precipitation			

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Appendix A1

COUNTRY	3 ISO CODE
Afghanistan	AFG
Albania	ALB
Algeria	DZA
Argentina	ARG
Aruba	ABW
Australia	AUS
Austria	AUT
Azerbaijan	AZE
Belarus	BLR
Belgium	BEL
Brazil	BRA
Bulgaria	BGR
Canada	CAN
Chile	CHL
China	CHN
Colombia	COL
Comoros (the)	COM
Congo (the Democratic Republic of the)	COD
Costa Rica	CRI
Croatia	HRV
Cuba	CUB
Cyprus	CYP
Czechia	CZE

Denmark	DNK
Dominica	DMA
Dominican Republic (the)	DOM
Ecuador	ECU
Egypt	EGY
El Salvador	SLV
Eritrea	ERI
Estonia	EST
Ethiopia	ETH
Faroe Islands (the)	FRO
Fiji	FJI
Finland	FIN
France	FRA
French Guiana	GUF
Georgia	GEO
Germany	DEU
Ghana	GHA
Gibraltar	GIB
Greece	GRC
Guatemala	GTM
Honduras	HND
Hong Kong	HKG
Hungary	HUN
Iceland	ISL
India	IND

Indonesia	IDN
Iran (Islamic Republic of)	IRN
Iraq	IRQ
Ireland	IRL
Israel	ISR
Italy	ITA
Jamaica	JAM
Japan	JPN
Jordan	JOR
Kazakhstan	KAZ
Kenya	KEN
Korea (the Democratic People's Republic of)	PRK
Korea (the Republic of)	KOR
Kuwait	KWT
Latvia	LVA
Libya	LBY
Liechtenstein	LIE
Lithuania	LTU
Luxembourg	LUX
Madagascar	MDG
Malawi	MWI
Malaysia	MYS
Mali	MLI
Malta	MLT
Mauritania	MRT

Mauritius	MUS
Mayotte	MYT
Mexico	MEX
Moldova (the Republic of)	MDA
Monaco	MCO
Mongolia	MNG
Montenegro	MNE
Morocco	MAR
Mozambique	MOZ
Myanmar	MMR
Netherlands (the)	NLD
New Zealand	NZL
Nicaragua	NIC
Niger (the)	NER
Nigeria	NGA
Norway	NOR
Papua New Guinea	PNG
Paraguay	PRY
Peru	PER
Philippines (the)	PHL
Poland	POL
Portugal	PRT
Qatar	QAT
Republic of North Macedonia	MKD
Romania	ROU

Russian Federation (the)	RUS
Rwanda	RWA
Saudi Arabia	SAU
Senegal	SEN
Serbia	SRB
Sierra Leone	SLE
Singapore	SGP
Slovakia	SVK
Slovenia	SVN
Somalia	SOM
South Africa	ZAF
South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands	SGS
South Sudan	SSD
Spain	ESP
Sri Lanka	LKA
Sweden	SWE
Switzerland	CHE
Syrian Arab Republic	SYR
Taiwan (Province of China)	TWN
Tajikistan	TJK
Tanzania, United Republic of	TZA
Thailand	THA
Tunisia	TUN
Turkey	TUR
Turkmenistan	TKM

Turks and Caicos Islands (the)	TCA
Uganda	UGA
Ukraine	UKR
United Arab Emirates (the)	ARE
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (the)	GBR
United States Minor Outlying Islands (the)	UMI
United States of America (the)	USA
Uruguay	URY
Vanuatu	VUT
Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)	VEN
Viet Nam	VNM

Appendix A2-Dairy

Product	HS6 - digit
Dairy produce; milk and cream, not concentrated, not containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, of a fat content not exceeding 1% (by weight)	040110
Dairy produce; milk and cream, not concentrated, not containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, of a fat content exceeding 6% (by weight)	040130
Dairy produce; milk and cream, not concentrated, not containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, of a fat content exceeding 1% but not exceeding 6% (by weight)	040120
Dairy produce; milk and cream, concentrated or containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, in powder, granules or other solid forms, of a fat content not exceeding 1.5% (by weight)	040210
Dairy produce; milk and cream, concentrated, not containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, in powder, granules or other solid forms, of a fat content exceeding 1.5% (by weight)	040221

Dairy produce; milk and cream, containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, in powder, granules or other solid forms, of a fat content exceeding 1.5% (by weight)	040229
Dairy produce; milk and cream, concentrated, not containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, other than in powder, granules or other solid forms	040291
Dairy produce; milk and cream, containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, other than in powder, granules or other solid forms	040299
Dairy produce; yogurt, whether or not concentrated or containing added sugar or other sweetening matter or flavoured or containing added fruit or cocoa	040310
Dairy produce; buttermilk, curdled milk or cream, kephir, fermented or acidified milk or cream, whether or not concentrated or containing added sweetening, flavouring, fruit or cocoa (excluding yogurt)	040390
Dairy produce; whey, whether or not concentrated or containing added sugar or other sweetening matter	040410
Dairy produce; natural milk constituents (excluding whey), whether or not containing added sugar or other sweetening matter, n.e.s. in chapter 04	040490
Dairy produce; butter and other fats and oils derived from milk	040500
Dairy produce; fresh cheese (including whey cheese), not fermented, and curd	040610
Dairy produce; cheese of all kinds, grated or powdered	040620
Dairy produce; cheese, processed (not grated or powdered)	040630
Dairy produce; cheese, blue-veined (not grated, powdered or processed)	040640
Dairy produce; cheese (not grated, powdered or processed), n.e.s. in heading no. 0406	040690

Appendix A3-Beef

Product	HS6 - digit
Meat; of bovine animals, carcasses and half-carcasses, fresh or chilled	020110
Meat; of bovine animals, cuts with bone in (excluding carcasses and half-carcasses), fresh or chilled	020120
Meat; of bovine animals, boneless cuts, fresh or chilled	020130
Meat; of bovine animals, carcasses and half-carcasses, frozen	020210
Meat; of bovine animals, cuts with bone in (excluding carcasses and half-carcasses), frozen	020220
Meat; of bovine animals, boneless cuts, frozen	020230

Appendix A4-Pork

Product	HS6 - digit
Meat; of swine, carcasses and half-carcasses, fresh or chilled	020311
Meat; of swine, hams, shoulders and cuts thereof, with bone in, fresh or chilled	020312
Meat; of swine, n.e.s. in item no. 0203.1, fresh or chilled	020319
Meat; of swine, carcasses and half-carcasses, frozen	020321
Meat; of swine, hams, shoulders and cuts thereof, with bone in, frozen	020322
Meat; of swine, n.e.s. in item no. 0203.2, frozen	020329

Appendix A5 -Poultry

Product	HS6 - digit
Meat and edible offal; poultry, not cut in pieces, fresh or chilled	020711
Meat & Offal Of Chickens, not Cut In Pieces, frozen	020722

Chicken Cuts & Edible Offal (incl Liver) Fresh/chilled	020713
Chicken Cuts And Edible Offal (inc Livers), Frozen	020714
Turkeys, Not Cut In Pieces, Fresh Or Chilled	020724
Turkeys, Not Cut In Pieces, Frozen	020725
Turkey Cuts & Edible Offal (incl Liver) Fresh/chilled	020726
Turkey Cuts And Edible Offal (incl Liver) Frozen	020727
Meat Of Ducks, Fresh Or Chilled, Not Cut In Pieces	020741
Meat Of Ducks, Frozen, Not Cut In Pieces	020742
Fatty Livers Of Ducks, Fresh Or Chilled	020743
Cuts And Offal Of Ducks, Exc Livers, Fresh/chilled	020744
Cuts And Offal Of Ducks, Frozen	020745
Meat Of Geese, Fresh Or Chilled, Not Cut In Pieces	020751
Meat Of Geese, Frozen, Not Cut In Pieces	020752
Fatty Livers Of Geese, Fresh Or Chilled	020753
Cuts And Offal Of Geese, Exc Livers, Fresh/chilled	020754
Meat, Offal Of Guinea Fowls, Fresh, Chilled Frozen	020760

Appendix A6-Coffee

Coffee; not roasted or decaffeinated	090111
Coffee; decaffeinated, not roasted	090112
Coffee; roasted, not decaffeinated	090121
Coffee; roasted, decaffeinated	090122
Coffee; husks and skins	090130

Appendix B1

Figure B1.1

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B1.2

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B1.3

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B1.4

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B1.5

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B1.6

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B1.7

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B1.8

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B1.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B1.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B1.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B1.14

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B1.15

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Appendix B2

Figure B2.1

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B2.2

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B2.3

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B2.4

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B2.5

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B2.6

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B2.7

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B2.8

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B2.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B2.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B2.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B2.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B2.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B2.14

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B2.15

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Appendix B3

Figure B3.1

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B3.2

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B3.3

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B3.4

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B3.5

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B3.6

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B3.7

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B3.8

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B3.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B3.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B3.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B3.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B3.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010– Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B3.14

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B3.15

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

Appendix B4

Figure B4.1

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B4.2

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B4.3

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B4.4

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B4.5

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B4.6

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B4.7

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B4.8

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B4.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B4.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B4.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B4.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B4.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B4.14

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B4.15

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 90m USD

Centrality Closeness

Appendix B5

Figure B5.1

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 50m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B5.2

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 50m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B5.3

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 50m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B5.4

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B5.5

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B5.6

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Authority

Figure B5.7

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B5.8

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B5.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B5.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B5.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B5.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B5.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B5.14

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B5.15

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016 – Threshold 50m USD

Centrality Closeness

Appendix 6

Figure B6.1

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010– Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B6.2

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B6.3

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 100m USD

Eigenvector Centrality

Figure B6.4

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010– Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B6.5

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B6.6

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 100m USD

Authority Centrality

Figure B6.7

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B6.8

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B6.9

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Hub

Figure B6.10

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B6.11

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B6.12

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Betweenness

Figure B6.13

Network Analysis – All Countries 2010– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B6.14

Network Analysis – All Countries 2013– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

Figure B6.15

Network Analysis – All Countries 2016– Threshold 100m USD

Centrality Closeness

